

DIPARTIMENTO DI STORIA CULTURE CIVILTÀ - DISCI

CORSO DI LAUREA MAGISTRALE IN
SCIENZE STORICHE E ORIENTALISTICHE – CURRICULUM GLOBAL CULTURES

INDENTURED SHADOWS: TAMIL PLANTATION SERVITUDE IN BRITISH CEYLON

Tesi di laurea magistrale in OCEANIC STUDIES (I.C.) (LM)

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Sessione III

Anno Accademico 2023/2024

Acknowledgements

I am deeply grateful to my supervisor, Professor Karin Pallaver, for the insightful support and guidance given throughout this research.

I would also like to thank my co-supervisor, Professor Chiara Petrolini, for the support given at the latter stages of this research.

A truly special thanks to the various institutions in Sri Lanka who hosted me during my research visit. First and foremost, to Ramla Wahab-Salman, Executive Director at the *American Institute for Lankan Studies*, and the team there whose support and guidance opened doors to a variety of research opportunities across the country. Other institutions and teams whose support made this research possible include Dr. Mario Gomez and the team at the *International Centre for Ethnic Studies* in Colombo and Kandy, *The Department of National Archives* in Colombo, the *Satyodaya Centre for Social Research and Encounter*, and the *University of Peradeniya*.

I would also like to acknowledge the financial support provided by the *University of Bologna*, which enabled me to pursue this research.

As always, the support provided by my family from afar is never forgotten and keeps me going.

Lastly, none of this would have been possible without the strength found in sharing endless study days and nights with the beautiful people in *GLoC*.

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Introduction

On 13th August 2024, the Sri Lankan *Daily Mirror* newspaper published a news story entitled “Sajith signs agreement with Tamil Progressive Alliance to grant equal rights to estate community”.¹ Sajith Premadasa, the Leader of the Opposition, pledged to grant equal rights and opportunities to the estate community in Sri Lanka. He noted that this was a “social contract” that would ensure “that the estate community... will not be treated merely as labourers” but enjoy equal opportunities in political, educational, health, and economic areas of society.²

This news story, simply occupying a small area of one page, is the current state of a story of migration beginning just under two hundred years ago and reflects on the complex image of power and identity that permeates the island of Sri Lanka. The estate workers referenced in the news article are primarily descendants of the Indian Tamils that migrated from the Tamil Nadu region of southern India. Their migration into Ceylon began in 1827 when George Bird, a pioneering planter, made a request for labourers to Governor Sir Edward Barnes.³ Since then, the Indian Tamil population grew dramatically through the decades, eventually making up 12.9 per cent of the total population in 1911. This was the first census in which the British showed them as a separate group to the Sri Lankan Tamils who had resided in Sri Lanka for millennia prior.⁴ Upon arrival they had to adapt to a new environment beset with a multitude of historical and political factors that shaped their position in society.⁵ On the other hand, their arrival served to be a disruptive one that had ramifications on the existing intersection of peoples that already called this island their home.

Indeed, the news article in question alludes to some of these historical and political factors that have characterised Sri Lankan history. Firstly, Sajith Premadasa is a politician who has, as shown through the newspaper article, historically championed the rights of Tamil people in Sri Lanka. This is reflected in the results of the 2024 Sri Lankan Presidential election that he was campaigning for at the time, where he received a majority of the vote in the Tamil-majority areas of Sri Lanka. The eventual winner, however, was Anura Kumara Dissanayake who generally won in areas whose majority is composed of Sinhalese people.⁶ This victory for the candidate broadly favoured by Sinhalese people highlights not only the fractured nature of Sri Lanka, but the skewed positions of power that have historically defined Sri Lankan history.

¹ *Daily Mirror*, 13th August 2024

² *Daily Mirror*, 13th August 2024

³ Nadarajan, V., *History of Ceylon Tamils*, Toronto, Vasantham, 1999, pp. 123-125

⁴ Chandrabose, A.S., “Cultural Identity of Indian Tamils in Sri Lanka: A Measurement of Multi-Dimensional Status of the Indian Tamil Society in Sri Lanka”, in Garg, S. (ed.), *Circulation of Cultures and Culture of Circulation: Diasporic Cultures of South Asia During 18th to 20th Centuries*, Colombo, SAARC Cultural Centre, 2014, p. 147

⁵ Chandrabose, “Cultural Identity”, p. 147

⁶ Manthri, “Presidential Election Results 2024”, <https://manthri.lk/en/presidential-election-result-2024>, last date of consultation 11 January 2025

The most recent census taken in 2011 highlights this imbalance. With Sinhalese people comprising roughly 74.9 per cent of the population, they hold a strong position of power over the minorities in the country. The minorities of Sri Lankan Tamils, Indian Tamils, and Muslims comprise 11.2 per cent, 4.2 per cent, and 9.3 per cent respectively. Religion also plays a key role in this imbalance. Buddhists represent 70.1 per cent, while Hindus, Christians, and Muslims are 12.6 per cent, 7.6 per cent, and 9.7 per cent respectively. The resulting demographic dominance of Sinhalese Buddhists demanded “checks against majoritarianism” that has been absent from modern, independent Sri Lanka since its inception in 1948.⁷

Finally, Sri Lanka's colonial history and its continuing relationship with power is evident in this newspaper article. To begin with, the entire newspaper is available in the English language. This underscores a continued colonial remnant from the time of British rule. Moreover, and perhaps more insidiously, the structures of power in society continue to have a relationship with Britain. Sajith Premadasa, for instance, completed his high school qualifications in the UK whilst also attending his first university there.⁸ Language and education are not only both intrinsically linked, but they tend to reproduce existing power structures that were moulded from old Sinhalese power structures by successive colonial powers from the sixteenth century. The group in question in the article, the Indian Tamils, are the focal point of this thesis whose identity will be shown to have adapted and have been adapted to successive power bases in Sri Lanka that were forever changed by the ‘Europeanising’ effect of colonialism on local institutions.

0.1 Historical Backdrop

0.1.1 The “Pearl” of the Indian Ocean

Sri Lanka has long been known as the ‘pearl’ of the Indian Ocean due to not only its abundance of rare minerals but also its strategic location. In the twenty-first century China has identified the island nation as a key node in its ‘string of pearls’ that make up its route for energy imports due to its position within the east-west international shipping passageway.⁹

This interest in Sri Lanka from foreign powers due to its position in the Indian Ocean, however, is not a new concept. From the sixteenth century up to independence in 1948, Sri Lanka was the prey of successive maritime powers that sunk their claws deeper into its institutions with every colonial iteration. The history of colonisation on the shores of Sri Lanka can generally be divided up into three eras: the Portuguese era between 1505 and 1658, the Dutch era from 1658 to 1796,

⁷ DeVotta, N., “Ethnoreligious Nationalism and Autocratization in Sri Lanka”, in Widmalm, S., *Routledge Handbook of Autocratization in South Asia*, London, Routledge, 2021, p. 287

⁸ The Island, “Sajith tables his educational qualifications in Parliament”, <https://island.lk/sajith-tables-his-educational-qualifications-in-parliament/>, last date of consultation 11 January 2025

⁹ Mendis, P., “The Sri Lankan Silk Road: The Potential War Between China and the United States”, *Harvard International Review*, vol. 34, n. 2, 2012, p. 54

and finally the British era from 1796 until 1948.¹⁰ Generally, the Portuguese and Dutch claims of sovereignty over the lands they conquered were done through taxation, coercion, and conversion. The British, however, enmeshed themselves within the, sometimes one and the same, religious and political institutions within Sri Lanka “to create a modern colonial state where natives would become colonial subjects.”¹¹

Portugal’s interest in Sri Lanka began with relatively benign intentions: to protect their interests in the spice trade. Indeed, their presence in the Indian Ocean in this regard was a new development as by the sixteenth century trade in this oceanic space was dominated by Arab, Indian, Malay, and Chinese merchants.¹² In time, the Portuguese created trading posts that developed into fortified bases from which they could extend their control of the interior of the island, such as Colombo Fort. Their armed presence on the island was utilised in particular by the Sinhalese *Kōṭṭe* Kingdom, who enlisted their help in local conflicts before eventually being subsumed by the Portuguese throne itself in the dying throes of the sixteenth century. For the Portuguese, this represented a dilution of the boundary between the local and the global. Or, as Zoltan Biedermann notes, Portugal saw itself “as a global polity uninflected by the local”.¹³ This shift in mindset is evidenced through an increased emphasis on the international economic network through cinnamon. This development was achieved by relying on the *Salagama* caste, people who migrated relatively recently from South India and specialised in the cinnamon trade.¹⁴ An increased focus on colonial networks in this nascent colonial era for Sri Lanka is in evidence here.

Administratively, the Portuguese and the Dutch kept much of the indigenous system. The local caste system was left broadly untouched, albeit with the new colonisers installed at the top. Three main additions to the institutional landscape can be identified during these two colonial eras: the residence and installation of a Portuguese or Dutch leader who directed colonial matters, as evidenced in particular by the Dutch East India Company was an increased focus on trade into colonial networks, and the spread of churches on the island.¹⁵ The spread of religion during this period reflects a spread of European ideals that would later be utilised by the British to tighten their control on the island. Ultimately, for the purpose of this thesis it is important to simply note here that the Portuguese and Dutch eras represented the beginnings of not only the influence of European systems of knowledge in Sri Lanka, but the insertion of their local economy

¹⁰ Wickramasinghe, N., *Sri Lanka in the Modern Age: A History*, New York, Oxford University Press, 2014, p. 9

¹¹ Wickramasinghe, *Sri Lanka*, p. 9

¹² Perera, C.G., *Kandy Fights the Portuguese: A Military History of Kandyan Resistance*, Sri Lanka, Vijithayapa Publications, 2007, p. 144

¹³ Biedermann, Z., *(Dis)connected Empires: Imperial Portugal, Sri Lankan Diplomacy, and the Making of a Habsburg Conquest in Asia*, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2018, pp. 217-218

¹⁴ Wickramasinghe, *Sri Lanka*, p. 14

¹⁵ Wickramasinghe, *Sri Lanka*, pp. 15-17

into European colonial networks of trade. Pertinently, this not only affected material goods, but also influenced colonial migrations into the island, particularly under the British.

0.1.2 British Control and the Subsumption of the “Pearl”

Whilst those two colonial eras represented the nascent European influence on the island, their limiting factor was their maritime presence. This was largely due to the fact that their focus lay on the use of Sri Lanka as a ‘node’ in their wider economic network of trade. Conversely, the British were more total in their colonial domination of Sri Lanka in multiple ways. Firstly, this is highlighted physically by the complete takeover of all tracts of land in Sri Lanka, named Ceylon under the British. This was accomplished in 1815 when they took possession of the kingdom of Kandy in the interior of Ceylon.¹⁶ This marked the first time that a colonial power had expanded outside of the maritime areas of the island and deposed the ancient Sinhalese rulers on the island. This had multiple consequences in various intersectional fields pertinent to this thesis.

Many of these can be encapsulated in the fate of the *Mahāvamsa*, a historical epic that has been described as “the charter of Sinhalese Buddhist nationalism”.¹⁷ With continuous entries dating back to the sixth century BC up until being halted by the annexation of Kandy in 1815, this text today represents a continuous unbroken history of the island. It has been used particularly in times of Buddhist reform to “reflect, produce, or legitimize changes in power”.¹⁸ Indeed, its central focus on the Buddha designates it not only as a sacred history, but its compositions by select monastic actors patronised by royalty over many centuries underscores its crucial importance as a central legitimating text for Sinhalese Buddhism within Sri Lanka.¹⁹ Moreover the epic nature of the tales within, involving heroes and sacred places, placed the Sinhala people as the natural rulers of Sri Lanka. It defined them not only religiously, but also in their relationship with themselves, their government and the wider society at large.²⁰ The contents of this epic in turn shows a grounding of nationalist identity before even a European colonist had set foot upon the island.

When the British took control of the institutions of Sri Lanka, accomplished in its totality with the takeover of the seat of religious power in Kandy, the halt of new entries to this sacred text emphasised the increased totality of colonial control compared to their colonial predecessors. No longer were the foreign powers a presence on the island that operated through coercion and

¹⁶ Evers, H., “Buddhism and British Colonial Policy in Ceylon”, *Asian Center*, vol. 2, n. 3, 1964, pp. 323-324

¹⁷ Gombrich, R., *Theravāda Buddhism: A Social History from Ancient Benares to Modern Colombo*, London, Routledge, 1988, p. 25

¹⁸ Scheible, K., “Sri Lanka's *Mahāvamsa*, The Great Chronicle,” in Lothspeich, P. (ed.), *The Epic World*, Oxon, Routledge, 2024, p. 133

¹⁹ Scheible, “Sri Lanka's *Mahāvamsa*,” pp. 137-138

²⁰ Kemper, S. *The Presence of the Past: Chronicles, Politics, and Culture in Sinhala Life*, New York, Cornell University Press, 1991, p. 222

trade with the Sinhalese Buddhists in the rugged interior of the island. Now, the colonial power had full control over the island and did not necessarily represent Sinhalese Buddhist interests. Further, this takeover of institutions led to an influx of European knowledge systems. The acceleration of this under the British led to a transformation in the interpretation of ancient texts such as the *Mahāvamsa*. Its nascent beginnings in pre-colonial times as a source of Sinhalese consciousness had found form with the transformation of institutional knowledge present under the British. Now the text served as a legitimation of Sinhalese Buddhist nationalism, a political identity that flourished under colonial rule and found its footing in independent Sri Lanka.

The *Mahāvamsa's* sacred importance to Sinhalese Buddhist identity survived through roughly four and a half centuries of colonialism. As a result, it is of little surprise that this text has been used as a “viable resource for autonomous, authentic identity construction for Sinhalese Buddhists in the post-colonial period.”²¹ Neil DeVotta states that whilst the majority of Sinhalese Buddhists have not read it, they have “internalized and embraced the *Mahāvamsa* as sacred and undisputable history” whilst using it as an “impetus for political Buddhism” with “implications for ethnic conflict and conflict resolution”.²² Referring to the conflict between the Sinhala and Tamil peoples beginning at the latter end of the twentieth century, this conflict was rooted in a Sinhalese nationalist ideology rooted in “language, race, and religion” that had been formulated from the time of the British colonial period.²³ The *Mahāvamsa* had specifically been used as a vehicle to celebrate Sinhala culture and its people, subjugated under decades of colonial and Christian domination.²⁴

Through looking at the *Mahāvamsa* in pre-colonial, colonial, and post-colonial times, some pertinent themes emerge. The emergence of the text as a source of nationalistic pride exclusive to Sinhalese Buddhists underscores the effect the colonising of institutions had on Sinhala identity. Its purpose as a legitimation of rule for the Sinhala people in pre-colonial times was sharpened under colonial rule as their seat of power was overrun and the *Mahāvamsa* was pushed aside by the British. A nationalistic fervour sprouted that, for the first time, was exclusively championing Sinhalese people and excluding peoples in the name of a nationalist identity. The perceived right to rule over Sri Lanka was instilled in Sinhalese people over time, partly due to the existence of sacred texts such as the *Mahāvamsa*. Considering the morphing identity of Sinhalese Buddhist consciousness through colonialism is crucial for this thesis. However, this shift in institutional control provides only a backdrop to the main purpose of this thesis, namely the changing economic outlook and its effect on migrations into British Ceylon.

²¹ Scheible, “Sri Lanka's *Mahāvamsa*,” p. 141

²² DeVotta, N., *Sinhalese Buddhist Nationalist Ideology: Implications for Politics and Conflict Resolution in Sri Lanka*, Washington, DC, East-West Center Washington, 2007, pp. 5-6

²³ Tambiah, S.J., *Buddhism Betrayed? Religion, Politics, and Violence in Sri Lanka*, Chicago, University of Chicago Press, 1992, p. 131

²⁴ Tambiah, *Buddhism Betrayed?*, p. 131

0.1.3 Research Question

Within the context of encroaching colonial influence and the resulting reshaping of indigenous identities lies the initial migration of Indian Tamil people into British Ceylon. Following the abolition of slavery within the British Empire, scores of Tamil labourers from South India made the long journey to the Kandyan heartland of Ceylon to work on the coffee plantations. Initially it was promises of an improved wage compared to what they received in India that attracted them, as well as the stunning natural beauty. One contemporary voice notes of “the pretty and picturesque appearance of the well-watered capital of Ceylon, with its cinnamon gardens, lakes, and islands!”²⁵

This rather rosy image of life for the Indian Tamil working on the plantations in Ceylon was contrary to reality. Indian migration en masse from the 1830s was part of an empire-wide drift to indentured servitude to replace slave labour. Indentured labour migration under government control was permitted first to Mauritius in 1843 and then to other West Indian colonies from 1846 onwards.²⁶ Here they were directed under government control to work on plantations producing resources such as sugar. It was hoped that this new system would promote the superiority of ‘free’ over slave labour in the production of plantation products for the colonial economic market.²⁷ Colonial directives motivated by capitalistic market pressures drove this large push of migration from India to various parts of the British Empire.

In British Ceylon, these labourers swiftly found an environment of low pay, harsh treatment and unacceptable living conditions. Initially brought over to work on the coffee plantations, they dotted the landscape of the hill country, working long hours to satisfy an insatiable need for exotic products to feed the imperial network with. A “coolie”, as they were pejoratively known, Tamil guide illuminates the perception of them within the colonial landscape. Colonial and industrial stakeholders likened them to “urchins, animals and ‘machines’ that could work with efficiency and in silence among the tea bushes at a distance.” They were seen as an alienated people sprung from the earth and not from women's wombs, a fixed entity rather than on the move.²⁸

This perception of the labourer was consistent throughout Ceylonese society. As this thesis will demonstrate, these indentured labourers found themselves discriminated against due to an intersection of factors including caste, ethnicity, and religion that led to their alienation from

²⁵ Mouat, F.J., *Rough Notes of a Trip to Reunion, the Mauritius and Ceylon: With Remarks of the Eligibility as Sanitaria for Indian Invalids*, New Delhi, J. Jetley, 1852, p. 3

²⁶ Carter, M. and Torabully, K., *Coolitude: An Anthology of the Indian Labour Diaspora*, London, Anthem Press, 2002, p. 50

²⁷ Hassankhan, M., Roopnarine, L., Ramsোধ, H., *The Legacy of Indian Indenture: Historical and Contemporary Aspects of Migration and Diaspora*, London, Routledge, 2016, p. 4

²⁸ Jegathesan, M., *Tea and Solidarity: Tamil Women and Work in Postwar Sri Lanka*, Seattle, University of Washington Press, 2019, p. 76

Ceylonese society. They largely remained legally undocumented and socially isolated from both Sinhalese and Sri Lankan Tamil communities living in Ceylon due to British colonial policies. This led to a widening divergence in living standards and access to opportunities. Predicated on British colonial economic policy, this divergence was further exacerbated in the post-colonial era due to indigenous nationalistic tendencies that had been inflamed during the colonial period.

This leads us to the primary question interrogated in this thesis: how did the migration of Indian Tamil indentured labourers in the nineteenth century influence intersectional tensions within Sri Lanka? From here, a deep excavation into the experiences of the Indian Tamil indentured labourer in the nineteenth century can illuminate subaltern historical experiences. In doing so new reflections on the changing idea of nationalism and the 'Europeanisation' of institutions will emerge. An intersection of caste, religion, and language will be interrogated to illuminate a complex image of Sri Lankan society that was morphed by, but not defined by, colonialism.

0.2 Literature Review

0.2.1 Secondary Literature

Researching experiences of Indian Tamil indentured labourers in British Ceylon requires an academic lens that appreciates local cultural shifts within overarching imperial structures. This approach intends to provide a more nuanced perspective often overlooked by the centre-periphery model. A prevalent analytical tool since the twentieth century, centre-periphery approaches entrench a colonial Eurocentric perspective on communities in the 'periphery', minimizing their experiences and agency within the colonial framework. Many postcolonial authors lead this ongoing methodological shift.²⁹ Stephanie Newell's concept of 'paracolonialism' is most applicable for this research. Newell discards the traditional ideas of 'pre'-colonial, colonial and 'post'-colonial in favour of acknowledging the local cultural shifts that occurred *alongside* and *beyond* British imperialism.³⁰ In doing so the wider global context can be extrapolated to illuminate cultural shifts in both a temporal and spatial manner. In short, this framing allows the global migration flows pertinent to the development of Tamil indentured labour communities to be analysed in the context of both Sri Lankan and global history.

Complementing 'paracolonialism' is Dipesh Chakrabarty's idea of 'time-knots'. These represent the complex intersections of different temporal experiences, perspectives, and narratives that converge in the writing of history. Consequently, the interconnectedness of past, present, and future are highlighted to illustrate how various temporal threads come together to shape

²⁹ Kaps, K. and Komlosy, A., "Centres and Peripheries Revisited: Polycentric Connections or Entangled Hierarchies?", *Review (Fernand Braudel Center)*, vol. 36, n. 3-4, 2013, p. 237

³⁰ Newell, S., "'Paracolonial' Networks: Some Speculations on Local Readerships in Colonial West Africa", *Interventions*, vol. 3, n. 3, 2001, p. 350.

historical interpretations.³¹ Pertinently, this allows for the disparate strands of this thesis to come together. Ideas of Sinhalese nationalism, the colonial economy, and influence of religion can be examined temporally in a paracolonial sense to appreciate how the Indian Tamil experience was not shaped by simply by colonialism itself but also by the wider Sri Lankan historical context. The following section provides a brief literature review revealing the intersectional aspects of this research and how the existing historiography contributes to the overall discussion of Tamil migration as a microcosm of the longstanding impacts of colonialism on diverse and complex South Asian communities.

Considering the framing of the paracolonial lens, the experiences of indentured labourers and, more broadly, those in servitude in Sri Lankan history, is invaluable. Nira Wickramasinghe's research contextualises the colonial influence and shifting nature of servitude in Sri Lanka.³² Similarly, structural concepts surrounding enslavement provide a useful methodological background, as well as more specific articles surrounding the impact of colonial slavery on Sri Lanka.³³ Moreover, testimonies from enslaved peoples encompass and detail the experiences of those in servitude within the Indian Ocean World.³⁴ However, testimonies from enslaved communities during British Ceylon (1796-1948), particularly during the early nineteenth century, are broadly lacking.

Elsewhere, there are resources surrounding the colonial effects on the experiences of plantation workers in Sri Lanka. Patrick Peebles' *The Plantation Tamils of Ceylon* is key.³⁵ His study assesses Tamil plantation workers in the early twentieth century and how their experiences were shaped both by colonial exploitation and their actions for social change. Intertwined with this specific topic is the research of land rights. This provides invaluable information into why indentured labourers were sent to specific regions or even plantations. The experiences of these migrants were at the behest of a colonial need to boost the economy at little cost, with little regard for the needs of the Tamil labourers.³⁶ Analysing these two new modes with an intersectional perspective allows for a considered look at the experiences of the Indian Tamil plantation workers in Sri Lanka.

³¹ Chakrabarty, D., *Provincializing Europe: Postcolonial Thought and Historical Difference*, Oxfordshire, Princeton University Press, 2000, pp. 111-114

³² Wickramasinghe, N., *Slave in a Palanquin: Colonial Servitude and Resistance*, New York, Columbia University Press, 2020; Schrikker, A. and Wickramasinghe, N. (eds.), *Being a Slave: Histories and Legacies of European Slavery in the Indian Ocean*, Leiden, Leiden University Press, 2020

³³ Blackburn, R., "Slave Exploitation and the Elementary Structures of Enslavement," in Bush, M.L. (ed.), *Serfdom and Slavery: Studies in Legal Bondage*, Oxon, Routledge, 2013, pp. 158-180; Wickramasinghe, C.S.M., "Coloured Slavery in Ceylon (Sri Lanka)," *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society of Sri Lanka*, vol. 54, 2008, pp. 159-178

³⁴ Van Rossum, M., Geelen, A., Van den Hout, B. and Tosun, M., *Testimonies of Enslavement: Sources on Slavery from the Indian Ocean World*, London, Bloomsbury Publishing, 2020

³⁵ Peebles, P., *The Plantation Tamils of Ceylon*, London, Leicester University Press, 2001

³⁶ Ellman, A.O., Ratnaweera, D.D.S., Silva, K.T., Wickremasinghe, G., *Land Settlement in Sri Lanka 1840-1975: A Review of the Major Writings on the Subject*, Colombo, Agrarian Research and Training Institute, 1976, p. 25-28

Furthermore, additional studies directly address the intersection of secondary literature concerning indentured labourers and ethnicity. Shihan de Silva Jayasuriya provides a rare insight into experiences of African people relocated to Ceylon during the colonial period.³⁷ These analyses highlight how the intersectional issues tackled in this research are replicated in different contexts. Similarly, S. Kadirvel provides an account of Indian Tamils in Sri Lanka in relation with the Sinhalese in the Matale Rebellion of 1848.³⁸ Further available research pursues additional elements concerning the role of ethnicity in Sri Lankan society. However, most of this research only assesses how the Sinhalese people affect other communities rather than following a paracolonial approach by analysing and contextualising local culture in a globally temporal and spatial way.

Religion and education, other intersectional issues targeted in this research, are approached separately by scholars in this field. Observed in Sri Lanka's religious diversity, religion remains one of the most academically discussed aspects of Sri Lankan history, politics, and culture. Relevant to this thesis is the pre-existing literature surrounding the British colonists and their effects on Buddhism in the nineteenth century, the role religion plays in Sri Lankan conflicts, and the relationship between the Tamil and Sinhala peoples. Elizabeth J. Harris is particularly prominent regarding the religious aspect whereas David Feith's research provides a helpful backdrop to the ethnic relations in question.³⁹ Meanwhile studies regarding education attainment in plantation society remain limited. Angela Little provides one of the few comprehensive accounts of the role education played in the plantations and the ramifications this had on wider Ceylonese society.⁴⁰ Pertinently, G.A. Gnanamuttu contributes to the discussion of education on the plantation by providing an analysis of the influence of other colonial-era factors that add to the intersectional lens of this thesis.⁴¹ While available research and primary sources remain rare on this topic, this thesis aims to include as much evidence as possible to construct a nuanced interpretation of the Tamil labour experience.

As summarised above, multiple methodologies, theories, and studies concerning Sri Lankan indentured labour is available that provides an invaluable foundation for what this research aims to achieve. Crucial to this thesis is the dispersed literature concerning ethnicity, religion, and gender. However, two main issues remain prominent. Firstly, the studies are generally just that:

³⁷ Jayasuriya, S., "Recruiting Africans to the British Regiments in Ceylon: Spillover Effects of Abolition in the Atlantic", *African and Asian Studies*, vol. 10, n. 1, 2011, pp. 15-31; Jayasuriya, S., "A Forgotten Minority: The Afro-Sri Lankans", *African and Asian Studies*, vol. 6, n. 3, 2007, pp. 227-242

³⁸ Kadirvel, S., "Sectional President's Address: Indian Tamils in Sri Lanka: The Contours of Dissonance", *Proceedings of the Indian History Congress*, vol. 61, no. 2, 2000-2001, pp. 1043-1061

³⁹ Harris, E.J., *Theravada Buddhism and the British Encounter: Religious, Missionary and Colonial Experience in Nineteenth Century Sri Lanka*, Oxon, Routledge, 2006; Feith, D., "Tamil and Sinhala Relations in Sri Lanka: A Historical and Contemporary Perspective", *Global Change, Peace & Security*, vol. 22, no. 3, 2010, pp. 345-353; Harris, E.J., *Religion, Space, and Conflict in Sri Lanka: Colonial and Postcolonial Contexts*, Oxon, Routledge, 2018

⁴⁰ Little, A., *Labouring to Learn: Towards a Political Economy of Education and Plantations in Sri Lanka*, Colombo, SSA, 1999

⁴¹ Gnanamuttu, G. A., *Education and the Indian Plantation Worker in Sri Lanka*, Colombo, G. A. Gnanamuttu, 1977

dispersed. This research aims to combat this pitfall by illuminating the experiences of the Tamil people through a paracolonial gaze. The closest research available that pursues a similar methodological framework is Patrick Peebles' *The Plantation Tamils of Ceylon*. However, Peebles' book primarily focuses on cases that occurred a century past this project's timeline. Consequently, the early nineteenth century experience of Tamil labourers in Sri Lanka remains understudied in academic literature in the intersectional manner it deserves. My research confronts this lacuna on Tamil and local cultural historiography through utilising archival research through a variety of nineteenth century sources to illuminate the experiences of the Tamil minority group.

0.2.2 Primary Sources and Methodology

Illuminating the experiences of subaltern groups through archival research is hampered due to inherent issues with the archive itself. As scholars such as Gayatri Spivak and Ranajit Guha have stated, archives are often the product of elite institutions, reflecting the priorities and biases of those in power.⁴² This meant that the voices of marginalised groups are frequently filtered or even omitted entirely through the perspectives of dominant actors such as colonial officials or wealthy landowners. When the subaltern are visible in the archive, they are usually a passive subject or included due to moments of strife. Further, postcolonial historians face the daunting challenge of creating histories due to subaltern testimonies and traces being systematically erased.⁴³

Another factor to consider when delving into the archive is the diminishing of one's experience due to the intersection of one's identity. Or, as Kimberly Beasley more succinctly phrases it, "the intersection of these identities can lead to their invisibility".⁴⁴ With respect to the focus of this thesis, collapsing the identity of an Indian Tamil indentured labourer into their ethnicity, linguistic background or other marker of identity is detrimental as it results in their true nature being lost. Indeed, Sajith Premadasa's quote at the beginning of this thesis echoes this statement. He stated that the estate community "will not be treated merely as labourers", but enjoy a wealth of opportunity that society offers. This highlights how the perception of the Indian Tamil migrant has been collapsed into simply 'labourer', reducing their possibilities in Ceylonese and independent Sri Lankan society. This same view was present in the archive through the voices of

⁴² Spivak, G.C., "Can the Subaltern Speak?", in Morris, R.C. (ed.), *Can the Subaltern Speak?: Reflections on the History of an Idea*, New York, Columbia University Press, 2010, pp. 21-78; Guha, R., "On Some Aspects of the Historiography of Colonial India", in Guha, R. (ed.), *Subaltern Studies I: Writings on South Asian History and Society*, Delhi, Oxford University Press, 1982, pp. 1-9

⁴³ Thomas, D., "Imagining Archives", in Thomas, D., Fowler, S., and Johnson, V. (eds.), *The Silence of the Archive*, London, Facet Publishing, 2017, p. 120

⁴⁴ Johnson, V., "Solutions to the Silence", in Thomas, D., Fowler, S., and Johnson, V. (eds.), *The Silence of the Archive*, London, Facet Publishing, 2017, p. 146

the landowners and colonial government. Applying the voices of the powerful, then, requires a sceptical and well-read eye that can place their portrayal of the 'labourer' into the wider context of their oft-ignored lives.

Nevertheless, this thesis would not have been possible without the invaluable insights gained during my research trip to Sri Lanka. The access to primary sources at the Colombo National Archives provided a wealth of materials which offered unique, firsthand perspectives from influential sources such as the colonial government and landowners, whilst local voices were heard through sources such as newspapers. Equally important was the guidance I received from researchers at various institutions in Sri Lanka, whose expertise and local knowledge were instrumental in helping me navigate the archival material and contextualize my findings. This combination of archival access and collaborative support not only deepened my understanding of British Ceylonese society but also allowed me to engage more critically with existing scholarship, particularly on the intersectional and influential role religion and educational attainment had on the population. The time I spent in Sri Lanka was central to shaping the arguments and conclusions of this thesis, making it a more grounded and nuanced contribution to the study of the Indian Tamil experience in the nineteenth century. What follows is a short summary of some of the key institutions that aided the research for this thesis.

The Department of National Archives in Colombo allowed me access to unique material that covered different contemporary voices from the time. Hundreds of pages of minutes from both the colonial government as well as the Planters' Association illuminated the differing institutional viewpoints that directed the lives of the indentured labourers. Moreover, correspondence from individuals crucial to this period, such as Governor of Ceylon Edward Barnes, gave a personal dimension to the research that helped to delve deeper into the inner machinations of colonial society of the time. This in turn allowed for further insight into the motivations for the direction of the plantation industry in Ceylon.

Away from institutional voices, local perspectives were represented in the archive. English-language texts by Tamil authors discussing the rebellions of 1818 and 1848 underscored how the Tamil community was affected by the new British colonial layer of power in society. Pertinently, the publication dates of these sources were primarily post-Sri Lankan independence. This silence from Tamil indentured labourer voices from the period this research is analysing shows how the archive is a site that replicates the silencing of the subjugated voices in colonial society.

Elsewhere, the American Institute for Sri Lankan Studies (hereafter AILS) served as both a networking hub for different archival centres around Sri Lanka and a site for unique secondary sources. Through their guidance, access to the University of Peradeniya's reading room offered further archival access to contemporary seminars discussing the Tamil indentured labourer experience, histories written by Tamil authors and unique studies into the modern experience of Tamil people. Further, the library at AILS offered a plethora of secondary literature pertaining to

the intersectional experience of Tamil peoples, such as religion, ethnicity, and the effect of colonial education policies on their lives.

Finally, the International Centre for Ethnic Studies (hereafter ICES) offered a multi-dimensional research library and access to a multi-day conference focused on the political development of Sri Lanka and the effects on different strata of society. The library provided texts analysing the unique power structure on the plantations and how this reflected British power structures onto the workers themselves. Away from specific policy, research here contributes differing perspectives on the contemporary environment which this research is interested in. Attending the conference also added different perspectives from Sri Lankan scholars on how the political environment in Sri Lanka developed temporally from the colonial period under the Portuguese to the present day. Taken together, both ICES and AILS presented the opportunity to historicise and contextualise the archival research obtained at the Department of National Archives. Combining their multi-dimensional literature with the selective voices found at the archives provided the groundwork for a nuanced analysis regarding the institutionally ignored perspectives of the Indian Tamil indentured labourer in the nineteenth century.

0.3 Chapter-by-Chapter

This thesis comprises four chapters, each examining the experiences of these indentured labourers from a different, nuanced angle. Further, each chapter includes a 'long shadow' section, placing the historical analysis from the time period in question into temporal perspective. This is done to highlight how the crucial flashpoint of the migrations of the Indian Tamil people into Ceylon was a disruptive one that altered, but did not define, the historical trajectory of Sri Lanka and its people.

Chapter one, "Colonial Fractures and the Disruption of Power, Religion, and Caste in Pre-Colonial Sri Lanka", analyses the impact of Portuguese colonialism on the power structures and religious dynamics of pre-colonial Sri Lanka, exploring how their arrival disrupted the island's caste-based system and religious harmony. The Portuguese transformed land ownership, turning communal land into a commercial asset. Meanwhile they reshaped the institution of slavery, increasing its scope and altering its role in society. Their policies undermined traditional caste hierarchies and introduced exploitative systems that prioritized economic gain. At the same time, their efforts to spread Christianity disrupted the previously pluralistic religious landscape, fostering resistance among the Sinhalese majority and intensifying the exclusivist tendencies of Sinhalese Buddhist nationalism.

The works of Sinhalese poet Alagiyavanna Mukaveti are used as a case study to highlight the interplay between power and religion during this period. The poet's writings reflect the evolution of Sinhalese nationalism, from a pluralistic acceptance of other religions to a more exclusive

ideology shaped by resistance to Portuguese domination. By establishing the roots of power, hierarchy, and resistance in colonial Sri Lanka, this chapter provides a foundational context for the analysis in subsequent chapters. Furthermore, extrapolating the shifting nature of servitude on the island at this flashpoint in history sets the foundation for analysis into the Indian Tamil indentured labourer and their role in British colonial society.

Chapter two, "Migration, Indenture, and the Struggles of Tamil Labourers in Ceylon", focuses analysis on nineteenth century Ceylon. It explores the systemic forces driving Indian Tamil migration, such as the abolition of slavery, British economic interests, and labour shortages due to local resistance to plantation work. The chapter details how Indian Tamil labourers were drawn into exploitative plantation systems through hierarchical structures like the kangany system, which relied on debt-driven recruitment and caste-based subordination to maintain control. These workers, viewed as temporary "strangers," were excluded from broader societal integration and subjected to harsh working and living conditions that entrenched their marginalization.

Colonial policies including the Colebrook-Cameron Commission are also interrogated, highlighting how they reshaped Sri Lankan society by abolishing traditional systems like *rājākariya* and prioritizing land acquisition for plantations. This shift disrupted existing social hierarchies while embedding Indian Tamil labourers into a rigid colonial power structure that marginalized them economically and socially. By examining these historical developments through a paracolonial lens, the chapter underscores the enduring legacy of colonial hierarchies in shaping the socio-political and economic landscape of modern Sri Lanka, setting the stage for later discussions on the agency and identity of Indian-origin labourers.

Chapter three, "Rebellions, Resistance, and the Struggle for Agency in Colonial Ceylon", explores the nature of rebellion in British Ceylon, focusing on the resistance of not only the plantation workers but also that of Sinhalese peasants. Colonial policies, such as land confiscations, exploitative taxation, and forced labour, are shown to have undermined traditional structures and exacerbated tensions in Ceylonese society. Major uprisings, including the Uva-Wellassa Rebellion between 1817 and 1818 as well as the Matale Rebellion of 1848, are analysed to show how economic and cultural suppression drove both elite and peasant-led resistance. Alongside these large-scale revolts, everyday acts of defiance by plantation labourers are examined, such as absenteeism and desertion, which challenged the rigid hierarchies of plantation capitalism under the British.

Considering the temporal aspect of this thesis, this chapter traces the evolution of resistance from spontaneous and localized actions to more organized, institutional forms as Ceylon's political and economic systems professionalized. This is shown to be in step with the broad shift from the philosophy of *laissez-faire* inherent in nineteenth century Ceylon to the 'professionalisation' of institutions in the twentieth century. The establishment of trade unions and the extension of political rights were actioned by an increasing number of people, though

the labourer was excluded from the burgeoning collective action movement. Analysis through a paracolonial lens demonstrates how resistance shaped colonial power structures and contributed to the social and political transformations that laid the groundwork for modern Sri Lanka.

Chapter four, "Educating the Excluded through Language, Caste, and Structural Violence", argues that education was a tool of structural violence, perpetuating social hierarchies and marginalizing Indian Tamils through systemic exclusion. Under British rule, laissez-faire policies and capitalist plantation priorities limited access to quality education, confining labourers' children to rudimentary "line schools" whilst privileging elite groups with socially progressive educational opportunities, such as English-medium instruction. Missionary and planter-led initiatives further entrenched divisions by reinforcing class, caste, and religious hierarchies.

In the 'long shadow' of nineteenth century education policy, colonial frameworks were replicated in post-independence Sri Lanka. Policies such as the discriminatory Citizenship Acts of 1948 and 1949, as well as the Sinhala Only Act, exacerbated the societal division and further isolated the Indian Tamil estate community. Language and religion became instruments of exclusion, shaping educational access and deepening societal divides. Through a paracolonial lens, the chapter underscores the continuity of structural inequalities, showing how education reinforced the systemic oppression of Indian Tamils, leaving them stateless and socially isolated for decades.

Finally, the conclusion reflects on the central themes of the thesis, tying together the historical, social, and political dynamics that have shaped the experience of Indian Tamil plantation workers in Sri Lanka. It highlights how their marginalization, beginning with their introduction during the colonial era, was perpetuated by the intersection of pre-colonial hierarchies, colonial policies, and post-independence nationalism. The modern-day exclusion of Indian Tamils from both Sinhalese and Tamil nationalist projects is excavated, revealing the limitations of viewing the Sri Lankan civil war solely through ethnic binaries. Instead, it calls for an intersectional approach that accounts for the complex interplay of caste, class, language, and physical location in shaping their identity in society and continued marginalization.

Building on the paracolonial analysis featured in previous chapters, this conclusion demonstrates how colonial systems of control, such as the professionalization of institutions and the physical segregation of plantation workers, entrenched inequalities that persisted into the post-colonial era. It also explores how Indian Tamils resisted marginalization during the civil war through subtle acts of agency, from rejecting cultural norms to emigrating. By situating these experiences within broader historical continuities, a foundation for understanding the long shadows of colonialism and the nuanced realities of identity formation in Sri Lanka is provided, setting the stage for further exploration of subaltern voices in the country's history.

Chapter One: Colonial Fractures and the Disruption of Power, Religion, and Caste in Pre-Colonial Sri Lanka

“This bright, beautiful island was made into a Paradise by the Aryan Sinhalese before its destruction was brought about by the barbaric vandals ... This ancient, historic, refined people, under the diabolism of vicious paganism ... are now declining and slowly dying away.”¹

Sri Lankan history is a tale of dichotomy, a harmonious story defined by fragmentation. Structurally, power is held in the hands of the Sinhalese majority. In the modern era, this power was consolidated in May 2009 when the Sri Lankan army defeated the Liberation Tigers of Tamil Eelam after a protracted conflict spreading over twenty-six years. This victory shifted into focus some questions regarding the role of minorities in society, such as the Indian Tamil and Muslim populations.² How will modern-day Sri Lanka incorporate these minorities in the long run? Sri Lanka’s historic tendency to practise religious pluralism has trended downwards in recent years. This chapter aims to discover the roots of this trend to further shed light on the current Sri Lankan political landscape.

Further, another aim is to answer these questions by focusing on two commonalities between them that are particularly pertinent to Sri Lanka’s storied history: power and religion. Focus will be placed on historicizing the roles of power and religion around the time the Portuguese established relations with Sri Lanka before eventually colonizing it. In doing so the roots of the modern proclivity towards Sinhalese-Buddhist nationalism will be shown to have been a rebellion against foreign invasion. Applying a paracolonial lens to this period also brings to light how the increasingly penetrative colonial influence under the British began with initial contact by the Portuguese. Pertinently, exploring the shifting nature of servitude on the island underscores the Indian Tamil experience on the island centuries later with regards to their migratory status as well as their treatment on the plantations they worked on.

1.0.1 Disruptive Influence

Portugal's initial colonisation of Sri Lanka was a significant event in the island’s history. First establishing a trading post in Colombo in the early 16th century, they slowly expanded their

¹ DeVotta, N., “The Genesis, Consolidation, and Consequences of Sinhalese Buddhist Nationalism”, in Rouhana, N. and Shalhoub-Kevorkian, N. (eds.), *When Politics are Sacralized: Comparative Perspectives on Religious Claims and Nationalism*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 2021, p. 194

² Feith, D., “Tamil and Sinhala Relations in Sri Lanka: A Historical and Contemporary Perspective”, *Global Change, Peace & Security*, vol. 22, n. 3, 2010, p. 345

control over the island by establishing a network of forts and garrisons along the coast.³ The encroaching influence of Portugal had wide-reaching effects. The caste-system in Sri Lanka, well established for centuries within the Indian sub-continent, was disrupted. Robert Knox succinctly described it as a kind of European feudalism due to its linking of land obligations to secular and religious authorities. Further, the structure of such a system meant the Sinhalese majority held higher status and therefore higher power in the secular aspects of Sri Lankan society.⁴ Portugal's arrival represented a fundamental shift in how power was replicated across the island, disrupting established power dynamics and having tangible effects on both contemporary and modern Sri Lanka.

Religion played a similarly disrupting force during this particular period of Sri Lankan history. Whilst religion had close ties to power, demonstrated by the fact that priests were considered religious leaders with political power, it is important to distinguish these two themes.⁵ Religion manifests the fragmented harmony that categorises Sri Lankan history. Before the Portuguese, Buddhism and Hinduism were somewhat harmonious. Hinduism found a place in Buddhist temples while Buddhist kings married Hindu queens. This has been described as 'syncretic inculturation' by Leonard Pinto or, in other words, religious harmony.⁶ However, this is a contested view. As will be discussed, this term ignores the complexity of the longstanding dynamics of power between religion and the caste system incorporated into the fabric of Sri Lankan society. Since the Portuguese influence, Christianity morphed the makeup of Sri Lankan society. The caste system was transformed whilst places of worship were either built or razed to the ground. These attacks on the established religious order led to Buddhism itself becoming more exclusive and hostile towards other religions. This shift will be analysed in a case study using the works of Alagiyavanna Mukaveti, a Sinhala king's court member who wrote poems about his religious experiences during this turbulent time. Through the use of these poems the interplay between power and religion will be illuminated, highlighting how power and religious identity morphed while many Buddhist institutions were retreating.

As has been demonstrated, inquiring about these broad themes reveals certain pervasive commonalities. Wildly different cultural aspects are affected, from the caste system to religious places of worship to poetry. This chapter, then, aims to synthesize these aspects by analysing them through the lens of slavery. This will be done for two reasons. First, slavery as an institution represents this chapter's main goal: to show how the immediate impact of Portuguese influence instigated long standing change in Sri Lankan society that can be felt to this day. Indeed, several

³ Pieris, P.E. and Ferguson, D., "Portuguese Ceylon at the Beginning of the Seventeenth Century: A Sketch", *The Journal of the Ceylon Branch of the Royal Asiatic Society of Great Britain and Ireland*, vol. 21, n. 61, 1908, pp. 90-92

⁴ Pieris and Ferguson, "Portuguese Ceylon", p. 104

⁵ Pinto, L., *Being a Christian in Sri Lanka: Historical, Political, Social, and Religious Considerations*, Bloomington, Balboa Press, 2015, 2

⁶ Pinto, *Being a Christian*, pp. 12-13

contemporary observers as well as modern scholars have noted the difference between pre-colonial Sri Lankan slavery and that of colonial plantation-based slavery. Chandima Wickramasinghe, for instance, argues that slavery can exist 'in different shapes and manners within the same country in the course of its historical period due to political, social and cultural changes or backgrounds.'⁷ This is certainly the case in Sri Lanka as colonial powers impressed their ideologies onto a country wholly unfamiliar with European patterns of knowledge. For example, access to colonial economic networks led to an influx of enslaved peoples who were of different ethnic origins to their master. Moreover, the use and partial disregard of the existing caste system by the Portuguese affected the nature of who a slave was and why they might serve.⁸ Analysis of this 'flashpoint' slavery will encapsulate the core ideas of power and religion in this chapter, allowing them to coalesce. Finally, there is a relative lack of scholarship surrounding pre-colonial Sri Lankan slavery. Moreover, what there is has been described as scholars who have 'simply flipped through several points'.⁹ Consequently, this chapter aims to provide a somewhat useful addition to Sri Lankan scholarship whilst demonstrating the various ways in which the impact of colonialism greatly influences the Sri Lanka of today.

To support this chapter, both contemporary accounts and modern scholarly texts will be utilised in a variety of ways. The contemporary accounts, particularly those of Alagiyavanna, will be used to illustrate how the impact of Portuguese influence on Sri Lanka affected the power structures within the Sinhalese court, as well as how religious identity morphed particularly in relation with religious conversion. Modern scholarly texts, meanwhile, will be used to interrogate the past. For example, what did it mean to be a slave in pre-colonial times compared to colonial? Is the term 'slave' accurate from a western point of view for pre-colonial slavery? From a *longue durée* perspective how does the shift in the nature of slavery intersect with power and religion? What are the ramifications of this today? Posing these questions will help shed light on a relatively neglected part of Sri Lankan history in pre-colonial slavery, as well as adding a historical perspective to the current situation in Sri Lanka.

1.1 Power

Slavery and power are intrinsically connected. Indeed, the modern definition provided by the UN refers to slavery as situations of exploitation that a person cannot refuse or leave because of a

⁷ Wickramasinghe, C.S.M., "Coloured Slavery in Ceylon (Sri Lanka)", *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society of Sri Lanka*, vol. 54, 2008, p. 170

⁸ Wickramasinghe, "Coloured Slavery", pp. 159-160

⁹ Wickramasinghe, C.S.M., "Redemption of Slaves in Ancient Sri Lanka", in Kleijwegt, M. (ed.), *The Faces of Freedom: The Manumission and Emancipation of Slaves in Old World and New World Slavery*, Leiden, Brill, 2006, p. 117

multitude of abuses of power such as violence or coercion.¹⁰ This understandably broad definition is sufficient for its purpose in colonial and postcolonial times. Yet, for the purpose of this chapter, it is appropriate to distinguish how structures of power intersected with slavery in Sri Lanka before and after Portuguese influence.

Owen Patterson's definition of slavery is very strict in its wording. He states that slaves had no honour, even the ones who helped administer empires.¹¹ This definition ignores the contextual nuances that embody societies with slave labour, such as in the case of Sri Lanka. Slavery being permanent is a falsehood due to manumission being a common practice in Sri Lankan slavery.¹² Moreover, the voluntary submission of oneself to slavery in temples was commonly carried out due to its association with religious honour in Sri Lankan society.¹³ Indeed, the acquisition of at least a modicum of honour as a slave is a reflection of the contemporary society they found themselves in. Sri Lankan people were considered subjects not citizens, whilst their identity was seen as a reflection of their master. In very general terms they embodied different values or significance according to the prevailing principles of social organisation.¹⁴ Interrogating Patterson's quote, then, is useful in illustrating how slavery operates very differently in certain power structures, most pertinently in the caste-based system of Sri Lanka.

1.1.1 Pre-Colonial Slavery

The caste-based system was introduced to Sri Lanka from India in the third century BC. It developed as a professional based social system, with *Kṣatriya*, ruling class, and *Brāhmana*, advisors to kings, occupying the first two castes with the majority of the population making up the third caste composed of farmers, *Veśya* or *Govigama*. Within each caste there were many divisions, such as the goldsmiths ranking highly in the third caste while the *rodīya* people were ranked at the lowest level.¹⁵ It is also important to note that all castes were primarily subsistence cultivators, and caste-specific vocations were restricted to subsidiary pursuits. For centuries the land was communally cultivated on a system of reciprocal labour exchange in lieu of services rendered in common to the state for the well-being of society. In other words, land was not a marketable commodity, but it was the means of sustenance for everybody under the supervision

¹⁰ United Nations, "Slavery Convention", [https://www.ohchr.org/en/instruments-mechanisms/instruments/slavery-convention#:~:text=\(1\)%20Slavery%20is%20the%20status,right%20of%20ownership%20are%20exercised](https://www.ohchr.org/en/instruments-mechanisms/instruments/slavery-convention#:~:text=(1)%20Slavery%20is%20the%20status,right%20of%20ownership%20are%20exercised), last date of consultation 31 May 2024

¹¹ Patterson, *Slavery and Social Death*, pp. 10-11

¹² Wickramasinghe, "Redemption of Slaves", p. 121

¹³ Wickramasinghe, "Redemption of Slaves", pp. 130-131

¹⁴ Blackburn, R., "Slave Exploitation and the Elementary Structures of Enslavement", in Bush, M.L. (ed.), *Serfdom and Slavery: Studies in Legal Bondage*, Oxon, Routledge, 2013, pp. 159-161

¹⁵ Wickramasinghe, "Coloured Slavery", p. 173

of the King.¹⁶ Certain communal rights were bestowed upon the population as a result of this system. For example, this would allow the population a certain amount of land for themselves to do with as they wished. This allowed for a certain level of freedom as long as the King was recognised as such. Upholding common rights, then, formed the backbone of Sri Lankan society in pre-colonial times. So much so that communal identity under the King was also extended to those in servitude.

Within the structures of power expressed by the caste system, slaves were afforded several rights on account of the necessity to uphold caste-based honour. This system took precedence over power imbalances intrinsic to slavery. People could not be placed nor place themselves under a master that was of a lower caste. Similarly, they could not be forcibly married to someone considered 'lower' than themselves within the system. Furthermore, as land was not considered a marketable commodity it was given to slaves so they could live with their families and sustain themselves.¹⁷ The structures of power present in pre-colonial Sri Lankan society, then, allowed those in servitude to maintain the right to sustain themselves with lodgings and a family. Additionally, slavery was rarely permanent. The reasons for being forced into slavery were similar to that of other slave-holding societies. Unpaid debt, for example, was a very common reason to be put into servitude. This took the form of either placing yourself or pledging someone else, such as your daughter, into slavery. However once the debt was paid manumission was usually initiated by the master himself either by granting freedom from chores or accepting the value of the slave in cash.¹⁸ Multiple examples of personal manumission, such as the individual or a relative paying the manumission fee, have been recorded since ancient times.¹⁹ These routes to freedom highlight not only an impermanence of servitude but also an ability for slaves to collect some personal wealth. As has been demonstrated here, those in servitude in pre-colonial Sri Lanka had at least some rights due to the respect afforded to the caste-based system present in pre-colonial Sri Lanka. Patterson's claim that slavery is both permanent and dishonourable, then, does not apply here but provides a useful framework to consider the changes brought about by Portuguese influence on the structures of power in Sri Lanka.

1.1.2 Portuguese Slavery

The Portuguese arrived in Sri Lanka at the dawn of the 16th century, entering a country ruled by a Sinhalese king in the lowland capital Kotte. The primary objective of the Portuguese at this time was power and economic influence through trade. To do this they needed to wrestle the

¹⁶ De Silva, M.U., "Land Tenure, Caste System and the Rajakariya, Under Foreign Rule: A Review of Change in Sri Lanka Under Western Powers, 1597-1832", *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society of Sri Lanka*, vol. 37, 1992/1993, p. 1

¹⁷ Wickramasinghe, "Coloured Slavery", p. 160

¹⁸ Wickramasinghe, "Redemption of Slaves", p. 120

¹⁹ Wickramasinghe, "Redemption of Slaves", pp. 121-123

monopoly of trade held in the Indian Ocean space from the Arabs. Sri Lanka eventually turned into a valuable resource due to its very central location within this vast resource of space.²⁰ What they discovered on the island, however, was a power structure defined by a profession-based caste system that was sustained through common land rights. Feeling that this was insufficient for their broader aims of economic influence, they slowly began influencing the caste-system as well as those at the very top of it: kings.

The concept of the common land was one of the first major factors of Sri Lankan society to be directly and purposefully influenced by the profit-driven Portuguese. To do this, they offered to protect Sri Lankan interests from Arab traders who were smuggling in return for land.²¹ As their help was increasingly relied on, so too did the acquisition of land by the Portuguese increase. During this time customary dues and services to the state were not paid, leading to largely unsuccessful attempts by the king to de-base land acquisitions not expressly agreed upon by himself. In 1597, after Portugal seized control of Sri Lanka, customs and traditions were disregarded further. A Portuguese landholding group was established, allowing for Portuguese landholders to flout the rights of royalty and determine the allotment of the land.²² This change indicated a clean break from the past. An extraction of wealth was occurring in a space that was traditionally held as a common good. Both the method and resulting consequences of this land grabbing by the Portuguese is indicative of their wider disrupting influence on Sri Lankan society, particularly with regards to slavery.

The shift in the concept of land from a common good to a commercial one intersected with a shifting approach to slavery. Whereas pre-colonial slavery was tied more to the land they worked on as opposed to an economic benefit, the Portuguese brought strict profit-driven motives. To do this they increased both the number of slaves as well as changing their roles when enslaved. From their maritime empire they imported African people, captives of war and kidnapped native children to be sold into slavery. Internally, a greater acquisition of slaves was obtained by forcing those from lower castes into slavery due to poverty. These castes included *chaleas*, *paduwa* and *karawa*, whose professions were cinnamon peelers, palanquin bearers, and fisher folk respectively. With increased slave numbers, the Portuguese began to impose minimum quotas on resources produced. For example, irrespective of land held, those in the *chaleas* caste above 12 years old had to hand over large quantities of resources. This gave more power to the new Portuguese landlords who could demand more resources without fulfilling their share of the contract by providing provisions to maintain themselves, such as arable land. Moreover, the relative freedom afforded to pre-colonial Sri Lankan slaves was reduced dramatically, meaning slavery was indeed more akin to a state of permanence that Patterson stated.²³ This reduction in

²⁰ Pinto, *Being a Christian*, pp. 12-13

²¹ Pinto, *Being a Christian*, p. 16

²² De Silva, "Land Tenure", pp. 5-6

²³ Wickramasinghe, "Coloured Slavery", pp. 161-163

freedom intersected with abusing the established power structure of the caste system to force more people into slavery. In doing so the Portuguese began an ongoing clash with the existing Sinhalese rulers that ultimately led to a protracted shift in policy that was less pluralistic in nature. Parallel to the encroachment of Portuguese influence on Sri Lankan power, a Sinhalese stronghold was established to both consolidate Sinhalese power and retain old Sri Lankan customs from European influence. The Kingdom of Kandy was founded in the central area of Sri Lanka in the late 15th century. It was ruled by Sinhalese kings and considered itself the true ruler of the 'Kingdom of Sinhala', in reference to the Sinhalese people who inhabited the island and formed the majority.²⁴ This adoption of power took on a distinctly religious flavour, as will be explored later. What is important to note now, however, is that the code of law established during the Kandyan period, the *Niti Niganduwa*, established rules mainly to preserve the caste dignity of those that fell into slavery.²⁵ This meant that the right to land, property and manumission was upheld in the Kingdom of Kandy in direct contradiction with Portuguese rule. The embedded hierarchical nature of broader Sri Lankan society reflected in the caste system also led to people from the outer areas paying homage to the rulers of this Kingdom. This affirmed the sovereignty of the Sinhalese Kandy king over the wider Sri Lankan area whilst planting the seeds of a Sinhalese nationalism born in colonial resistance that can be felt to this day.²⁶

The structures of power, then, have been shown to have been profoundly affected by the arrival of the Portuguese. The Sinhalese rulers began to foster a sense of Sinhalese nationalism that directly contradicted Portuguese rule. That one of the foundations of this was to sustain caste dignity in relation to slavery demonstrates not only the importance of castes in the system of traditional power but also the perceived importance of slavery and its role in pre-colonial Sri Lankan society. In imposing a distinctly European colonial tint on slavery the Portuguese instilled a sense of Sinhalese nationalism that would, as will be further shown, manifest itself in the recent modern conflict between the Sinhalese and Tamil peoples.

1.2 Religion

Throughout Sri Lankan history religion has played a defining role in how power operates. These two factors have intersected throughout history to create an image of Sri Lanka as the natural possession of both the Buddha and the Sinhala people. This is vividly reflected in the words of a modern Sri Lankan person. They describe Sinhalese possession of Sri Lanka as mythical, linked

²⁴ Harris, E., *Religion, Space and Conflict in Sri Lanka: Colonial and Postcolonial Contexts*, Oxon, Routledge, 2018, pp. 15-16

²⁵ Wickramasinghe, C.S.M., "The Abolition of Colonial and Pre-Colonial 'Slavery' from Ceylon (Sri Lanka)", *Cultural and Social History*, vol. 7, n. 3, 2010, p. 318

²⁶ Harris, *Religion, Space and Conflict*, p. 16

with how the religion of Buddhism will find peace on the island. A combative hue was also placed on this mythos as the constant invasions to disrupt this peace were highlighted, with 'the worst of it all' being the "three European invasions."²⁷ Not only is it power and religion that intersect here, but also the historical role of colonialism. These three intersecting factors will be analysed through the lens of slavery in Sri Lankan society during this socially disruptive time to show that the modern tensions in Sri Lankan society derive from the time of colonialism.

Interrogating this space as a religious one sheds light on a dynamic, imagined and socially produced space that intermingles with issues of power and identity.²⁸ Indeed some scholars have noted that the deconstruction of space involves a process of "inclusion and exclusion, of appropriation and alienation."²⁹ Applying this here asks revealing questions of the nature of Portuguese influence on Sri Lankan territory and their connections with the native elites. Moreover, the dynamism of such a space is heavily influenced, as David Morgan argues, by belief. Belief is not so much an abstract proposition, but a "shared imaginary" expressed through practice, materiality and aesthetics.³⁰

The idea of belief as a 'shared imaginary' is best emphasized by the sacred importance placed upon the city of Kandy, the capital of the Kandyan Kingdom. In a spatial analysis of the city of Kandy, James Duncan concluded that it was purposefully designed to reflect the kings' responsibility to protect Buddhism and to impress the people through the rulers' power. The use of a 'symbolic layout' and religious symbols positioned the king as a mediator between the gods and the people, and protector of the Buddha's presence through his relics.³¹ Therefore the tributes that poured in from the outer areas not only affirmed sovereignty as mentioned before but affirmed the Sinhalese Kandy king as a god-king who was governed by Buddhism. These kinds of tributes encapsulate what I have termed the 'fragmented harmony' of Sri Lankan history. This fragmented harmony is not exclusive to space, however. Within Kandy an inbuilt, unity-creating hierarchy in the form of the caste system is retained. Sinhalese kings preside over not only Sinhalese but Tamil and Muslim minorities amongst others. This unified hierarchy has been usefully termed as 'inclusive subordination'.³² Other peoples and religions are welcomed into society, as long as they took their rightful place under the Sinhalese god-king. Intensifying the

²⁷ Harris, *Religion, Space and Conflict*, p. 13

²⁸ Harris, *Religion, Space and Conflict*, pp. 2-3

²⁹ Winkler, U., Fernández, L.R., and Leirvik, O., "Preface: Contested Spaces, Common Ground? The Spatial Turn in Intercultural Theology and Interreligious Studies", in Winkler, U., Fernández, L.R., and Leirvik, O. (eds.), *Contested Spaces, Common Ground: Space and Power Structures in Contemporary Multireligious Societies*, Leiden, Brill, 2016, p. XII

³⁰ Morgan, D., "The Matter of Belief", in Morgan, D. (ed.), *Religion and Material Culture: The Matter of Belief*, Abingdon, Routledge, 2009, p. 11

³¹ Duncan, J.S., *The City as Text: The Politics of Landscape in the Kandyan Kingdom*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 2005, p. 59

³² Harris, *Religion, Space and Conflict*, p. 16

fragmentation between Buddhism and other religions represented a slow retreat from the 'syncretic inculturation' of the past. Consequently, a 'shared imaginary' helped develop a pan-Sinhala Buddhist consciousness led by the king of Kandy through the use of religious symbols and metaphors.

While the Kingdom of Kandy provided a space for Sinhala consciousness to flourish, the role of Christianity in 'Portuguese' Sri Lanka affected the social fabric of the island whilst ultimately bolstering Sinhalese nationalism. The Portuguese, approaching Sri Lanka with a sword in one hand and a cross in the other, set about their conversion task in two ways: converting the elites in society as well as targeting those in lower castes.³³ Converting the elites was, on the face of it, successful. Members of the royal family and nobles of the court became Catholics and as a result many churches were built leading to extensive conversions in the Portuguese-influenced coastal areas.³⁴ However, digging deeper reveals that the conversion had a limited effect. Conversion was initially done as part of a negotiation tactic between the king and the Portuguese in return for help against raiding Arab traders. Moreover, Catholicism was treated as simply an addition to the existing religious landscape. Figures such as Jesus and the Virgin Mary were absorbed culturally much like the Hindu gods Viṣṇu and Saman were.³⁵ These two factors meant that for the rulers adopting Christianity was an extension of the 'inclusivist subordination' explored previously. That is to say that it could exist within an environment where Sinhalese Buddhism was king.

Converting the lower castes had a stronger effect on Sri Lankan society due to its ability to disrupt the inherent power structure in Sri Lanka: the caste system. This was done in two main ways. Firstly, violence was used to intimidate and subsequently convert the locals. In 1546 the Portuguese ordered the destruction of all temples on the island. Churches were erected in their wake, providing a tangible example of where the method of using the sword and the cross in Sri Lanka coalesced. Buddhist monks were forced to flee for their lives, finding refuge in the Kandyan Kingdom.³⁶ This disrupting wave sent further fractures through a Sri Lanka known for its religious harmony while at the same time bolstering Sinhalese nationalistic identity through these divides. The role of Christianity for everyday people was transformative, and this is highlighted in how attitudes shifted for the lower castes through the adoption of Christianity.

Outside of the Kandyan Kingdom Christianity had a transformative effect on Sri Lankan society. This was achieved not only through the violent destruction of non-Christian places of worship but

³³ Paranativana, K.D., "Suppression of Buddhism and Aspects of Indigenous Culture under the Portuguese and the Dutch", *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society of Sri Lanka*, vol. 49, 2004, pp. 3-4

³⁴ Pinto, *Being a Christian*, pp. 73-74

³⁵ Obeyesekere, G., "Between the Portuguese and the Nāyakas: the Many Faces of the Kandyan Kingdom, 1591-1765", in Biedermann, Z. and Strathern, A. (eds.), *Sri Lanka at the Crossroads of History*, London, UCL Press, 2017, p. 162

³⁶ Paranativana, "Suppression of Buddhism", pp. 6-7

also through certain incentives given to incorporate people into the newly established systems of power. The caste system was rigid in pre-colonial times, identifying people as a particular profession with little chance for climbing the proverbial 'social ladder'. This was disrupted by the Portuguese through bestowing certain freedoms upon people who converted to Christianity. For example, a woman of the *somenos* caste (tanners and shoemakers) who was previously a slave stopped covering her head outside the church. This violated the old custom of the land yet sheds light on how Christianity disrupted people's behaviour on a day-to-day level, making it more 'European'.³⁷ The motivations behind this are clear: the existing religions on the island, primarily Buddhism and Hinduism, were seen as idolatrous and should be eradicated.³⁸ Moreover, in the example of the woman from the *somenos* caste, removing the obligations of slavery shows how the Portuguese attempted to weaken and delegitimize the old Sinhalese customs.

As explored previously, slaves' role in society was closely tied to the caste system and the associated concept of a common land. This position was purposefully shifted by the Portuguese, who pushed for a more 'European'-type of slavery resulting in a dissolution of rights and expansion of the enslaved labour force. Here it will be shown how power and religion intersected during the crucial flashpoint of colonial influence to change slavery's role in colonial and even post-colonial Sri Lanka.

Before the arrival of the Europeans, slavery had been practiced on the island during both the Anuradhapura period (from the 4th century BCE to the 11th century CE) and the Polonnaruwa period (from the 11th century CE to the 14th century CE) in conjunction with institutions including Buddhist temples and royal households.³⁹ The slaves used in temples were sometimes called *ārāmikas*, meaning attendant to a monastery, and as slaves were held in high regard. There was a certain pride associated with being in servitude to the monastery. Indeed, King Aggabodhi IV even granted his own relatives to the temple. Moreover, there is no evidence to suggest that they held any special privileges while in servitude, showing how religion held a revered position in society that is represented through the role of slaves.⁴⁰ Having *ārāmikas* in Buddhist temples being held in such high regard is also evidence of how 'inclusivist subordination' can be found as a common thread in Sri Lanka from pre-colonial times. Indeed, even Tamil people who follow the Hindu religion gave slaves to temples as a show of good faith. This helped cement Sri Lankan society as a tolerable one that incorporated other religions, albeit in a subordinate sense. In addition, associating high status and pride with serving Buddhism highlights how this particular religion, more so than the others in society, was considered at the top of the social hierarchy.

³⁷ Wickramasinghe, "Coloured Slavery", p. 163

³⁸ Pieris and Ferguson, "Portuguese Ceylon", p. 104

³⁹ Wickramasinghe, N., *Slave in a Palanquin: Colonial Servitude and Resistance in Sri Lanka*, New York, Columbia University Press, 2020, p. 6

⁴⁰ Gunawardana, R.A.L.H., *Robe and Plough: Monasticism and Economic Interest in Early Medieval Sri Lanka*, Arizona, University of Arizona Press, 1982, pp. 97-98

Pertinently, the seeds of Sinhalese Buddhist nationalism were being sewn even before Portuguese influence.

With regards to slavery, the adoption of Christianity was a direct route out of servitude, but the rate of re-enslavement went up. Religion in this case establishes itself as a symbol of not only relative freedom, compared to the plantation slavery exercised by the Portuguese, but rebellion. To do this the Kandyan Kingdom exercised their power to distribute 'certificates of freedom' to ex-slaves. Perhaps cynically this was beneficial to the Buddhist elite as people were incentivised to join the stronghold in the country which consolidated their right to rule. Nevertheless, the incentive for people to move was real and demonstrates how pre-colonial religious power structures intertwined with slavery. Moreover, this promise of freedom consolidated Sinhalese power and ultimately their perceived legitimacy to rule. Slavery's intersection between religion and power, then, also underscores how Sri Lankans rebelled against the Portuguese at this time. This rebellion was as we have seen achieved by lower castes but also the Sinhalese elite. In this case, the rebellion took a subtler tone, but one that had foundations in the idea of Sinhalese nationalism.

1.3 Alagiyavanna and the Development of Sinhalese Nationalism

The established interaction between inclusivist subordination and Sinhalese nationalism, described by Elizabeth Harris as 'exclusivism', took on a deeper meaning during the time of colonial expansion. This interplay of power and religion is keenly evident in the poetic works of Alagiyavanna Mukaveti. He was a renowned Sinhala poet during this period of initial colonial influence. The scope of his works was vast yet illustrated a tale of a man whose beliefs morphed and adapted to an external encroachment onto internal power structures. Tellingly these shifts tend to reflect the resistance and subsequent perceived tactical acceptance of Christianity within the wider Sinhala consciousness.

*Pay homage with devotion, my friend, to the venerable Tooth Relic,
Which is like the moon decorating the sky of the mouth of the Best of Sages,
Whose resplendent lotus like feet, being worshiped, always shine,
With the rays of the crest-gems on the crowns of the brahmās, gods, humans, and nāgas.⁴¹*

Written in *Sāvul Sandēśaya*, the name of one of Alagiyavanna's works, a strong reflection of Sinhalese nationalism can be seen. Referencing the Tooth Relic, an essential component of justifying one's claim to the throne, was a Sinhalese Relic dating back to at least the eleventh century. This item is portrayed as the primary core off which others reside (different gods and

⁴¹ Berkwitz, *Buddhist Poetry and Colonialism*, p. 57

humans alike). What we can see here is perhaps in a not-so-subtle sense evidence of Sinhalese nationalism existing even since pre-colonial times. This can also be construed as a reflection of the rigidity of the caste system and the 'natural' order of things. Crucially the dichotomy of both hierarchy and regulated acceptance of religions is evident, revealing a somewhat pluralistic society.

Regulated pluralism in Sri Lanka came under threat during early colonial times, leading to the denouncement of other religions as a protective measure. In *Subhāṣitaya*, dated after *Sāvul Sandēśaya*, Alagiyavanna wrote:

*Forsaking the refuge of the Great Sage, whose feet rest upon the
Heads of all gods and persons,
And venerating other gods [instead], those beings,
Who guard their false views for the sake of pure liberation,
Are like those who struggle to draw water from the dimbula flower.⁴²*

Here a greater resistance to other religions can be seen, most clearly in the evocative language of 'false views for the sake of pure liberation'. Speaking of false religions in the hope of liberation tells of a certain anxiety that "Sinhala authors could no longer assume the predominance of Buddhist teachings in the society of that time".⁴³ In the context of the time of the Portuguese sword and cross an elitist consolidation of power occurred taking the form of eliminating other perceived threats or weaknesses to their power. It is here that the sharp edges of Sinhalese nationalism began to take form, rendering other religions as less palatable and therefore unfit for Sri Lankan society.

Sharpening itself against the Portuguese was, if we take Alagiyavanna as an example, a temporary measure. An acceptance of Christianity followed, although the extent of this is debatable.

*Who is great in terms of virtue,
Who is engaged in the protection of the world,
And who possesses wondrous, supernatural powers,
May the Lord Jesus Christ protect us!⁴⁴*

Taken from *Kustantīnu Haṭana*, the Sinhalese poet demonstrates his conversion to Christianity in the early 17th century. However, the reality is perhaps more complex than is first assumed. Both here and elsewhere post-conversion, Jesus Christ is portrayed as one who is on the path to

⁴² Berkwitz, *Buddhist Poetry and Colonialism*, pp. 150-151

⁴³ Berkwitz, *Buddhist Poetry and Colonialism*, p. 152

⁴⁴ Berkwitz, *Buddhist Poetry and Colonialism*, p. 195

becoming a Buddha, a bodhisattva.⁴⁵ In highlighting Jesus Christ's offer of protection to devotees instead of a higher purpose suggests that Alagiyavanna was quietly resisting the Portuguese in keeping with the policy of 'inclusivist subordination'. In other words, his Buddhist roots are still intact in the face of Portuguese oppression. A more pragmatic reason could also explain this conversion. As other landowning Sinhala elites did, conversion to Christianity was a way to retain a higher quality of life.⁴⁶ Whatever the reason, it is pertinent to consider here how even in the mire of violent Portuguese expansion into Sri Lankan territory, seeds of Sinhalese Buddhism can be found amongst the works of Sinhala elites. Considering the initial reaction to encroachment was the disavowment of other religions as a protective measure, the seeds of Sinhalese nationalism can be found at the intersection of power and religion during colonisation.

1.4 Long Shadows

A particular Sri Lankan origin story is told to Sinhalese people around the world. It tells of Vijaya, son of an Indo-Aryan king in North India who was exiled to the island just south of India: Sri Lanka. Here he encounters two different tribes of demons and cannibals, overcomes them, and ushers in an era of prosperity and unity for the Sri Lankan people. This well-known story serves as the origin story of the Sinhalese while also legitimizing their right to rule, in the eyes of modern Sinhala nationalists.⁴⁷

The idea of a Sinhalese right to rule is deeply rooted yet, as demonstrated, has been forced to adapt. The 'fractured harmony' that developed in pre-colonial Sri Lanka was sustained under the condition that other religions knew that they had to submit to the Buddhist power structures on the island. Aside from the aforementioned origin story, religious institutions legitimised this right to rule by benevolently allowing other religions in their spaces on the condition that they acknowledge the supremacy of the holiest of Buddhist relics. This relatively unchallenged rule was disrupted by the Portuguese, almost shattering the fractured harmony of Sinhalese rule in Sri Lanka. In retreat, Sinhalese nationalism took on a monotheistic tone, beginning to disregard other religions to rebel against the Portuguese invasion. Analysis of Alagiyavanna's works provides a prime example of how the Sinhala elite adapted to the disruptions caused by the Portuguese and indicates how Sinhalese nationalism survived.

This intertwining of power and religion is most sharply felt when considering the differing approaches to the institution of slavery. The Portuguese used it to flatten the existing caste

⁴⁵ Berkwitz, *Buddhist Poetry and Colonialism*, p. 195

⁴⁶ Berkwitz, *Buddhist Poetry and Colonialism*, p. 134. There are academic debates about whether or not this pragmatism coincided with a genuine change of religious heart, and whilst interesting these are outside of the scope of this chapter

⁴⁷ James, P., "Despite the Terrors of Typologies: The Importance of Understanding Categories of Difference and Identity", *Interventions*, vol. 17, n. 2, 2015, p. 189

system, increasing re-enslavement rates while subsequently pushing people away for freedom. There were differing layers to the rebellions of course as evidence suggests conversion to Christianity occurred to go against traditional Buddhist clothing. Most pertinent here however is how the differing approaches by the Sinhalese and Portuguese caused Sinhalese nationalism to morph and develop into a less pluralistic ideology and set it on its course for the modern day. How does this reflect in the modern day? The recent end of the civil war in which the Sinhalese-led army crushed the Tamil army after 26 years underscores the lack of religious pluralism that was evident in pre-colonial Sri Lankan society. It is important to note that since the Portuguese Sri Lanka was subsequently colonized by the Dutch and the British. This long period of colonisation led to shifting power dynamics intrinsically linked with the dominant colonial power of the time. However, the roots of the modern, less tolerant Sinhalese-Buddhist consciousness can evidently be found at the moment of Portuguese invasion. It did not bring about a new concept of Sinhalese nationalism but instead forced it into a metaphorical corner, forcing a concentration and exclusivist process that bled into strengthening the already existing caste system, forming a power and religious power structure at the top. Or, as Indunil Janaka Kodithuwakku succinctly states: "Portuguese colonialism left an indelible scar in Sinhalese-Buddhist consciousness."⁴⁸

⁴⁸ Kodithuwakku, I.J., "Encountering Different Cultures: Concords and Frictions in Pre-Colonial, Colonial and Post-Colonial Sri Lanka", *Annali di Studi Religiosi*, vol. 21, 2020, p. 223

Chapter Two: Migration, Indenture, and the Struggles of Tamil Labourers in Ceylon

“Diaspora, the voluntary or forcible movement of peoples from their homelands into new regions, is a central historical fact of colonization ... the practises of slavery and indenture ... resulted in worldwide colonial diasporas.”¹

In light of the 2024 presidential election in Sri Lanka, questions surrounding the rights of estate workers of Indian origin were being woven into the national discussion. As highlighted at the outset of this research, one particular headline stated how one presidential candidate aimed to fully integrate these workers into Sri Lankan society. Not only shall they be labourers, but they will be “entrepreneurs with equal opportunities in political, educational, health, and economic sectors.”² The political willingness to discuss the productive integration of this group is a relatively new phenomenon. Indeed, the necessity to raise this issue in the most recent national election alludes to the legacy of British colonial rule that reinforced the social stratification of these indentured labourers. It ensured that they were confined to the lowest rungs of society with limited access to economic and political opportunities. The prominence of this issue in contemporary political discourse highlights the resilience of the social stratification that sidelined these estate workers. Further, it demonstrates how this marginalisation remains embedded within Sri Lankan society, creating a long shadow from colonial Ceylon to independent Sri Lanka.³ The roots of such social stratification are multitude. The international expansion of slavery at the flashpoint of initial European contact in Sri Lanka led to not only ethnic and cultural shifts but also an increasingly aggressive Sinhalese Buddhist nationalism that shunned other ethnicities and religions away from power. Against this backdrop, then, this chapter will explore another flashpoint in time: the era of the coffee plantations in Sri Lanka. This crop dominated the economic development of the island from the 1830s to the 1880s. This boom in economic development was marked by the arrival of indentured labourers of South India into the plantations of Sri Lanka. Whilst fluctuating through the decades, this mass migration of people changed the makeup of Sri Lankan society, culminating in the latest census numbering them at around 840,000 or 4.2% of the total population.⁴ This emergence of the plantation system as well as the commencement of the steady migration of Indian workers to Sri Lanka has been described

¹ Ashcroft, B., Griffiths, G. and Tiffin, H., *Post-Colonial Studies: The Key Concepts*, London, Routledge, 2007, pp. 61-62

² *Daily Mirror*, 13 August 2024, p. 3

³ *Daily Mirror*, 13 August 2024, p. 3. The Tamil Progressive Alliance, a grouping of organisations that fight for the rights of Tamil people of Indian origin, stated that “... while the estate community has Indian origins, they wished to be recognized and treated as equals in Sri Lankan society.” The choice of ‘while’ here indicates an unwillingness to accept them on account of their relatively recent migration to Sri Lanka.

⁴ Minority Rights Group, “Tamils in Sri Lanka”, www.minorityrights.org, last date of consultation 17 September 2024

as two of the most important features of its economic history.⁵ The emerging commercial mould impressed by British rule led to the development of “strangers” that, as destiny would have it, produced a long temporal shadow of a social problem which dwarfed all others.⁶

Such a long shadow stemmed from a series of events that eventually stumbled onto South Indian workers broadly as a matter of convenience. As will be explored shortly, the abolition of slavery, global natural disasters and colonial racism culminated in these systematic migrations to Sri Lanka. The first migrations began in 1827 at the behest of Governor Sir Edward Barnes, and migrations for the dominant crop of coffee continued until around 1880.⁷ Upon their arrival, these labourers were placed in a system that found strength in segregating the new workforce from the rest of society.⁸ Enmeshed within the wider policy of colonial Britain dividing ethnicities in their colonies to consolidate power, this segregation resulted in societal problems that encompassed education, health and gender as well as reflecting on the nature of rebellions against the colonial state.

These themes will be explored in later chapters. For now, it is important to consider exactly who these migrant workers were and place their individual circumstances within the currents of temporality. The abolition of slavery in 1833 had far-reaching effects on the wider colonial empire. Upon abolition the central hub for coffee production, the West Indies, suffered a severe labour shortage as newly emancipated workers “refused to serve as plantation labour.”⁹ The resulting drop in coffee exports to England led to a reduction in the duty of Ceylon coffee in 1835 as well as a steady stream of minds with expertise in the field of coffee cultivation.¹⁰

These factors explain the wider economic reasons as to why Sri Lanka was almost hand-selected by the empire to become a global leader in coffee exports. But what of the local effects? Indeed, such a migration led to an almost immediate ostracization from the people already residing in Sri Lanka. From the beginning, they were perceived by the state and other ethnic communities in Sri Lanka as a source of cheap migrant labour and not as citizens. They were Indian residents and while they were in Ceylon they were the responsibility of their employer, the estate management.¹¹ Viewing them as simply bodies used for plantation work rather than as human beings with rights was reflected even in a Tamil ‘coolly’ guide that was distributed around colonial and industrial stakeholders. This piece of literature has an interesting duality. Its existence feeds

⁵ Driesen, I., *The Long Walk: Indian Plantation Labour in Sri Lanka in the Nineteenth Century* New Delhi, Prestige Books, 1997, p. 9

⁶ De Silva, K.M., *Social Policy and Missionary Organisations in Ceylon, 1840-1855*, London, Longmans for the Royal Commonwealth Society, 1965, p. 270

⁷ Nadesan, S., *A History of the Up-Country Tamil People in Sri Lanka*, Colombo, Ranco Printers and Publishers Ltd., 1993, pp. 16-17

⁸ Chandrabose, A.S. and Sivapragasm, P.P., *Red Colour of Tea: Central Issues that Impact the Tea Plantation Community in Sri Lanka*, Colombo, Human Development Organisation, 2011, pp. 14-15

⁹ Nadesan, *Up-Country Tamil People*, p. 17

¹⁰ Nadesan, *Up-Country Tamil People*, p. 17

¹¹ Nallasamy, A., *Rights of Tamil Children in a Plantation Community*, Colombo, Initiative in Research and Education for Development in Asia (INASIA), 2000, p. 3

the 'othering' of these labourers whilst also reflecting concerns about their humanity. How much can they pluck? Where and when would they laugh? How much could they carry? These concerns were considered, of course, at a distance. These workers formed part of the natural landscape, meshing themselves in like, as some contemporary observers quipped, urchins. As mentioned in the introduction, Mythri Jegathesan stated that these labourers were viewed as a people that had simply sprung from the earth, not from women's wombs. A fixed point rather than a mobile one.¹² However, the considerations floated by the Tamil 'coolly' guide also highlight the importance of this manual labour. In an era of technological advancements these labourers proved to go against the grain. Their hands fuelled the explosion of coffee and later tea exports that became both an important cog in the British colonial economy as well as the lynchpin of the Sri Lankan economy.¹³

Considering the layers of power alluded to here, namely the British, the estates, and the indentured labourers, this chapter will interrogate the experiences of the newly migrated indentured labourers into Ceylon and extrapolate these into the modern day. This paracolonial lens will consider how the broader considerations of empire intermingled with the middlemen of estate management to influence the experience of the Tamil labourers during the coffee plantation era. In doing so, the machinations of colonial power will be illuminated, showing how tensions between the British and the estates resulted in the long shadow we see today in modern Sri Lankan society. Further, the academic grounding being laid here will provide the framework for later chapters on these indentured labourers' agency. This fresh diaspora on the shores of Ceylon, in spite of the colonial power structures, manoeuvred through physical isolation from other ethnicities and historical silencing to establish a distinct identity. Or, as Stuart Hall states that diaspora identities are "constantly producing and reproducing themselves anew, through transformation and difference." Therefore, the diaspora experience, pertinently here that of the Indian Tamil experience, is not static or fixed but "subject to the continuous play of history, culture and power."¹⁴

2.1 The Genesis of Migration

Before discussing the experiences of these new labourers on the shores of Sri Lanka, it is vital to investigate why these migrations occurred in the first place. It will be shown that due to a complex interplay of factors such as the abolition of slavery, British economic interests, and

¹² Jegathesan, M., *Tea and Solidarity: Tamil Women and Work in Postwar Sri Lanka*, United States of America, University of Washington Press, 2019, p. 76

¹³ Wickramasinghe, N., *Metallic Modern: Everyday Machines in Colonial Sri Lanka*, New York, Bergahn Books, 2014, p. 138

¹⁴ Hall, S., "Cultural Identity and Diaspora", in Williams, P. and Chrisman, L. (eds.), *Colonial Discourse and Postcolonial Theory: A Reader*, London, Routledge, p. 396

cultural convenience, labourers from the Tamil Nadu region were seen as the best option to introduce to the Sri Lankan plantation labour force.

Perhaps the root cause for considering a migratory workforce was the unwillingness of the local population to undertake hard manual labour in exchange for wages. Following the abolition of slavery in 1833 within the British Empire, there was an assumption on the part of the British that any work would be gladly taken up in exchange for a wage. Indeed, at the genesis of the plantation era, a small number of the local population primarily composed of Sinhalese peasantry were tasked with clearing forests to make way for the coffee plantations.¹⁵ The British officials were dissatisfied with the turnout, however. The majority of the peasantry were more than happy to tend to their little holdings and were not enamoured by the offer of wages.¹⁶ Such a misalignment of priorities between the local peasantry and the colonial officials has been put down to views on wealth accumulation. The assumption by the British was that the offer of wages would motivate the Sinhalese people as this was a chance to better themselves. This mindset, borne in the midst of an individualistic British society, directly contradicted the more collectivist mindset of the Sinhalese people. As Ralph Pieris states, “in traditional Ceylon the basic structure of the social fabric and the constitution of its ethos were such, that there was no inducement for individuals to exert themselves in accumulating wealth.”¹⁷

Whilst this can be true, it is pertinent to further contextualise this misalignment in interest. As explored in chapter one, Sinhalese Buddhist nationalism gripped the island in the wake of the initial colonial invasion of the Portuguese. The city of Kandy became a stronghold of Sri Lankan traditions, including that of the caste system. A certain antipathy from the working class to receiving wages for labour work had roots in the social system that had defined society for centuries.¹⁸ Further, as was alluded to before, the Sinhalese already had small plots of land. These were small but contained sustenance sources such as cows and fruit gardens. Landlessness was not an issue for them and as a result there was little motivation to give it up to work on coffee plantations.¹⁹ These two issues of caste and land led to this initial hiccup in labour numbers but, as will be shown, these came to define much of the legislation from the British to ensure the smooth-running of a plantation economy.

Considering the lack of both available and dependable workforce within Sri Lanka, eyes moved abroad for potential labourers. The international context is crucial here. Chinese labour was considered but deemed impracticable as there was a more convenient source of labour much closer to Ceylon: the southern Tamil Nadu region of India.²⁰ These labourers were convenient in

¹⁵ Driesen, *Long Walk*, p. 12

¹⁶ Driesen, *Long Walk*, p. 12

¹⁷ Pieris, R., “Society and Ideology in Ceylon During a ‘Time of Troubles’, 1795-1850”, *University of Ceylon Review*, vol. 9, n. 3, 1951, p. 177

¹⁸ Driesen, *Long Walk*, p. 13

¹⁹ Boyd, W., “Ceylon and its Pioneers”, *The Ceylon Literary Register*, vol. 2, n. 32, 1888, p. 249

²⁰ Nadesan, *Up-Country Tamil People*, p. 6

many ways. Their proximity to Ceylon meant travel costs were minimised. Moreover, the existence of the centuries-old Tamil Sri Lankan population meant there were some existing shared cultural traits, such as religion and language. Finally, due to the slave revolt in the West Indies in 1833, and the subsequent abolition of slavery in British colonies, importing slaves was not an option.²¹ However, this shift in policy from slavery to indentured labour on plantations would prove to be economically fruitful for the British.

2.1.1 Plantation Economics

Economic benefit is a common thread that defined British policies regarding the import of Indian Tamil labour. Before going into specific directives regarding these factors and their relation to the experiences of the indentured labourers, it is useful to interrogate how plantations using indentured labour is not only cheaper than slave labour but also beneficial to retain colonial power structures. Rachel Kurian identifies three reasons as to why this is the case. Firstly, in places where slave plantations existed, the cost of recruitment and transport weighed heavily. This was due to the fact that the local populations had been decimated to the point of needing external migrations.²² As has been explored, the situation in Ceylon offered a more nuanced take. Due to the Portuguese colonial flashpoint, slavery took on a decidedly 'European' tint by increasingly importing enslaved peoples from regions such as Africa. Moreover, the consolidation of Sinhala Buddhism allowed for the caste system to retain its lustre, thus causing problems for the British hiring local indentured workers. Consequently, the migration of Indian Tamils into Ceylon incurred the same expenses. However, the method of transporting these labourers with the 'kangany' system was not only inexpensive for the British but also solidified their position within the colonial power structure.

The second reason Kurian identifies is the issue of retaining a permanent workforce on the plantations. An element of force had to be applied under slavery to maintain a constant workforce temporarily. Plantations were, in effect, designed to replicate "a class structure of workers and owners, connected hierarchically by a staff line of overseers and managers."²³ This system is true of both slave and indentured labourer plantations, but the former's cost is higher due to the lack of coercion with wages leading to increased incidents of desertion.²⁴ A similar cost applicable for both types is that associated with the reproduction of labour. Retaining a permanent workforce requires the construction and running of services such as schools for the new generation of labourers as well as hospitals for their general health. Under slave plantations these served their minimum requirements of keeping the workforce able-bodied. For indentured

²¹ Nadesan, *Up-Country Tamil People*, p. 6

²² Kurian, *State, Capital and Labour*, p. 5

²³ Kurian, *State, Capital and Labour*, p. 6

²⁴ Kurian, *State, Capital and Labour*, pp. 5-6

labourers, this was subject to pressures from both the plantation and the British to balance well-being and cost-cutting with those on a wage. Consequently, the importance of providing services to indentured labourers required a complex interplay between employer and the colonial office resulting in fluctuating results that cast a long shadow into the current day. Whilst these will be discussed in chapter four, the strict hierarchy of plantations meant that both slaves and indentured labourers shared a relatively powerless position. Further complexities were introduced for the Indian Tamil population as they were subject to extra layers of hierarchy that further solidified the position of both the plantation owners as well as the British.

Lastly, Kurian states how the need to provide slaves with subsistence is eradicated if other forms of labour were available. Specifically, she cites Wallerstein who states that the cost of subsistence is eradicated if the worker is allowed a small plot of land to work on. Reductions in remuneration would cover the cost to the employer of such a plot of land, therefore further cheapening the cost of labour in contrast with that of slave labour.²⁵

Taken together, the contrast between slave and indentured labour plantations in the economic sense illuminates some analytical roots of this thesis. The increased state intervention required by the increasingly complex developments of social services post-abolition has led to plantations themselves being described by several scholars as ‘enclaves’ or ‘total institutions’ in which micro-capitalist tendencies emerge.²⁶ This is true of certain factors such as the strict plantation hierarchy and the general need to retain a permanent workforce. However, it is too broad of a concept. Selvaratnam described plantations as ‘imperial assets’, in which external factors shaped the internal structures. Indeed, he goes on to say that “... the extra economic measures and processes that this mode of production found necessary to use with the support of the colonial state in order to initiate a continuous supply of South Indian workers and incorporate them into the plantation system has received very little treatment”.²⁷ These extra economic measures that he mentions, which include recruitment and development of social services amongst others, are the direct result of colonial intervention. This thesis aims to go further, arguing that not only did this shift affect the economic considerations at the top of the hierarchy, but the migration of Indian Tamils to Ceylon sparked a radical shift that fundamentally changed the plantation as well as Sri Lankan society as a whole.

2.1.2 Colebrook-Cameron Commission

²⁵ Kurian, *State, Capital and Labour*, p. 7

²⁶ Kurian, *State, Capital and Labour*, p. 32; Mandle, R., “The Re-Establishment of the Plantation Economy in the South 1865-1910”, *The Review of Black Political Economy*, vol. 3, n. 2, 1973, pp. 81-86; Smith, R.T., “Social Stratification, Cultural Pluralism and Integration in West Indian Societies”, in Lewis, S. and Mathews, T. (eds.), *Caribbean Integration: Papers on Social, Political, and Economic Integration*, Puerto Rico, Institute of Caribbean Studies, 1967, pp. 253-256

²⁷ Selvaratnam, V., “A Theoretical Perspective in the Study of Plantation Systems: The Malaysian Case”, *Economic and Political Weekly*, vol. 23, n. 21, 1988, p. 1080

As discussed, the shift from slave to indentured labourer plantations kept a strict plantation hierarchy that allowed those in power to keep a strict mandate. In the case of the coffee plantations in Ceylon, the British colonial government set on a course of development that would drastically disrupt the ancient internal societal structures of the island. To achieve this, the British first had to conquer the Sinhalese stronghold in Sri Lanka: Kandy.

Following the period of Portuguese colonisation on the maritime provinces of Sri Lanka, the British embarked on a “campaign of cruelty and inhumanity” that would lead to the conquering of Kandy in 1815.²⁸ Considerations of the local people regarding this matter will be explored in greater depth in the subsequent chapter. Here, the British view will be largely considered. Following their full colonisation of the island in 1815, ordinances largely had two main goals: to develop the island for a full-scale plantation economy and to consolidate power through exacerbating existing structural divisions between Sri Lankans. Both of these motivations are littered in official correspondence around this time. For example, in a report into the maladministration of British officials in Westminster in 1850, the low country Sinhalese people that had been under European colonial rule since the Portuguese are said to “have been in the actual progress of education and civilisation”. Kandyans, on the other hand, needed to be brought into this historical path of ‘civilisation’ as they “consider themselves as a distinct race, and a distinct nation.” For the British this idea of ‘civilisation’ is inextricably linked with development. Indeed the low country Sinhalese are praised in this report as being “anxious to contribute, both in labour and in money, towards the formation of roads, and they have offered the Government every assistance in carrying them out.”²⁹ This mindset of associating ‘civilisation’ and development drove the colonial ordinances that defined plantation development on the island. This is reflected in perhaps the most influential commission set up by the British for the time period in question: the Colebrook-Cameron Commission.

In the immediate years following the annexation of Kandy, expenditure on the island far outweighed revenue. This was in large part due to the increased costs associated with the development between the upcountry and the low country.³⁰ Determined to rectify the situation, the British government sent a commission to the island to investigate. Lasting three years between 1829 and 1832, the Colebrook-Cameron Commission made sweeping recommendations for administrative, financial, economic, and judicial reform.³¹ What resulted were recommendations, most of which were accepted, that represented the first shift to

²⁸ Vimalananda, T., *The Great Rebellion of 1818: The Story of the First War of Independence and Betrayal of the Nation*, Colombo, M.D. Gunasena & Co. Ltd., 1970, p. xlvi

²⁹ Vimalanda, *The Great Rebellion*, p. lxxiv

³⁰ Sivasundaram, S., “Tales of the Land: British Geography and Kandy Resistance in Sri Lanka, c. 1803-1850”, *Modern Asian Studies*, vol. 41, n. 5, 2007, p. 950

³¹ Britannica, “Colebrook-Cameron Commission”, <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Colebrook-Cameron-Commission>, last date of consultation 22 September 2024

constitutional government, as well as the beginnings of a standardised system of governance encompassing justice, education, and civil administration. Indeed, Colvin R. de Silva views these reforms as the dawn of a “new era”, meaning “Ceylon was firmly set on the highway of modern development.”³² The sweeping reforms are as follows:

“(1) that the formerly absolute power of the governor of Ceylon be limited by a separation of the executive, legislative, and judicial authorities, a step that would entail the creation of an Executive Council, which was to act jointly with the governor in decision making, and a Legislative Council, which was to include some native Ceylonese members; (2) that all of Ceylon be united under one administrative system; (3) that more civil service posts be opened to natives; (4) that a uniform judicial system be created to promote greater efficiency and equal treatment before the law of Ceylonese and Europeans; (5) that *rājākariya*, the traditional system of land tenure, be abolished, along with government trade monopolies; and (6) that a uniform system of education be developed, with English as the medium of instruction.”³³

What follows is an analysis of this commission and how it signalled the British colonial government's wishes to incorporate the newly acquired Kandyan lands into Ceylon. Generally, a strong focus on colonizing the administrative structures of the island were seen as key. By abolishing traditional structures and replacing them with more ‘European’ entities, it would benefit Britain significantly on the international scale by allowing easier integration of the Ceylonese economy into the global economy. Moreover, allowing Ceylonese members to join these new structures would not only legitimise them to the local population but also allow Britain to utilise pre-existing caste structures to strengthen their grip on power. Finally, the broad effects of these structural shifts in relation with the influx of indentured labourers shall be put into focus, in particular with regards to land developments and the incorporation of old Ceylon elites into the colonial apparatus. Thus, will provide a useful analytical backdrop for the subsequent chapters whose themes have roots in the Colebrook-Cameron Commission.

2.1.3 *Rājākariya*

One of the most pertinent recommendations of the commission was that of abolishing the system of *rājākariya*. Meaning ‘King's work’ in Sinhalese, it was a system that facilitated the mobilisation of labour, with the bulk of labour taking place in the production process. These services of labour could range from labour for public roads or buildings to special services related to their caste.³⁴ *Rājākariya* strengthened the hierarchical order as the King represented a divine

³² De Silva, C.R., *Ceylon under the British Occupation, 1795-1833: Its Political, Administrative and Economic Development*, Colombo, The Colombo Apothecaries' Co., Ltd., 1962, p. 594.

³³ Britannica, “*rājākariya*”, <https://www.britannica.com/topic/rajakariya>, last date of consultation 23 September 2024

³⁴ Britannica, “*rājākariya*”, <https://www.britannica.com/topic/rajakariya>, last date of consultation 23 September 2024

entity from which the rest of society was organised in a network of service functions centred on the king.³⁵ Even until the commission, it was still common in the northern districts for debtors to become the slaves of their creditors.³⁶ This ancient system crystallised power in the hands of the rulers whilst also retaining the caste structure that defined traditional Sri Lankan society into the 19th century.

These ancient structures of Sinhalese power were represented through courtly proceedings and the 'Kandy *Perahera*', in which all social representatives parade through the city with the venerated relic of the tooth of the Buddha while the king watched from a special stage.³⁷ This rather ritualistic way to represent society served political and ideological purposes, concealing how society truly functioned. The true workings, as described by Professor Nirmal Dewasiri, can be described as a mode of surplus extraction by the working class. The existence of *rājākariya* split the total supply of labour in the social formation into two separately functioning circulation systems. The first was the labour used primarily for the sustenance of the labourer and their family. The second was the *rājākariya* itself. Here peasants from different castes were called by the divine king to perform various tasks pertaining to their standing in society. As the performer of *rājākariya* was simultaneously the producer in the other system of labour circulation, an equilibrium had to be achieved to ensure smooth proceedings. Pertinently, the role coolies played within this system highlights a characteristic of Sri Lankan society that carried on through the colonial period into the modern day. Their low social origin within the caste system meant that they were most vulnerable to the increase in demand for menial and laborious work. Those of a higher caste, such as cinnamon peelers, were able to negotiate for better economic packages that made their lives more comfortable.³⁸ The integration of the caste system into the economic sphere through *rājākariya*, then, resulted in two problems for the colonial powers. Firstly, the careful equilibrium that was nurtured for centuries was disrupted by the influx of migrants from abroad for labour for maximum profit. This resulted in a growing urban elite that could claim *rājākariya* labour and subsequently morphed traditional society and its labour needs. Secondly, both the Dutch and British needed some form of this system for them to retain power. The primary method of allocating labour was land tenure and, as M. U. de Silva noted, this form of social relation had become 'second nature'.³⁹ As a result, after taking the traditional heartland of Kandy, the British needed to discover how to utilise land allocation for their own benefit while

³⁵ Dewasiri, N., *The Adaptable Peasant: Agrarian Society in Western Sri Lanka under Dutch Rule, 1740-1800*, Leiden, Brill, 2008, p. 93

³⁶ Report on Ceylon (Colebrooke Report) 24. Dec. 1831, Colombo, 24 December 1831, Sri Lanka National Archives (hereafter SLNA) Record #19

³⁷ Dewasiri, *The Adaptable Peasant*, p. 93

³⁸ Dewasiri, *The Adaptable Peasant*, pp. 94- 97

³⁹ De Silva, M.U., "Land Tenure, Caste System and the Rajakariya, Under Foreign Rule: A Review of Change in Sri Lanka Under Western Powers, 1597-1832", *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society of Sri Lanka*, vol. 37, 1992/1993, p. 12

transplanting their profit-focused initiatives onto a society that was, until recently, in service solely to their divine king.

Such a strict control of who gained land was a problem for the British as they wished to integrate Ceylon into the global plantation economy. To do this, aggressive reforms were pursued on the back of these recommendations. According to government reports, the “removal of all restrictions on trade, on the free disposal of labour, and the liberty of cultivating all descriptions of produce” are all cited as being the positive results from putting the power of land grants in the hands of the colonial government. Additionally, these benefits are required for both the “settlement and improvement of the country.”⁴⁰ Considering the colonial government's persistence on developing the plantation industry in Ceylon, the abolition of the *rājākariya* system highlights how the method of land distribution is crucial for attracting labour. More specifically, it shows how the migration of Indian Tamils into Ceylon was intrinsically linked with inter-colonial competition for labour whilst tradition was shown to be merely a hindrance that needed to be moulded.

The migration of Indian Tamils was something that also needed to be sold to the labourers so they would make the initial migratory jump to Ceylon. Here, the association of land and economic gain is clear to see. The taking of the Kandyan Kingdom in 1815 also included swathes of land that had not been cultivated for plantations. Moves to utilise this fertile land began in earnest and resulted in discussions of economic viability in both the felling of trees and attracting labour to do so. One such discussion revolved around the ‘Regulation of Government, No. 2’ in 1822. Here the narrative lies around land cultivation taxes. In Ceylon a tax of one tenth on the value of timber cut compared positively with a tax of up to one half in the southwestern Indian region of Malabar.⁴¹ This highlights inter-empire economic competition, whilst also acting as an early indication of consideration of Indian labourers into Ceylon. Moreover, lack of caste restrictions on such labour shows how the net was cast wide for attracting migrants to the island whilst simultaneously undermining traditional societal structures.

Removing the restrictions imposed by the *rājākariya* system also led to the development of what was considered to be one of the most pressing developmental issues of the time: roads. The aforementioned tracts of Kandyan land also needed effective transport links to export the coffee from the plantation to the maritime city of Colombo and then, the globe. This necessity was pushed in particular by Edward Barnes, Governor of Ceylon from 1824 to 1831.⁴² It proved to be a tactful move as it not only helped the export of coffee but, in the short term, it also penetrated the previously inaccessible Kandyan heartland. Subsequently the first plantation was established in Gampola in 1824 by one George Bird, with Edward Barnes setting one up himself in Peradeniya

⁴⁰ Report on Ceylon (Colebrooke Report) 24. Dec. 1831, Colombo, 24 December 1831, SLNA, Record #19

⁴¹ Report on Ceylon (Colebrooke Report) 24. Dec. 1831, Colombo, 24 December 1831, SLNA, Record #19

⁴² Nadesan, *Up-Country Tamil People*, p. 16

one year later.⁴³ This start was rather slow, however, with the Colebrook-Cameron Commission's recommendations of abolishing the *rājākariya* coming in the early stages of the 1830s, around the time of the abolition of slavery. Following the commission, the integration of road development with the abolition of slavery resulted in a theoretically freer Sinhalese workforce who by and large chose not to work hard labour, pertaining to their general place in the caste system and, by extension, *rājākariya*. The need for indentured labourers was consequently heightened.

The rapid growth of the plantation industry that the recommendations allowed required something that was now placed in the hands of the British: land. The British effectively took the role of the old Sinhalese kings with regards to land, but the aforementioned shifts in power meant that both the people manning the land drastically changed as well as the rate of buying and selling. The former is implicit with the nature of the British colonial system. Namely, the use of the products of the fertile land of Ceylon shifted from the Sinhalese majority to the British colonial government. Consequently, those tilling the land did not need to answer to the Sinhalese, reducing their overarching power on the island.

The act of buying and selling land, however, reveals a much more telling story of how the plantation industry grew and the tensions that arose from it between the British, the plantation owners and the indentured labourers. The adoption of the recommendations from the Colebrook-Cameron Commission led to a re-examination of the property rights regarding private land. What arose from this was an incompatibility issue between the Sinhalese perception on land rights and the western capitalist view. The plantation owners themselves stated that proof of ownership had typically been expressed “by right of inheritance” by peasants, further supported by “*Wattoru*”, or tax receipts. Evidence was afforded on three material points: first, the name of the cultivator or owner of the land; second, the name of the land cultivated; and third, the amount paid with the rate of taxation.⁴⁴ An issue that was raised by the British, in particular some plantation owners, was that there were no true boundaries to these inherited lands, meaning that proof of private ownership could not be established in the Western tradition.⁴⁵ Being called a ‘defect’, this acquisition of land represented an ideological clash between the British and the Sinhalese. The British interest in kick starting the plantation industry meant that the abolishing of *rājākariya* was a key moment in the shift to morphing Ceylon to be compatible with the global colonial economy.

To illustrate the variety of perspectives on the issue of land acquisition, it is crucial to highlight how the plantation owners fit into the colonial economy of Ceylon. *The Planters’ Association of Ceylon*, established in 1854, is a representative body that is designed to protect the interest of

⁴³ Nadesan, *Up-Country Tamil People*, p. 17

⁴⁴ Minutes of the Meetings of Subcommittees of the Planters Association of Ceylon from March 1926 to March 1929, Colombo, 14 January 1928, SLNA 248/2

⁴⁵ Minutes of the Meetings of Subcommittees of the Planters Association of Ceylon from March 1926 to March 1929, Colombo, 14 January 1928, SLNA 248/2

the plantation owners as well as the plantation industry as a whole. According to them, they wish to “speak authoritatively on their [the plantation owners] behalf and to deal with those responsible for the administration of the island.”⁴⁶ A formal body, they represented the first step towards a professionalisation of the industry in Ceylon. In the early days of the coffee plantation, until around 1850, planters were usually untrained in cultivation practices.⁴⁷ Crucially, these lack of skills were also reflected in a short term interest in maximising profit before returning home rather than in the long-term prospects of the plantation industry.⁴⁸ This is reflected in the words of Sir James Emerson Tennent, Colonial Secretary of Ceylon between 1846 and 1850: “the Governor and the Council, the Military and the Judges, the Clergy and one half of the Civil Servants penetrated the hills, and became purchasers of Crown Lands.”⁴⁹ Further, he notes that “few colonial pursuits present attractions superior to those exhibited in Ceylon, either as to actual enjoyment or reasonable returns for investment.”⁵⁰ Plantation owners, then, from a variety of professional backgrounds that lacked farming experience were known to have utilised the newly-conquered Kandyan hills for private monetary gain.

These purely economic motivations paradoxically led to the beginnings of professionalisation within the planting industry. Between 1848 and 1849 the coffee industry “experienced its first depression”, leading to a drastic fall in prices and panic within the community of plantation owners.⁵¹ This downturn in economic fortunes was one of the driving factors to shake the laissez-faire attitude out of this community. Migration was also deeply connected to this. The motivations of the indentured labourers from South India directly mirrored that of the plantation owners. They saw plantation work in Ceylon as a way to escape the cycle of poverty found in their villages, and bring home small fortunes for their families in India.⁵² This reputation meant that initially plantation owners had a healthy influx of indentured labourers, even considering the fact that most did not permanently settle there. This, however, changed when migration levels dipped leaving a labour shortage around the same time as the depression in coffee prices. The specific reasons for this will be explored in the discussion about the integration of the caste system in the colonial economy shortly. What is relevant for now is to consider that the global economy and the migration of labour were intrinsically linked. Labourers were motivated by money in parallel with plantation owners. The key difference between these two groups of actors, however, was power. The plantation owners, primarily of British descent, were able to form *The Planters’ Association of Ceylon* to protect their interests because of their position within

⁴⁶ *The Planters’ Association of Ceylon*, “About the Planters’ Association of Ceylon”, <https://paofceylon.org/History.html>, last date of consultation 21 September 2024

⁴⁷ Kurian, *State, Capital and Labour*, p. 51

⁴⁸ Kurian, *State, Capital and Labour*, p. 51

⁴⁹ Tennent, J., *Ceylon: An Account of the Island Physical, Historical, and Topographical, Volume II*, London, Longman, Green, Longman, and Roberts, 2019, p. 735

⁵⁰ Tennent, *Ceylon: An Account*, p. 739

⁵¹ Driesen, *Long Walk*, p. 21

⁵² Driesen, *Long Walk*, p. 18

the local colonial economy. On the other hand, the labourers had little power apart from the decision to go to Ceylon for plantation work or not. This would not change until the twentieth century, when the long shadow of professionalisation of the industry proved fruitful for the now settled migrants from India.

With a massive influx of migrants entering Ceylon willing to work on the newly emancipated land after the Colebrook-Cameron Commission, land acquisition was vital to support the growing plantation economy. As a result, the British government enacted several Crown Land Ordinances to regulate land transactions. The first in 1840 set the tone for how the British wanted to approach this issue in a post-*rājākariya* Ceylon. A Crown Land was defined as follows: "All Forest, Waste, unoccupied, or uncultivated lands shall be presumed to be the property of the Crown until the contrary thereof be proved".⁵³ This not only subsumed the fertile land for plantations but also delegitimised the previous system of land ownership. *The Planters' Association of Ceylon* themselves stated that the previously mentioned "*Wattoru*" system was 'lax' due to a lack of boundaries being legally insufficient. From 1840 the focus was "to prevent Encroachments upon Crown Lands", which in turn reveals some truths about how the British and Planters' Association viewed not only themselves within Ceylon, but also the land itself.⁵⁴

The Planters' Association, in a memorandum written in 1928 regarding land tenure, placed themselves historically as a continuation of old rulers in Sri Lanka. They likened themselves to the Sovereign of Lanka named Pandukabhaya who, in the twelfth year of his reign during the fifth century BC, fixed the boundaries of the villages in all parts of Lanka. He would grant land considering the following factors: caste, situation of property and servitude to the King.⁵⁵ This self-comparison was a common colonial tactic that utilised existing power structures to place themselves at the top of the hierarchy to control the local populace and economy. In doing so a colonial-caste system arose.⁵⁶ In this case, the recognition of a previous sovereign served as proof as a natural continuation of the Sri Lankan hierarchy. By placing this in the context of land acquisition, it can be ascertained that both the British colonial government and the plantation owners used land as a method of control. After conquering the Sinhalese stronghold of Kandy and its associated land they could replace the old power structures with themselves at the top. To expand upon this, another self-recognised similarity was the method of filling the land with labourers. As was discussed in the previous chapter, donations were accepted to the Sinhalese King on divine grounds. These donations could either be fulfilled in financial terms or, as was

⁵³ Minutes of the Meetings of Subcommittees of the Planters Association of Ceylon from March 1926 to March 1929, Colombo, 14 January 1928, SLNA 248/2

⁵⁴ Minutes of the Meetings of Subcommittees of the Planters Association of Ceylon from March 1926 to March 1929, Colombo, 14 January 1928, SLNA 248/2

⁵⁵ Minutes of the Meetings of Subcommittees of the Planters Association of Ceylon from March 1926 to March 1929, Colombo, 14 January 1928, SLNA 248/2

⁵⁶ Quijano, A., "Coloniality of Power, Eurocentrism, and Latin America", *Nepantla: Views from South*, vol. 1, n. 3, 2000, pp. 533-538

common and respected in society at the time, enslavement. Under the British, this was adapted to benefit the burgeoning plantation industry. The consideration of land for Pandukabhaya and other kings was in servitude, whereas the Crown accepted a consideration in money. Specifically, this system took the form of an auction. Here planters or prospective planters would bid for plots of land that would, due to spikes in demand at times, result in intense financial competition between planters for land that led to self-described 'land-lust antipathy' by *The Planters' Association*.⁵⁷ They even go so far as to state that there is a shared 'plight' between the capitalist and the Peasant with relation to the selling of Crown Lands. Due to the nature of an auction, there is no guarantee of getting the land they wish for.⁵⁸ The British colonial government, then, established themselves as a continuation of the Sinhalese divine monarchs that preceded them. Their infallibility was made more certain by the buffer of the plantation owners between them and the indentured labourers. By inserting this capitalist mode of production into Ceylon, the British not only extracted wealth from the island but also allowed any grievances to be placed on the capitalists they themselves encouraged.

This grievance buffer the British placed between themselves and the labourers was also replicated by the plantation owners themselves. Angela Little discusses the existence of "powers of hierarchy" in which there are always buffers of blame between the planter and the labourers.⁵⁹ This works in tandem with the already existing caste system that serves to reinforce and sustain the colonial power structures that the British colonial system sought. In turn, the Indian indentured labourers in Ceylon found themselves at the bottom of a rigid hierarchy that served not only the British but old Sinhala elites that were kept in positions of power.

One representative case that encapsulates this web of power is that of the Coast Advance System. After it became apparent in the 1830s that working the plantations in Ceylon was not the pot of honey that was foretold, and also being denied Government assistance for recruitment, the planters themselves took matters into their own hands.⁶⁰ A system was needed that ensured both a steady flow of new recruits as well as worker retention on the estates. Kangannies, meaning 'the one who observes' in Tamil, were sent to India to attract and take labourers for plantation work. They spread the idea that wealth could be discovered on the shores of Ceylon, that there was a way out of poverty that was already orchestrated by the British. In the Tamil Nadu region of India, a brutal system of land tenure meant that they were saddled with debt that trapped them in their small holdings. Utilising this, the Ceylonese planters supplied the Kangannies with enough money to pay off the debts of the Indian workers who then

⁵⁷ Minutes of the Meetings of Subcommittees of the Planters Association of Ceylon from March 1926 to March 1929, Colombo, 14 January 1928, SLNA 248/2

⁵⁸ Minutes of the Meetings of Subcommittees of the Planters Association of Ceylon from March 1926 to March 1929, Colombo, 14 January 1928, SLNA 248/2

⁵⁹ Little, A., *Labouring to Learn: Towards a Political Economy of Plantations, People and Education in Sri Lanka*, Colombo, SSA, 1999, pp. 46-48

⁶⁰ Driesen, *Long Walk*, pp. 80-81

became beholden in debt to the kanganies themselves, who were in turn indebted to the plantation owners.⁶¹ This debt-driven chain of command was designed to ensure the smooth running of plantations while keeping those at the top of the hierarchy at arm's length from those at the bottom.

This system was fraught with problems for the labourers. To begin with, the kangany was tasked by the planter to look after the new recruits on their journey south. This included providing rice and other foodstuffs for them, as well as adequate transport.⁶² The expenses incurred on the journey for the kangany was usually around eight shillings per head. This was then incorporated into the estates' "Debt Account" that was charged against the kangany and his recruits as they began their life in Ceylon. On return the recruiters were then paid between one and two shillings per head as well as a token one pound per month in recognition of their kanganyship.⁶³

However, this predatory chain of debt that perpetuated the plantation system meant that the Kanganies began hoarding as much of the planters' cash advance that was given to them, at the expense of the labourers themselves. By trusting the kangany with a lump sum, soon the recruiters began minimising the costs associated with looking after the new recruits. Food became scarce for the recruits on the journey to Ceylon, whilst a renewed focus on collecting more recruits at once to bring back meant the journey back was also cramped. Disastrous results followed. Disease and hunger plagued the new labourers, leading to scores of corpses littering the path from Tamil Nadu to Ceylon. Moreover, those that do arrive to their plantations arrive both fatigued and emaciated, meaning they were unable to work immediately. For the kangany himself, gathering as many recruits as he possibly could had little downside. Since only a part of the employer's advance was spent on the immigrant, the recruiter could make up for any deaths on the march home. Moreover, there was no law enforcing arrangements in India in Ceylon, meaning that in the case of death on the road the kangany could not be punished.⁶⁴

Considering the chain of command that has been explored here, what can we extrapolate about the indentured labourer experience in Ceylon in this early coffee plantation period? Firstly, it is important to note that these extra layers of hierarchical bureaucracy that permeated the plantation system were different to other British colonies at the time. As Nadesan points out, it was common for indentured labourers to receive certain benefits from their employer such as "fixed wages, free housing, medical attendance and other amenities".⁶⁵ The existence of the kangany system freed the employer from any such obligations. Indeed, the chain of debt that supported the hierarchy of command allowed for more predatory practices, meaning even the journey from South India to Ceylon was riddled with risk.

⁶¹ Nadesan, *Up-Country Tamil People*, pp. 22-23

⁶² Nadesan, *Up-Country Tamil People*, p. 23

⁶³ Driesen, *Long Walk*, p. 81

⁶⁴ Driesen, *Long Walk*, p. 82

⁶⁵ Nadesan, *Up-Country Tamil People*, p. 24

At an increasingly systemic level, the previously mentioned laissez-faire attitude of the planters themselves bled into the kangany system and dominated the entire logistical framework. With little in the way of protections, the entire system was at the mercy of global economic fluctuations. At times this benefitted the planters as the suffocating land tenure system in India meant that labour was more willing to migrate south to supplement the plantation business. Further, using kanganies in the recruitment system meant that planters could easily adjust labour levels depending on seasonal demand.⁶⁶ On the other hand, fluctuating coffee prices led to thousands of acres of land being neglected when there was a downturn, leaving only the best estates in business. This depression was further substantiated by a drop in migration figures in the years preceding it largely due to the “deplorable social and economic disabilities which labour had to endure while employed in Sri Lanka, and when travelling between India and the plantation.”⁶⁷ Indeed Governor Lord Torrington expressed such an opinion at this time, noting that the fall in immigration was the result “not of a fear of the Kandyans, but of causes arising from bad treatment at the hands of plantation owners.”⁶⁸ On a grand scale it is clear then that land and immigration figures are intrinsically linked during this early period of plantations in Ceylon. Moreover, the laissez-faire attitude that encapsulated this era bled through the hierarchy that the British had morphed to their benefit since the takeover of Sinhalese Kandy in 1815. This resulted in a debt chain that put much hardship on the Indian indentured labourers, ruled by a hierarchy of caste-related buffers designed to minimise their agency as much as possible.

2.1.4 Caste-Issues

Such a web of oppression orchestrated by the British was made possible due to the utilisation of the existing caste system to not only strengthen societal relations horizontally but to keep lower castes relatively subservient. Or, as Paul Caspersz succinctly states, “caste, class and social status oppressed the immigrants in their South Indian society. They contributed to the acceptance of oppression on the journey and to the maintenance of the state of oppression once they reached journey's end in the plantations of Sri Lanka.”⁶⁹ Caste identity at its core implies a specific way of thinking, namely hierarchical rather than egalitarian norms. These norms involve an ability of self-reflection depending on the context, situations, and social domains one finds oneself in. Caste does not disappear in these different circumstances, yet caste identities can be imbued with new dimensions that include, for example, the mobilising for both economic and political

⁶⁶ Kurian, *State, Capital and Labour*, pp. 91-92

⁶⁷ Driesen, *The Long Walk*, p. 21

⁶⁸ Driesen, *The Long Walk*, p. 21

⁶⁹ Caspersz, P., *A New Culture for a New Society: Selected Writings 1945-2005*, Kandy, Satyodaya Consumer Seva, 2005, p. 6

gain.⁷⁰ What follows is an interrogation into how the use of the caste system functioned in both an economic and a political sense. It will be shown that the caste-based hierarchies above the Indian labourers seeped through not only the private plantations but the various arms of the colonial government.

Both economic and political gain can be seen in the use of the caste hierarchy to keep colonial control. Directly above the Indian labourers in this hierarchy were the kanganyes. The inherent caste-based superiority possessed by the kangany when recruiting proved fruitful as it was said to have made the recruits more likely to be compliant to the kanganyes' requests.⁷¹ Through having a power dynamic such as this at the 'bottom' of the hierarchy, a buffer of caste-based honour also protected those further up the hierarchy, along with the aforementioned debt system. Having a subservient class of people on the plantations who answered to someone from a similar background, albeit of a higher caste, also ensured that rebellious activities were somewhat nullified.

The Colebrook-Cameron Commission, whose recommendations proved crucial for land acquisition, also played a role in caste-based power dynamics. A recommendation that is pertinent to this section was to admit Ceylonese people to the ranks of the civil service. This was a recommendation that was born out of both financial and political expediency.⁷² For the former reason, hiring Ceylonese people was cheaper than hiring those of British descent to these roles. Concerning political expediency, the matter is a little more complex. Certainly, it has its roots in the takeover of Kandy in 1815. The Kandyan elites here were resistant to British colonial rule in the years following the takeover. This culminated in events such as the Uva-Wellassa Rebellion in 1818 that consisted of Kandyan elites unhappy with British colonial rule. These annoyances were founded upon not only a sense of injustice but also an active disrespect of traditional customs displayed by the British. For example, the suggestion to remove the venerated Tooth of the Buddha from Kandy was highly unpopular at the time and represented a lack of understanding and agreement between the Kandyan officials and the British.⁷³ This sense of injustice led to not only the aforementioned rebellion, which the British quelled, but also an extra impetus to quell potential rebellions spearheaded by old Sinhalese elites.

Considering these historical aggravations between the old Kandyan elites and the British colonial government, the Colebrook-Cameron Commission's recommendation of allowing Ceylonese people into the colonial civil service was politically expedient for multiple reasons. Mendis encapsulates these reasons succinctly, stating that 'the highest classes among them should be

⁷⁰ Hollup, O., *Bonded Labour: Caste and Cultural Identity Among Tamil Plantation Workers in Sri Lanka*, New Delhi, Sterling Publishers, 1994, p. xxv

⁷¹ Little, *Labouring to Learn*, pp. 46-48

⁷² Little, *Labouring to Learn*, p. 78

⁷³ Vimalanda, *The Great Rebellion*, pp. 183-184

rendered morally and intellectually competent to fill offices of trust'.⁷⁴ It is important to note here that the higher classes mentioned were not necessarily the hereditary Kandyan elites, but those of a general higher caste that were used as an instrument of control over these elites.⁷⁵ Moreover, the Colebrook-Cameron Commission also recommended solidifying this through education, allowing for, theoretically, an increasingly subservient class that could use English to a professional standard all the while creating a bureaucratic buffer between the British and those manufactured to be lower in the hierarchy of power. Specifically, the low-country Sinhalese population gained the most, along with the Burghers who represented a continuation of colonial power on the island from the Portuguese. Those sidelined included the Kandyan Sinhalese and the Indian Tamils working on the plantations.⁷⁶ This shift, then, is representative of an early attempt by the British to use the existing caste societal structure for their own gain. Additionally, it also constitutes the beginning of a longer-term trend of professionalisation and away from the laissez-faire method of governing that dominated the nineteenth century history of Ceylon.

2.2 Long Shadows

Through the exploration of certain key themes present in the coffee plantation period of Ceylon, the seeds of indentured subordination can be found to have been planted. The migration of labourers from the Tamil Nadu region of South India was running parallel to the consolidation of power undertaken by the British. This consolidation is inherently paracolonial in nature, as traditional hierarchical behaviours intrinsic in the caste system morphed through colonialism but not because of it. Analysing this period through a temporally free lens such as this will highlight how the historically inspired changes in this time come to define the modern-day experience for Indian-origin labourers in Sri Lanka. The repercussions of the policies enacted after the Colebrook-Cameron Commission, namely the shift in land and caste policy, will be highlighted to demonstrate this.

Akin to nineteenth century Ceylon being morphed extensively by the British led Colebrook-Cameron Commission, events affecting indentured labourers in the twentieth century can be extrapolated from the adoption of the Donoughmore Commission's recommendations in the new constitution of 1931. In this latter era of British Ceylon, there had been a marked shift away from laissez-faire to an increasingly professional and bureaucratic environment. Deriving from the Colebrook-Cameron Commission roughly one hundred years prior, a Ceylonese middle class had developed that were both richer and more influential in the day to day running of the colony. These included not only the Sinhalese that had been favoured by the British in the nineteenth

⁷⁴ Mendis, G.C., *The Colebrook-Cameron Papers: Documents on British Colonial Policy in Ceylon, 1796-1833, Volume I*, University of California, Oxford University Press, 1956, p. 374

⁷⁵ Little, *Labouring to Learn*, p. 79

⁷⁶ Little, *Labouring to Learn*, p. 87

century but also Ceylon Tamils who had been in Sri Lanka for centuries before the arrival of European influence on the island.⁷⁷ Against this backdrop, the primary ramifications of the Donoughmore Commission will form the subsequent analysis: enfranchisement and citizenship. With the recommendations put forward by this commission in the latter part of the 1920s, the right to vote was extended to all adults with a five-year residential qualification.⁷⁸ This step will be shown to reinforce the strict caste-based hierarchy the British had developed over time and sideline those considered to be of lower caste, in particular the Indian estate workers.

The enfranchisement of the population cut along existing ethnic and religious divides, allowing for a glimpse at the complex intersectional issues that pervaded society at the time. A working-class movement rooted in the capital of Colombo led to pressures to instigate the right to vote for all. This would include the multiple groups of people, including the Sinhala and Tamil peoples. Moreover, any income, property or education qualifications would be abolished.⁷⁹ However, following the recommendations of the commission, a new buzzword began to enter common parlance: 'the Indian menace'. This 'menace' stemmed from fears of extending the right to vote to the plantation workers who had Indian heritage. This fear could be put to a variety of reasons that ultimately come down to societal power structures. Nadesan posits two intersecting ideas. Firstly, the nationalist Sinhalese people who had been taken under the wing of the British for a century were worried that their position in society would be at threat. Elsewhere, the European planters and aristocratic class feared that by giving their workers the vote that their position would be weakened.⁸⁰ The demonization of those subjugated in society is something that is familiar in many historical contexts. What is pertinent to note here, however, is through the policies enacted by the British over the course of a century, pre-existing Sinhalese power dynamics resurfaced. This time, however, the subject of their grievances were the Indian-origin estate workers, many of whom had resided in Ceylon their entire lives. The resulting fallout of the potential franchise of these labourers was that the criteria of having residence for five years were changed to having domicile interests.⁸¹ Pressured by those who had benefited from the shifting caste relations since the British took over, this change was a direct result of a long-standing consolidation of power that stripped rights away from the Indian-origin indentured labourers.

The reason they were subject to such ire regarding enfranchisement was also partly due to their relatively recent migration to the island. Due to this Indian estate worker Tamils were considered

⁷⁷ Minutes of the Meetings of Subcommittees of the Planters Association of Ceylon from March 1926 to March 1929, Colombo, 27 March 1928, SLNA 248/2

⁷⁸ Britannica, "Donoughmore Commission", <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Donoughmore-Commission>, last date of consultation 25 September 2024

⁷⁹ Nadesan, *Up-Country Tamil People*, p. 70

⁸⁰ Nadesan, *Up-Country Tamil People*, pp. 71-72

⁸¹ Samaraweera, V., "Indian Tamil Immigrant Labour in Ceylon and the Land Problem: The Case of the Land Development Ordinance of 1935", *Proceedings of the Fourth International Conference Seminar of Tamil Studies*, vol. 2, 1974, p. 105

different from Ceylon Tamils. Indeed, they were considered to be simply 'birds of passage'. According to the higher-ups in the caste-hierarchy, they were here not because of a love for Ceylon but because of circumstance only.⁸² This prejudice against this group most derives from their past migratory patterns. As established earlier in the chapter, in the initial period of coffee plantations it was common for workers to move to the island for a short period of time before moving back. However, the Donoughmore Commission estimated that at the time of writing between 40 and 50 per cent of the Indian plantation workers were permanently settled.⁸³ The reasons for this shift and its ramifications will be explored in detail in the subsequent chapters. However, for now it is pertinent to note that from the latter half of the nineteenth century labourers were increasingly encouraged to arrive with their families. The core reason for this was to encourage permanent settlement to ensure a more stable plantation workforce following the fall of coffee and rise of tea, rubber, and coconut cultivation.⁸⁴ However, this migratory shift did not change the perceptions of these workers and led to them being considered as an impermanent class of people that therefore did not deserve civil rights.

This alienation went further, as debates over the granting of land came from a Land Commission that sprouted from the recommendations of the Donoughmore Commission. A shift in policy here meant that land would now be granted for settlement to a wider array of classes, with the only stipulation being it had to be given specifically to the Ceylonese middle-classes. An Interim Report specified 'Ceylonese' to mean "Sinhalese, Ceylon Tamils, Burghers, Ceylon Moormen, Ceylon Malays, and Europeans domiciled in Ceylon, i.e. who have adopted Ceylon as their permanent home".⁸⁵ This careful definition notably excludes one substantial portion of society: the Indian Tamils. The nationalist sentiment exhibited by the Sinhalese with regards to enfranchisement was again on display here. They held strong bureaucratic power and wielded it against a class of people that had few rights in society. Moreover, many of these Indian Tamil families knew nothing of their 'homeland', aside from stories told by their ancestors.⁸⁶ As a result, the broad anti-Indian Tamil sentiment that pervaded Ceylonese society at the time culminated in not only a lack of voting rights but also land rights. This led to this sizable portion of society being sidelined within Ceylon with few legal rights available to them to change their situation.

The anti-Indian Tamil sentiment in the late British Ceylon period carried over into the period of independence for Sri Lanka. Indeed, independence for Sri Lanka did little to alter the relationship of domination and dependence established by the British. With respect to plantations, they continued to flourish due to their adherence to multinational corporations and metropolitan

⁸² Samaraweera, *Indian Tamil Immigrant Labour*, p. 101

⁸³ Samaraweera, *Indian Tamil Immigrant Labour*, p. 97

⁸⁴ Kurian, *State, Capital and Labour*, pp. 97-99

⁸⁵ Samaraweera, *Indian Tamil Immigrant Labour*, p. 103

⁸⁶ Samaraweera, *Indian Tamil Immigrant Labour*, p. 103

plantation companies.⁸⁷ The increased entanglement of the Sri Lankan economy into, first, the periphery metropolitan economic system followed by the global economic system suited the pauperised and proletarianized population mobilised to benefit wealthy foreign investors.⁸⁸

What of the Sri Lankan population? The carefully moulded caste-based hierarchies developed by the British left a Sinhala elite that firmly established themselves as the natural rulers over the island. This of course has certain historical precedents. Even before European influence the Sinhalese Buddhist population took the reins of power for centuries. As chapter one argues, the arrival of the Portuguese sparked a shift from accepting a pluralistic society into one that began to shun other religions to protect Buddhism. Ideologically encapsulated in Kandy, this fell and through colonialism the Sinhalese Buddhist consciousness survived through the, one might say, British-led caste system. Those kept in key administrative offices were quick to consolidate their role in society, highlighting how the entrenched nationalistic Sinhalese Buddhism that existed before colonialism and was subsequently morphed by it led to attitudes of domination that marginalised those most vulnerable in society.

This marginalisation manifested itself in an attempt to establish the Sinhalese culture as the dominant force in Sri Lanka. This motivation is best reflected in the Sinhala Only Act, passed in the Parliament of Ceylon in 1956.⁸⁹ This act aimed to supplant English as the official language of the island with Sinhalese. The Tamil language was specifically excluded from this act. This had several ramifications. As an aggressively pro-Sinhala act, this represented a step to establish the Sinhalese Buddhist state that had been transformed by the imposition of colonial political structures. The fact that this act was being passed through a parliament shows how the centuries old Sinhala Buddhist consciousness did not develop because of colonialism but was simply shaped by it.

This paracolony of historical experience on the island is also reflected in the Ceylon Tamil experience. Ceylon Tamils historically see themselves as just a part of Sri Lankan history as the Sinhalese population. The *Vaddukodai Resolution* of 1976, the first declaration of the separatist Tamil United Liberation Front, stated that they consistently gave no consent for subjugation from both colonial powers and the Sinhalese.⁹⁰ On the chargesheet against Sinhala nationalism included the aforementioned Sinhala Only Act, the state-aided mass colonisation of the traditionally Tamil north-eastern areas of Sri Lanka by Sinhalese people, and the disenfranchisement of Indian-origin Tamils. Further, this resolution reflects on the nationalistic

⁸⁷ Dawood, N., *Tea and Poverty: Plantations and the Political Economy of Sri Lanka*, Hong Kong, Urban Rural Mission, 1980, p. 4

⁸⁸ Dawood, *Tea and Poverty*, p. 3

⁸⁹ Sri Lanka Consolidated Acts, "Official Language Act (No. 33 of 1956)", http://www.commonlii.org/lk/legis/num_act/ola33o1956180/, last date of consultation 2 October 2024

⁹⁰ Ismail, Q., "Constituting Nation, Contesting Nationalism: The Southern Tamil (Woman) and Separatist Tamil Nationalism in Sri Lanka", in Chatterjee, P. and Jeganathan, P. (eds.), *Subaltern Studies XI: Community, Gender and Violence*, London, Hurst & Company, 2001, pp. 232-234

motivations of the Tamils as they argue for the establishment of a separate state named 'Eelam'.⁹¹ Reading specifically into the Sinhala-Tamil tensions on the island is outside of the remit of this thesis, but it is important to note that the paracolonial experience of the Sinhalese people is also shared by the Tamil people. The goals of each group have been moulded by the British as they now take place within a nation state that has institutions that reflect that of the British-style parliamentary democracy.

Within this tapestry of conflicting conflicts that intersect along many lines, most notably religious and ethnic, lie the Indian-origin Tamils who now represent a more permanent group of people in Sri Lanka. This chapter has looked at how and why they migrated, as well as how they were placed within the shifting power structures on the island. Naturally this paracolonial analysis was viewed through the lens of those in power. How the British and post-independence, the Sinhalese people utilised their existence on the island for profit as well as to sustain their own lofty positions within society.

In the subsequent chapters the analysis tackles the indentured labourer experience from the bottom-up. It will be shown how the indentured labourers' experiences fit into the overarching systems they found themselves in and how they expressed their agency even when, in a legal sense, they had very few rights.

⁹¹ Ismail, "Constituting Nation", p. 234

Chapter Three: Rebellions, Resistance, and the Struggle for Agency in Colonial Ceylon

“The British Governor it was said, trembled, grew perplexed, and bemoaned his plight when the intelligence of a possible plot to overthrow the eighteen-month-old British regime in the Kandyan Provinces was conveyed to him...”¹

The nineteenth century was a hotbed for both subversive and violent resistance activities around the world. These took a multitude of forms and served different purposes depending on the context it found itself in. Context was not a restricting factor, however. The most influential revolts caused concern internationally, especially at a time when the world was increasingly interconnected through global trade routes. An early and pivotal example is that of the slave revolt in San Domingo. Led by Toussaint Louverture in 1801, the independent state of Haiti was eventually proclaimed in 1804. Kumari Jayawardena notes that the importance of this revolt was two-fold. Firstly, it occurred early thus providing a benchmark for other revolts around the world against oppressive regimes. Secondly, it highlighted the plight of the plantation workers whilst concurrently causing concern and anxiety amongst colonial rulers.²

This rather grand revolt, in the sense that it led to the establishment of a new state, certainly was not the norm for rebellions at this time. Indeed, Michael Craton posits that “defining slave resistance merely to include plots and acts of overt rebellion is unduly limiting and misleading”.³ As Kurian and Jayawardena state, “in spite of serious hindrances for collective action and protests, workers on post-slavery plantations in Asia did not accept their exploitative conditions of work easily.”⁴ These ‘serious hindrances’ led to increasingly creative rebellious activities that included but were not limited to: uprisings, killings, suicides, deserting plantations, feigning illness, and destroying equipment.⁵ For instance, plantation workers in French Indochina participated in sabotage of company property, self-mutilation and suicide, mass desertion, petty theft, as well as assaults and killings of planters.⁶ Elsewhere, individual forms of resistance proliferated under the indentured system of Indian and Chinese labour in Malaysia. These became “collective and confrontational under the Indian Kangany and Chinese contract systems”

¹ Vimalananda, T., *The Great Rebellion of 1818: The Story of the First War of Independence and Betrayal of the Nation*, Colombo, M.D. Gunasena & Co. Ltd., 1970, p. xxvii

² Jayawardena, K., *Erasure of the Euro-Asian: Recovering Early Radicalism and Feminism in South Asia*, Colombo, Social Scientists’ Association, 2007, pp. 89-90

³ Craton, M., “Forms of Resistance to Slavery”, in Knight, F. W. (ed.), *General History of the Caribbean: The Slave Societies of the Caribbean*, London, Macmillan, 1997, p. 222

⁴ Jayawardena, K. and Kurian, R., *Class, Patriarchy and Ethnicity on Sri Lankan Plantations: Two Centuries of Power and Protest*, New Delhi, Orient Blackswan, 2015, p. 15

⁵ Jayawardena and Kurian, *Class, Patriarchy and Ethnicity*, pp. 15-16

⁶ Murray, M., “‘White Gold’ or ‘White Blood’? The Rubber Plantations of Colonial Indochina, 1910-40”, *The Journal of Peasant Studies*, vol. 19, n. 3-4, 1992, pp. 57-58

which in turn led to large-scale desertions.⁷ These revolts underscore how these rebellions were certainly not unique to one area but intrinsic to many different colonial contexts. Whilst outside of the purview of this thesis, it is interesting to note how there exists to this day a collective historical experience of rebellion and agency that fed through different colonial networks.

What is more, whilst Craton focuses specifically on the resistance of enslaved peoples when asserting his opinion, this can be extrapolated further to the indentured labourers that are studied in this thesis. As has been mentioned in previous chapters, the experiences of the indentured labourer working on the plantations were not too far removed from the experiences of enslaved people. Scholars such as David Northrup provide useful nuance to this matter. He states that indentured labour in general differed in a notable way to slavery. The free choice to become an indentured labourer, a fixed-term contract with the employer and a right to shelter were common differences. However, as David Northrup also mentions, the reality frequently strayed from what was promised on paper. In reality, harsh living conditions imposed by planters and colonial administrators led to life for an indentured labourer to resemble slavery.⁸ And so, it was true in Ceylon. Once there, the labourers found themselves under a suffocating hierarchy of power that utilised the existing caste system to ensure more rigidity. They had a wage yet little agency in where they worked and how they lived. What follows in this chapter and beyond is an interrogation into how they slowly obtained their agency despite the aforementioned subjugation. It is pertinent, then, to begin by analysing the nature of resistance in Ceylon and how agency developed through the colonial period and beyond.

This chapter will focus broadly on two forms of resistance: day-to-day and institutional. The former will interrogate how the everyday acts of resistance had an impact on class relations. James Scott's analysis of labour resistance, which he labels as 'weapons of the weak', is particularly useful. Here he states that "class resistance includes *any* act(s) by member(s) of a subordinate class that is or are *intended* either to mitigate or deny claims (for example, rents, taxes, prestige) made on that class by superordinate classes (for example landlords, large farmers, the state) or to advance its own claims (for example, work, land, charity, respect) vis-à-vis those superordinate classes."⁹ Whilst broad, it is a fitting lens as it allows for both collective and individual analyses. Pertinently, this lends itself well to the individual agency that each labourer had whilst on the plantations in Ceylon. Furthermore, the intention behind the rebellion is highlighted as opposed to the result. This is crucial as the intention of a rebellion does not always match the result.¹⁰

⁷ Ramaswamy, P., "Labour Control and Labour Resistance in the Plantations of Colonial Malaya", *The Journal of Peasant Studies*, vol. 19, n. 3-4, 1992, pp. 87-105

⁸ Northrup, D., *Indentured Labor in the Age of Imperialism, 1834-1922*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 1995, pp. 4-10

⁹ Scott, J., *Weapons of the Weak: Everyday Forms of Peasant Resistance*, London, Yale University Press, 1985, p. 290

¹⁰ Edwards, G, dir., *Rogue One: A Star Wars Story*, Lucasfilm, 2016. Whilst a fictional universe, this film has allegories that have roots within the Viet Cong resistance to the USA during the Vietnam War. The intention of both the Viet

With respect to institutional resistance, this developed slowly over time and mirrors the shift from laissez-faire to professionalisation that was looked at in chapter two. In the coffee plantation era labourers were largely bound to their geographical location on the plantations. The lack of free association between plantation estates severely limited any chance of organised revolt for the labourers. This ‘compartmentalisation’, as Rachel Kurian states, meant that resistance had to be targeted at the plantation owners itself due to their role as their direct superior in the hierarchy of power.¹¹ However, external forces outside of the plantation sector allowed for a broader political platform. The growing nationalist movement in India, the implementation of universal franchise in Ceylon as well as the burgeoning trade union movement in the 1930s allowed for greater institutional agency on the side of the labourers themselves. The politics of plantation labour was forced into focus, allowing for outside forces to have influence as well as vice-versa.¹² This professionalisation of resistance allowed the agency, therefore, to shift from the individual to the collective.

It is important to note that the struggle to resist was felt most acutely by labourers themselves. The ‘compartmentalisation’ that restricted free association was not felt by the planters even in the early days. They could meet and exchange ideas with one another, fostering a community that birthed planters’ clubs and associations.¹³ The most influential of these would be *The Planters’ Association of Ceylon*, whose origins and influence were discussed in chapter two. Through this association the planters could discuss and formulate plans for collective action to promote their economic and political interests, such as political demands on the state.

3.0.1 Shifting Nature of Rebellions: From the Dutch to the British

The total control exerted on Ceylon by the British allowed for an increasingly stifling environment that hindered rebellious actions for multiple decades. In the preceding colonial era under the Dutch, it is clear how the nature of rebellious movements by the subjugated classes was reflective of the colonial hierarchies being influenced by strictly political decisions, most notably the abolition of slavery under the British.

The Dutch era was characterised by the establishment of strict racial and social hierarchies, where the categorization of castes and forced labour was institutionalised. Regarding the former, the Dutch East India Company (hereafter VOC, acronym of *Vereenigde Oost-Indische Compagnie*)

Cong and the Rebel Alliance was to overthrow their respective imperial powers. However, in reality the methods and tactics employed to achieve those goals ended up mirroring those involved in morally questionable scenarios to achieve their end goal. With respect to *Rogue One*, this involved scores of dead innocent people to achieve their end-goal

¹¹ Kurian, R., *State, Capital and Labour in the Plantation Industry in Sri Lanka 1834-1984*, PhD Dissertation, University of Amsterdam, 1989, p. 248

¹² Kurian, *State, Capital and Labour*, p. 248

¹³ Kurian, *State, Capital and Labour*, p. 248

maintained strict control over the indigenous labour force, particularly by enforcing bondage and land-based obligations on Tamil and Sinhalese communities. The Dutch utilised the system of *rājākariya*, which obligated locals to provide labour, often resulting in violent resistance, particularly when policies infringed on established social structures and autonomy.¹⁴ The institutionalisation of forced labour was evident in the economic structure, with Jaffna becoming a "slave-based export economy" focused on cultivating *tottam* (garden lands), where enslaved labour was primarily used for cash crops like tobacco and vegetables.¹⁵

Slave resistance, then, was shaped by strict control mechanisms that took on a bureaucratic hue. Dutch authorities categorised enslaved people by origin, notably from the East Indies, rather than by simply African identity. Over time, the idea of rebellion became intertwined with racial categorizations, where "black" and "slave" became synonymous in the collective memory of the people.¹⁶ This period emphasised a more rigid racial hierarchy, and the Dutch institutionalised slavery through registries and other bureaucratic means.

Whilst it is unfair to synthesise the multitude of ways that resistance manifested itself under the Dutch into one event, one such movement encapsulates how this regimented racial hierarchy revealed itself in complex ways temporally. The "Kaffir insurrection" refers to an event under Dutch rule in which a group of enslaved African individuals in Colombo allegedly revolted, resulting in the violent death of a Dutch official, the fiscal Barent van der Swaan, and his wife in 1723. This insurrection was significant for its impact on the colonial authorities' view of enslaved Africans, especially those classified as "Kaffirs," a term that came to encompass people of African descent.¹⁷

According to R. L. Brohier, this "insurrection" took place as the enslaved African population in Colombo grew large enough to gain a sense of solidarity and strength, which emboldened them to act. The rebellion reportedly began with an act of "murder in the citadel," where a "Kaffir servant" attacked the fiscal and his wife with a dagger, ultimately killing them. Brohier's account of the insurrection describes how the authorities then decided to "regiment all slave labour" in response to the revolt, effectively concentrating and controlling the movements of enslaved individuals in an area that came to be known as "Slave Island".¹⁸

However, historical documentation on this insurrection is said to be scarce, and some scholars question the accuracy and scale of Brohier's account. Indeed, Nira Wickramasinghe states that there is little evidence in VOC records of a large-scale slave revolt. The account seems to blend a combination of myth and popular memory, which has shaped the perception of the event. Additionally, other records show that the majority of enslaved individuals involved in such violent

¹⁴ Wickramasinghe, N., *Slave in a Palanquin: Colonial Servitude and Resistance in Sri Lanka*, New York, Columbia University Press, 2020, p. 138

¹⁵ Wickramasinghe, *Slave in a Palanquin*, pp. 95-98

¹⁶ Wickramasinghe, *Slave in a Palanquin*, p. 190

¹⁷ Wickramasinghe, *Slave in a Palanquin*, pp. 18-20

¹⁸ Wickramasinghe, *Slave in a Palanquin*, pp. 20-22

acts were from the East Indies, such as Balinese or Timorese slaves, rather than Africans.¹⁹ Summarily this indicates that Brohier's account, written several generations after the fact, represents a blackening of the term 'slave' that not only was not present under the Dutch but also reflects on a shift in attitude towards enslaved peoples over time. Moreover, this narrative's evolution reflects the complex interplay of race and rebellion under Dutch rule that shifted with the abolition of slavery under the British.

3.0.2 Development of Rebellious Discontent

The development of rebellious discontent within Ceylon is a phenomenon that mirrors the development of political agency. This should come as little surprise due to rebellious actions themselves being inherently forms of political expediency. Indeed, common repercussions of such actions include transforming local structures of governance, engaging civilians in the process of political change, as well as varying degrees of violence.²⁰ With respect to the research in question, and the associated paracolonial lens, the development of the political domain through monarchical colonialism into the present day is particularly pertinent. Nirmal Dewasiri posits that the evolution of the political domain within Sri Lanka is rooted in the weakening monarchical realm giving way to an idea of nationhood, class and, subsequently, the 'people' themselves.²¹ Here he highlights two key rebellions that happened in the specific frame of time that is being analysed in this thesis: the Great Rebellion of 1817-1818 and the Rebellion of 1848. Broadly speaking, these two rebellions reflect the shifting make-up of society that was imposed by the British. The former rebellion represented the last remnant of old Kandyan power rebelling against the colonial power. Fast forward thirty years and the rebellion is considered to be primarily a peasant-led revolt, one that in turn illuminates changes in political agency amongst differing classes ranging from the Sinhalese to the newly migrated indentured labourers on the plantations. Elsewhere in the British hierarchy of power, the planters' needs were entwined between the British and the labourers, leading them to use their own political agency to develop a long-standing pushback against the British colonial government as a result of the Rebellion of 1848. What follows is an analysis of these two key rebellions in Ceylon history, the political background they were impressed upon, and how they contributed to the distribution of power within Ceylon and, later, in independent Sri Lanka.

3.1 Institutional Rebellions

¹⁹ Wickramasinghe, *Slave in a Palanquin*, pp. 18-22

²⁰ Weinstein, J., *Inside Rebellion: The Politics of Insurgent Violence*, New York, Cambridge University Press, 2007, pp. 5-6

²¹ This idea was my interpretation of Professor Nirmal Dewasiri's presentation at the International Centre for Ethnic Studies in Colombo in July 2024. The monarchical level of power exhibited by the colonial regime worked in tandem with the professionalisation, or 'Europeanisation', of institutions developed with ferocity under the British.

3.1.1 The Great Rebellion of 1817-1818

The Great Rebellion, also known as The Uva-Wellassa Rebellion of 1818, represented a pivotal moment in the history of Ceylon as one of the earliest organized uprisings against British colonial rule. Emerging primarily in the Uva and Wellassa regions, the rebellion was driven by widespread discontent among local elites and peasants centred on oppressive British policies.

The rebellion had its genesis in the Kandyan Convention of 1815, which marked the British annexation of the Kingdom of Kandy. Although the convention ostensibly preserved the sovereignty of Kandyan laws and Buddhist practices, British policies were quick to undermine these promises.²² The erosion of local governance through the removal of traditional elites, the imposition of heavy taxes, and forced labour policies created widespread discontent.²³ Furthermore, the British confiscated land for plantation agriculture, disrupting local agrarian systems and exacerbating the grievances of the Kandyan peasantry.²⁴ These policies served not only as the root of the grievances harboured by the local population, but were additionally indicative of the colonial policies the British would pursue in Ceylon in the long term. Removing the existing elites allowed for a consolidation of the British-led hierarchy of power whilst confiscating arable land allowed for the development of the plantation industries.

This crucial pivot in history proved to be jarring for the Kandyan elites. The rebellion was eventually sparked in 1817 by a pretender to the Kandyan throne, Wilbawe, who claimed royal lineage and rallied support among the disaffected population. His claims resonated with local leaders, including Monarawila Keppetipola, who initially served as a British-appointed governor but later defected to lead the rebellion.²⁵ The movement combined grievances against economic exploitation and cultural suppression, making it a significant anti-colonial rebellion.

The rebellion itself was characterized by guerrilla tactics, utilising the terrain of the Uva and Wellassa regions to resist the superior military power of the British. Keppetipola's leadership was key in organizing local forces, but the British response was uncompromisingly brutal and systematic. The colonial government launched a scorched-earth campaign, destroying villages, burning crops, and targeting civilians to starve the rebels into submission.²⁶ The rebel leaders, including Keppetipola, were captured and executed in 1818 as Ceylon bore the brunt of a significant humanitarian cost as a result of this rebellion. Entire regions were depopulated,

²² Dewaraja, L.S., *The Kandyan Kingdom of Ceylon, 1707-1760*, Colombo, Lake House Investments, 1972, p. 34

²³ Roberts, M., *Caste Conflict and Elite Formation: The Rise of a Karāva Elite in Sri Lanka, 1500-1931*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 1982, pp. 25-29

²⁴ Pieris, P.E., *Tri Sinhala: The Last Phase, 1796-1815*, Ceylon, Colombo Apothecaries Co. Ltd, 1939, pp. 120-127

²⁵ Dewaraja, *The Kandyan Kingdom*, p. 57

²⁶ Obeyesekere, G., *Land Tenure in Village Ceylon: A Sociological and Historical Study*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 1967, pp. 76-79

devastating the agrarian economy of Uva and Wellassa and in turn leaving a lasting mark on the local population.²⁷

The Uva-Wellassa Rebellion, then, marked a turning point in British colonial rule in Ceylon. The violent suppression of the uprising solidified British dominance but also demonstrated the deep fractures between the colonizers and the Indigenous population. The punitive measures taken by the British, including land confiscations and collective punishments, deepened resentment toward colonial rule and contributed to the rise of later nationalist movements that tended to have roots in the Kandyan Sinhalese culture that was violently and systematically suppressed from this point onwards.²⁸ For example, one of the key aspects of the Sinhalese nationalist movement, religion, found extra impetus from this period. Initially promising to protect existing places of worship with the annexation of Kandy in 1815, this rebellion led to the British breaking that promise and subsequently allowing parity between all religions.²⁹ This was a choice that was not taken lightly. Indeed the governor of Ceylon at the time, Robert Brownrigg, was not convinced that this would cement British power relations in Kandy, stating that 'the people were willing to less to them'.³⁰ Nevertheless, the policy was pursued and was certainly emblematic of the cultural shift in Ceylon that was both instigated and utilised by the British to cement their powerful position.

Today, the rebellion's legacy endures in Sri Lankan historical consciousness as a symbol of resistance to oppression. Literature is published regarding this rebellion as a heroic last stand against foreign rule. Indeed, in one example the dedication is to the 'sacred memory' of those who died, whose 'blood is written in the history of our country'.³¹ Moreover, the text is littered with references to the 'barbarously splendid' Court of Kandy and the 'barbarities' employed by the British.³² One instance of such 'barbarity' highlights an ignorant disregard of Kandyan Sinhalese culture. During a time of rising discontent between the annexation of Kandy and the outbreak of rebellion, it was proposed by a Sinhalese rebel to remove the replica of the Tooth of the Buddha from Kandy. This was, and still is, a core part of Kandyan Sinhalese identity as well as the root of their nationalistic claim over Sri Lanka. This proposal was unknown to high-ranking British officials such as British representative John D'Oyly, who at this time was perhaps best known for drafting the 1815 proposal to annex Kandy.³³ This lack of communication reflects the lack of respect that the British gave to Kandy and its associated symbolic power. For the Sri Lankan population, acts such as these were simply a continuation of centuries of colonial

²⁷ Pieris, *Tri Sinhala*, pp. 211-212

²⁸ Dewaraja, *The Kandyan Kingdom*, p. 97

²⁹ Little, A., *Labouring to Learn: Towards a Political Economy of Plantations, People and Education in Sri Lanka*, Colombo, SSA, 1999, p. 76

³⁰ Little, *Labouring to Learn*, p. 76

³¹ Vimalananda, *The Great Rebellion*, p. vi

³² Vimalananda, *The Great Rebellion*, pp. xxviii-xliii

³³ Vimalananda, *The Great Rebellion*, pp. xxix-xxx

oppression. Culturally offensive acts such as the proposal to remove the Tooth of the Buddha fomented not only a rebellion, but long-lasting feelings of discontent that sharpened the Sinhalese Buddhist nationalist ideology that characterises Sri Lankan society today. As Governor Robert Brownrigg stated after the rebellion, ill-feeling derived from the curtailing of the rights and privileges of the Kandyan people that had been promised to them just two years prior.³⁴ Crucially, this rebellion represented the time in which the British presence on the island transitioned from exploratory to colonial. The promises that came with the 1815 annexation were swiftly disregarded in favour of colonial control. The rebels involved in the rebellion against the British were severely punished, including burning down the residences of the leadership.³⁵ Further, the promise of respect in 1815 was broken in ways that indicate the broad direction in which British colonial control would approach. Seizure of land, harsh deposition of disloyal Kandyans in favour of loyalists and a willingness to minimise Kandyan Sinhalese culture became key components of colonial rule. Colonial rule was established here, and the seeds of discontent that characterised Ceylonese society then and Sri Lankan society today were planted.

3.1.2 The Matale Rebellion of 1848

Over thirty-two years after The Uva-Wellassa Rebellion, another flashpoint of discontent erupted. If the aforementioned rebellion represented the moment in which old elites were deposed and colonial control was established, the Matale Rebellion of 1848 was the result of years of mismanagement centred around the abolition of slavery and the introduction of indentured labour into Ceylon. The discontent that resulted in the rebellion will be shown to have cut across three parts of society: the colonial government, the planters, and the labourers. A paracolonial analytical lens will be applied to this rebellion to demonstrate how Ceylonese society reacted to and was moulded by this rebellion focused on socio-economic discontent and fuelled by political marginalisation.

The British annexed the independent Kandyan Kingdom in 1815 through the Kandyan Convention, marking the end of centuries of resistance to foreign domination. Initially, the British promised to uphold local customs and preserve the power of the Kandyan chiefs. However, over time, British centralization policies eroded the autonomy of these elites, transforming them into mere administrative functionaries under colonial rule. The dismantling of the Kandyan socio-political order created widespread resentment, as the British failed to honour promises made in the convention.

The discontent deriving from the failure to honour the promises present in the Kandyan Convention was exacerbated when the British introduced Western legal and land tenure systems, displacing traditional practices. This disrupted local governance and diminished the status of the

³⁴ Vimalananda, *The Great Rebellion*, p. xxix

³⁵ Vimalananda, *The Great Rebellion*, p. xxx

Kandyan aristocracy, whose power had rested on their control over land and labour. Consequently, the once-powerful chiefs became marginalized, and their grievances found resonance among the rural peasantry, who suffered from economic hardship and the loss of communal land rights.³⁶

Losing communal land rights led to a harbouring of discontent amongst the Kandyan Sinhalese peasantry. *The Planters' Association*, whilst formally set up after the Matale Rebellion in 1854, were discussing the ramifications of the Crown Lands Ordinance of 1840 almost a century later in 1928. They lamented how colonial policies led to inharmonious living conditions due to the Sinhalese people lacking the disposition to leave their home villages, nor wanting to live in a mixture of castes.³⁷ This tension ended up being a crucial instigator of the Matale Rebellion. The Kandyan Sinhalese were unwilling to leave their home villages due to unfamiliar Western legal land systems. Moreover, the vast common land required to house the displaced people required extensive public works. As the Subcommittee of the Planters Association of Ceylon pointed out, "definite boundaries, individual rights of way, water service, sanitary provision, houses, pasture lands, and all the multifarious arrangements essential to the well-being of a very large number of people" were necessary.³⁸ Additionally, different types of people were brought from many different parts of the country, such as Sinhalese, Tamils, Moors and Malaysians. A diverse mix of people such as this meant that various castes were also placed together.³⁹ For Kandyans in particular, this resulted in the feeling of being sidelined in their own homeland.⁴⁰ Albeit several decades after the rebellion, this memorandum from *The Planters' Association* shows long-standing discontent with the policies of a colonial government determined to keep a firm grasp on Ceylonese society.

The disaffection felt by the Kandyan Sinhalese was not solely due to colonial government policies. The plantation owners themselves actively contributed to this feeling of 'sidelining' through a complex web of migratory power systems they established in bringing Indian Tamil labourers to Ceylonese shores. As discussed in the previous chapter, the introduction of these labourers from the 1830s saw the rise of the Kangany system of recruitment that installed an increasingly splintered social dynamic between even the Tamil people within Ceylon. On the one hand, the power that planters had in this area certainly would not be possible without the ordinances pushed by the colonial government. Indeed, their jobs would not be nearly as plentiful without them. On the other hand, the planters also utilised the situation for their own profit to not only

³⁶ De Silva, K.M., *A History of Sri Lanka*, London, Hurst, 1981, p. 225

³⁷ Minutes of the Meetings of Subcommittees of the Planters Association of Ceylon from March 1926 to March 1929, Colombo, 14 January 1928, Sri Lanka National Archives (hereafter SLNA) 248/2

³⁸ Minutes of the Meetings of Subcommittees of the Planters Association of Ceylon from March 1926 to March 1929, Colombo, 14 January 1928, SLNA 248/2

³⁹ Minutes of the Meetings of Subcommittees of the Planters Association of Ceylon from March 1926 to March 1929, Colombo, 14 January 1928, SLNA 248/2

⁴⁰ Duncan, J., *In the Shadows of the Tropics: Climate, Race and Biopower in Nineteenth Century Ceylon*, Burlington, Ashgate, 2007, p. 118

install their own power hierarchies within society but also transform old Sinhalese land in the name Western global markets that were completely foreign to them. This led to both physical divides in Ceylon as well as economic splits that devastated the Kandyan Sinhalese as their source of income was suddenly uprooted.

Key to this economic split was the “Grain Tax” that put increasing strain on farmers who were unused to the increased production required by the colonial government. This required all males to pay a fixed sum annually. The tax system was a regressive one, disproportionately affecting the rural peasantry, particularly in the Kandyan highlands. Subsistence agriculture was prevalent, meaning that output had the goal of sustenance for the local community, not the mass plantation farming pursued by the British. Problems littered this tax. Firstly, assessment of the crops, and therefore the required tax, was made before they even started growing. The unpredictability of Ceylonese land made this wholly unfair on the peasants.⁴¹ Moreover, the British government sometimes allowed arrears to stack up and then hit the peasants with a lump sum that they owed.⁴² Many peasants struggled to pay the tax in cash, forcing them into debt and severe economic hardships.

The initial spark of rebellion came when on 1st July 1848 license fees were introduced on a variety of things including guns, dogs, carts and shops. Moreover, labour was made compulsory on plantation roads due to the need for extra transport links from the plantations to the coast for export. This was seen in a particularly cynical light as an attempt to revive *rājākariya* for the benefit of the planters.⁴³ These taxes then were yet an extra burden not only on the finances of the Kandyan Sinhalese peasants but also on their traditions. Being forcibly coerced to perform labour, which was in turn heavily taxed, by anyone other than a Kandyan King was an offensive act.

The rebellion itself encapsulates the plight felt by the Kandyans since the arrival of the British. For instance, one of the leaders, Gongalegoda Banda, claimed descent from the line of Kandyan royalty that was deposed in the Uva-Wellassa Rebellion three decades earlier. Embodying the restoration of the Kandyan monarchy, he was crowned as a symbolic king at the Buddhist temple in Dambulla, thus invoking nationalist fervour.⁴⁴ Further, unhappy with the oppressive bureaucracy that had been placed on them in recent decades, the rebels targeted British administrative offices, tax collectors, and infrastructure in the Matale district. Their strategy relied on surprise attacks and exploiting the difficult terrain. However, the British, aided by local collaborators, quickly mobilized troops to suppress the rebellion. Martial law was declared, and

⁴¹ Roberts, M., “Grain Taxes in British Ceylon, 1832-1878: Problems in the Field”, *The Journal of Asian Studies*, vol. 27, n. 4, 1968, p. 825

⁴² Roberts, “Grain Taxes”, p. 825

⁴³ Taylor, M., “The 1848 Revolutions and the British Empire”, *Past and Present*, vol. 166, n. 1, 2000, pp. 164-165

⁴⁴ Roberts, M., *People Inbetween: The Burghers and the Middle Class in the Transformations within Sri Lanka, 1790s-1960s*, Colombo, Sarvodaya Vishva Lekha, 1989, p. 45

a brutal crackdown ensued. The leaders were captured, executed, or as was the case for Gongalegoda Banda, exiled to Mauritius.⁴⁵

3.1.3 Rebellion Implications

Although the Matale Rebellion failed in its immediate objectives, it sowed the seeds of Sinhalese nationalist consciousness in Ceylon. This rebellion centred around not leaders of the traditional elite but those of peasant stock. The aim was to make a return to the traditional Kandyan pattern of life through crowning one of their own as king.⁴⁶ Religion, an ever present in Sinhalese historical consciousness, also played a crucial part in their motivations. Stretching back to the Kandyan Convention of 1815 in which the British stated that a policy goal was to disassociate the Ceylonese state from Buddhism, the increased Christian presence on the island was seen to have helped to stoke a rebellious fervour amongst the Kandyan Sinhalese. Consequently, after the rebellion, the original goal of disassociate remained but with the concession that there was an obligation to initiate and supervise the performance of legal functions with regard to Buddhist temporalities in particular.⁴⁷ As the broad aim of returning to Kandyan traditions saw a dual focus on royalty and religion, the fires of Sinhalese nationalism can be seen to have been borne in the spark of rebellion.

It is worth noting that there is an interesting historiographical debate regarding if British policies created a landless Sinhalese proletariat. It is perhaps most commonly assumed that British policies, including the Crown Lands Ordinance of 1840, was the reason these Sinhalese were pauperised. British officials were involved in the planting industry and wanted the land for themselves, thereby displacing the Sinhalese.⁴⁸ However, another proposition has since been put forward. After approximately 1836, it was found that the ideal elevation for coffee crop production was over 1700 feet above sea level. These areas did not encroach on traditional village land, and it required a permanent workforce to man. The Sinhalese peasantry was instead consolidated in their village by enabling a substitution of their method of cultivation, chena, with a land-intensive one. As a result, there was no incentive to settle on the plantations as a permanent workforce. This is reflected in the fact that by 1871 only 3.33% of the resident population on the estates were Sinhalese.⁴⁹ However, this did not change the fact that they had been made systematically poorer by the encroaching influence of the British that used its colonial reach to create divisions in a place in which the Kandyan Sinhalese had ruled for centuries.

The stirring of Sinhalese Buddhist nationalism from oppressive socio-economic policies is but one facet of a larger picture. The annexation of Kandy in 1815 by the British was ideal for them as

⁴⁵ Ludowyk, E.F.C., *The Story of Ceylon*, London, Faber & Faber, 1962, p. 153

⁴⁶ De Silva, *A History*, p. 231

⁴⁷ De Silva, *A History*, p. 234

⁴⁸ Kurian, *State, Capital and Labour*, p. 56

⁴⁹ Kurian, *State, Capital and Labour*, pp. 56-57

they not only unseated the source of political power but also gained access to a vast expanse of land that was prime for plantation agriculture. This began a fascination with plantation agriculture, in the hope that it would bring not only wealth to the planters, but a modern and buoyant Ceylonese economy.⁵⁰ The subsequent obsession by the colonial government and the planters with coffee cultivation led to a coffee boom in the early 1840s that was inspired primarily by the sale of lands for plantation agriculture in 1840.⁵¹ However, a severe economic depression hit in 1847, leading to the new governor of the colony George Byng, Viscount Torrington, to impose the aforementioned taxes that provided the spark of rebellion centred in Matale. The volatility of the global economic market, along with an apparent disregard for the immediate needs and wants of the Indigenous population, was also a large factor in this particular rebellious movement.

3.1.4 Influence of Migratory Patterns

Entangling local agricultural patterns, then, had far-reaching socio-economic consequences that affected many strata of society. One particular stratum that was introduced to Ceylon through British economic policy was that of the Indian indentured labourers. Their inclusion into Ceylonese society was unprecedented as they rapidly became the backbone of the colonial economy. From when 'coffee-mania' gripped the nation from the 1840s the agricultural-export economy became the driving force of colonial policy.⁵² The integration of this new class of people, one that did not exist even at the time of the Uva-Wellassa Rebellion, meant that by the time of the peasant-led rebellion of 1848 there were differing power dynamics in play even between the peasant-class in Ceylon.

The aforementioned economic depression that hit Ceylon was therefore intimately entangled with the previously flourishing plantation industry on the island. A drastic fall of global economic prices 'drove thousands of acres out of cultivation and enabled only the best estates to stay in business.'⁵³ Immigration of labourers, however, saw a vast dip years prior in 1846 and continued to the economic depression. Most scholars attribute this dip to the deplorable economic and social conditions that these labourers had to endure not only when in employment in Ceylon but also on the journey there with the corrupt Kangany system. The Governor himself, Lord Torrington, expressed such an opinion in stating that the fall of immigration was the result "not of a fear of the Kandyans, but of causes arising from bad treatment at the hands of the plantation

⁵⁰ De Silva, *A History*, p. 229

⁵¹ De Silva, *A History*, p. 226

⁵² Wenzlhuemer, R., "Indian Labour Immigration and British Labour Policy in Nineteenth-Century Ceylon", *Modern Asian Studies*, vol. 41, n. 3, 2007, pp. 577-578

⁵³ Driesen, I., *The Long Walk: Indian Plantation Labour in Sri Lanka in the Nineteenth Century*, New Delhi, Prestige Books, 1997, p. 21

owners.”⁵⁴ So entrenched was the maltreatment of labourers that the minority of plantation owners who treated their workers well were quite publicly scorned. Written in print, a fellow planter stated that they were “pseudo-philanthropists... champions of coolies, caffres, and of every savage under the sun the eager betrayers of their own countrymen.”⁵⁵ This disdain towards the labourers by the owners highlights the systemic disregard for these labourers that permeates from the colonial government through the planters and even to the Kanganies.

Explaining migratory numbers through the maltreatment of workers certainly has merit. It is true that the perception of working the plantations in Ceylon had shifted when horror stories of corrupt Kanganies and hard labour practises reached the Tamil Nadu region of India.⁵⁶ However, external factors also contribute to this drop in migration figures. A cholera epidemic took hold of Ceylon in 1845, with contemporary Colonial Secretary James Tennent noting that this was a contributing factor both in the drop of labourers on the plantations as well as those migrating from India. However, it is unlikely that the cholera epidemic was so widespread as to cause a mass statistical drop-off in the plantations due to their high elevation.⁵⁷ A final external factor to consider is that of India. Another region fixed squarely in the British colonial economy, they historically jostled with Ceylon for migrant labour. An uptick in migration flow from India to Ceylon just before the economic depression in 1847 seemingly goes against the theory that labourers were turned off by harsh conditions in the plantations. However, it is likely that this was primarily caused by a famine in India at that time, driving labourers to Ceylon in search of increased financial security.⁵⁸

Regardless of the reasons for the fluctuating labour migrations into Ceylon, it is clear that the integration of the local Ceylonese economy into the global market had broad socio-economic implications that allowed for rebellious fervour to reach a zenith. The Uva-Wellassa Rebellion marked the British colonial transition from exploratory to colonial with the takeover of Kandy. The Matale Rebellion, on the other hand, was marked by colonial mismanagement. The colonial government's insistence on a laissez-faire approach to the agricultural export economy of Ceylon created a butterfly effect that swept through multiple strata of society. The harsh taxes that provided the spark for the Matale Rebellion was the last in a succession of policies that Kandyan Sinhalese people saw as an affront to their caste. Annual work under the supervision of others was considered to be degrading, as was the loss of their land to ‘foreigners’ in the name of a

⁵⁴ Driesen, *Long Walk*, p. 21

⁵⁵ Driesen, *Long Walk*, p. 36

⁵⁶ Wenzlhuemer, “Indian Labour Immigration”, pp. 576-577. As is the case with migration patterns into Ceylon, the reasons for Ceylon being an attractive prospect had both internal and external factors. Internally, the abolition of slavery deprived West Indian coffee planters of their cheap labour supply. Moreover, removal of protections for trade led to Ceylon becoming a more attractive source of coffee not only for the buyer but the labourer due to higher wages

⁵⁷ Driesen, *Long Walk*, p. 70

⁵⁸ Driesen, *Long Walk*, p. 70

colonial power.⁵⁹ Moreover the susceptibility to both global economic prices and migration fluctuations brought on by a laissez-faire attitude sharply affected British Ceylon as a whole. A blend of socio-economic issues was brought to the forefront with these rebellions that will be shown to have bled into the development of both British Ceylon and post-British Sri Lanka.

3.2 Day-to-Day Resistance

Broad economic mismanagement led to the institutional rebellious activity explored earlier, whilst these same factors forced the day-to-day disobedience displayed by the Indian indentured labourers. The laissez-faire system that led to such discontent within the Kandyan Sinhalese population also gave rise to severe grievances within the community of Indian indentured labourers. Pronounced economic interests from an intersection of the colonial government, the planters, and the Kanganies coalesced into a system that favoured a cheap and steady workforce over their wellbeing.⁶⁰ It is not surprising that the subsequent system of indentured labour migration was likened by some scholars to 'a new system of slavery'.⁶¹

What follows in this section is a look at what constituted rebellious activity for the indentured labourers. Naturally, they had less resources available to them compared with the rebellions at Matale and Uva-Wellassa. Their resulting resistance replicated itself in harming their oppressors in the only way they could: economically. This meant smaller, or less grand, acts of disobedience were carried out to resist the 'economic and ritual marginalisation they now suffer'.⁶² However, the challenges inherent in this come down to the same challenges found in subaltern studies more generally: an acute lack of source material. This boils down to two things. Firstly, day-to-day rebellious activities rarely make headlines. There is hardly ever a dramatic confrontation, or an event that may make the news. If a dramatic event occurs, it is due to a thousand tiny cuts toppling the giant of oppression. Secondly, it is rare that those in power wish to publicise such acts of subordination. In doing so their policies would be unmasked as unpopular, while their authority might be seen as tenuous.⁶³ As a result, what follows is analysis forged largely through accounts from those higher up the ladder of power, such as the planters and the British. From there the role of rebellious activity by the Ceylonese subaltern can be extrapolated paracoloniaally to see how their unsecured standing in society eventually stabilized itself into the modern era of Sri Lankan history.

3.2.1 Laissez-Faire Rebellions

⁵⁹ Kurian, *State, Capital and Labour*, p. 77

⁶⁰ Wenzlhuemer, "Indian Labour Immigration", p. 583

⁶¹ Tinker, H.R., *A New System of Slavery: The Export of Indian Labour Overseas 1830-1920*, London, Oxford University Press, 1974, pp. 1-4

⁶² Scott, *Weapons of the Weak*, p. xviii

⁶³ Scott, *Weapons of the Weak*, p. 36

Rebellious activity carried out by the indentured labourers mirrored the era of unadulterated free markets that characterised the coffee-era plantation period. Due to the rather intentional separation of plantation estates there was little in the way of communication between labourers, let alone organised resistance. As a result of this ‘compartmentalisation’, as Rachel Kurian states, absenteeism and bolting were the two most prevalent methods of resistance.⁶⁴ Both were quite effective as they hurt their oppressors economically and could work independently of each other. It is also important to note that the Indian plantation workers had on paper, certain employment rights such as a wage. However, these were not followed in many cases due to two main factors. Firstly, the system of indebtedness they found themselves in was made worse by the fact that any behaviour deemed ‘wrong’ by the employer was punished in the form of a fine, which came out of their future wages. For example, desertion was punishable by the forfeiture of wages and imprisonment of up to three months.⁶⁵ This strengthened their ties to their employer further, creating a cycle of debt that was difficult to break out of.

Further, the initial rights the workers had legally under Ordinance No. 5 of 1841 were rarely accessible to the worker in a practical sense. This was due to their high level of illiteracy coupled with the level of control exerted on them by the Kanganies and estate management. In 1847 Colonial Secretary James Tennent observed that the ‘coolie’ was either generally unaware of his rights or apprehensive of causing annoyance. As a result, ‘his disposition and habit was to suffer in silence’.⁶⁶

3.2.2 Absenteeism

Absenteeism, the act of not going to the place of work that you are scheduled to be at, was performed by an average of 25% of labourers. According to the Labour Commission of 1908, it was particularly pronounced in the low country regions where turnout was regularly between 60 and 70%.⁶⁷ However, this form of resistance in some way did not result in the desired effect. The Commission used this high level of absenteeism to validate the low wages that the labourers were given for their work.

Moreover, the reality of refusing to work was that it resulted in severe punishments administered by the employer. This usually took the form of violent outbursts. In one such case, a labourer who threatened to stop work due to months of unpaid wages was not able to induce his employer to pay his wages. Quite the opposite; he had the man whipped to death instead.⁶⁸

⁶⁴ Kurian, *State, Capital and Labour*, p. 117

⁶⁵ Kurian, *State, Capital and Labour*, p. 94

⁶⁶ Kurian, *State, Capital and Labour*, p. 95

⁶⁷ Kurian, *State, Capital and Labour*, p. 81

⁶⁸ Driesen, *Long Walk*, p. 26

Absenteeism could also reflect on the feelings of helplessness due to the predatory system of debt inflicted on the indentured labourer from the moment they agree to travel to Ceylon. They were so heavily indebted to the Kangany that takes them to their plantation that their motivation to work dropped. However, it is a system that almost encourages absenteeism. As the Commission states: “the cooly knows that the Kangany cannot afford to lose him and that he will be looked after if he does not work.”⁶⁹ Any work done by the labourer would go straight to the Kangany and into the vertical system of debts established by the British plantation system. This link between indebtedness and absenteeism was also noted by two contemporary planters, Wright and Huyshe-Elliott. They noticed their daily absenteeism figures of 30% correlated strongly with the individual level of debt.⁷⁰

3.2.3 Bolting

The act of deserting the estate in which the labourer was tied to, or ‘bolting’, was a form of resistance that preoccupied estate management for over a century. Protests of this kind were motivated by now familiar reasons. A culture of indebtedness mixed with harsh working conditions created an environment that necessitated either change or escape at all costs.

This was an act of rebellion common to plantations across colonies. Mirroring the materials available in Colombo National Archives, Jan Breman notes that the Dutch Planters Association in modern-day Malaysia exchanged a lot of correspondence detailing reasons for bolting and ways to fix it. Many examples were linked with the financial dire straits labourers found themselves in. Similar to the plantations in Ceylon, labourers would receive an advance of money when joining a plantation, which they would use to reduce their debt to the headman, a ‘Kangany’, when moving plantation after bolting.⁷¹ This chain of correspondence between planters serves as a reminder that a form of unionisation, or ‘professionalisation’, usually occurs amongst the more powerful groups in society before those with less power.

In 1921 Ceylon, for instance, an Assistant Commissioner expressed concern that a Kangany from a large estate in Ceylon was sourcing new recruits from a local professional recruiter in the Indian Tamil Nadu region. The concern sprung from the fact that the ‘quality’ of these recruits diminished with every new batch, stating that some of them were ‘riffraff from the streets’. Further, and most concerning for the estate in question, the rate of bolting was high. Eighty were said to have already deserted at the time of writing, and this number was said to have been increasing month by month.⁷² Whilst bolting was still a concern, the primary concern here was

⁶⁹ Kurian, *State, Capital and Labour*, p. 118

⁷⁰ Kurian, *State, Capital and Labour*, pp. 117-118

⁷¹ Breman, J., *Taming the Coolie Beast: Plantation Society and the Colonial Order in Southeast Asia*, Delhi, Oxford University Press, 1989, p. 50

⁷² Minutes of the Meetings of the Labour and Coast Agency Committee from January 1917 to March 1925. Vol. I, Colombo, 11 August 1921, SLNA, 248/1

the Kangany abusing the financial power that was bestowed upon them, resulting in an increase in bolting activity. This demonstrates both the 'unionisation' of planters that occurred in Ceylon as well as another example of why labourers may bolt, this time due to corrupt activity on the part of their recruiter.

Much like absenteeism, this method of resistance routinely led to harsh punishment. Minimising one evil merely meant giving rise to another in the form of a tighter financial grip. To prevent desertions, it was common for planters to intentionally keep wages in arrears, as they saw it as the most effective means of preventing workers from abandoning the estate.⁷³

What, then, can be gleaned from these two prominent forms of rebellion exhibited by the Indian indentured labourers? An inherently unbalanced power dynamic between employer and labourer meant that in reality they had very few options to improve their situation. Severe physical punishments that could lead to death were commonplace, while withholding their wages was another method the estate management used to bring any dissidents to heel. Additionally, the 'compartmentalisation' of labour ensured that communication, and therefore a chance of mass organised labour, was minimised. Little changed in this area until the early decades of the twentieth century when laissez-faire capitalism slowly morphed into a more professional outfit. Analysis of this professionalisation will underscore how the integration of the plantation sector further into the nation state eventually allowed for more organised forms of protest not only for the indentured labourer, but for multiple strata of Ceylonese society.

3.3 Long Shadows

The professionalisation of institutions happened at different paces depending on your standing in society. Though the planters had banded together into the powerful organisation called *The Planters' Association of Ceylon* as early as 1854, it took a further century for the wisps of organisation to form for the indentured labourers.⁷⁴ The causes of such disparity will be interrogated in detail here. Ultimately, however, it comes down to the hierarchies of power explored previously. Those at the top had more freedom to explore legal avenues to achieve their interests in society, as expressed by the aforementioned organisation. Conversely, the indentured labourers under the employment of the planters were entangled in myriad legal and systemic oppressions that hampered their ability to organise resistance. A long-enduring image of them as 'birds of passage' ensured that they were always seen as somewhat of an outsider. Their presence in Ceylon was merely out of circumstance rather than love for the island. As a

⁷³ Driesen, *Long Walk*, p. 26

⁷⁴ Nadesan, S., *A History of the Up-Country Tamil People in Sri Lanka*, Colombo, Rancor Printers and Publishers Ltd., 1993, p. 83

result, their rights could not match those of 'true' Ceylonese people.⁷⁵ What follows is an analysis of how the seeds of the institutional Sinhalese rebellions and the indentured labourer resistances set precedents for how the Indian Tamils live in the Sinhalese Buddhist-dominated Sri Lankan society of today.

The shell of 'compartmentalisation' that restricted the possibility of organisation between labourers on different plantations was slowly chipped away by outside forces that broadened the political platform available to them. The first of which was a growing criticism of the indentured labour system both in India and England. The latter was led by British reformists, who wished to look at the culture of life on the estates from housing to health to education.⁷⁶ Crucially here is the role of India. Due to a swell of nationalist sentiment within India, which led to greater opposition to this 'new form of slavery' experienced by Indians working in the colonies, indentureship was abolished in 1917. The ramifications of this were not felt overnight, but due to a series of ordinances passed by the Indian government in 1922 and the Ceylonese government the following year, migration took on a different hue. As Rachel Kurian states, "between 1923 and 1939 there was an overall increase in the number of workers who came to Ceylon for plantation work, as well as an increased degree of permanence as workers acquired the habit of returning to work on the same estates."⁷⁷ The increasingly permanent character of the labourer allowed for the basis of large-scale collective action due to strengthened ties between the estates and the villages in southern India.⁷⁸

This basis for increased collective action would not have been possible without removing some of the symptoms arising from the laissez-faire plantation capitalism that defined a century of labourers' lives. The Jackson Commission on Immigration in 1938 identified broad reforms that improved working conditions for the labourer that resulted in a more permanently settled workforce. Of particular note was the abolition of the predatory Kangany system in 1921 that allowed the individual kanganies to transfer labourers between estates almost at will to simultaneously increase their wealth and saddle the labourer with more debt. Partly on the insistence of India, the Ceylonese government began supervising the methods of recruitment in tandem with introducing debt controlling legislation by the mid-1920s.⁷⁹ Through inhibiting the predatory impulses of the kanganies both on the road and in estate life, the labourer began to exhibit a more sedentary character.

Day-to-day life also saw some improvement in this period. Educational facilities were provided to the children of the estate workers by laws introduced in 1907 and 1920. The various Medical

⁷⁵ Samaraweera, V., "Indian Tamil Immigrant Labour in Ceylon and the Land Problem: The Case of the Land Development Ordinance of 1935", *Proceedings of the Fourth International Conference Seminar of Tamil Studies*, vol. 2, 1974, pp. 97-99

⁷⁶ Kurian, *State, Capital and Labour*, p. 250

⁷⁷ Kurian, *State, Capital and Labour*, p. 250

⁷⁸ Kurian, *State, Capital and Labour*, p. 250

⁷⁹ Samaraweera, "Indian Tamil Immigrant Labour", p. 97

Wants and Diseases Ordinances that dealt with and sought improvements in the neglected fields of housing, health, and sanitation also led to longer, healthier, and more comfortable lives for the labourers compared with before. Moreover, the stable character of the population was perhaps reflected, too, in the balancing out of its sex-ratio. During the coffee-era plantation period the male-ratio was high due to their families being left behind. By the 1920's this had changed completely and males, females, and children under the age of sixteen each comprised roughly one-third of the population each.⁸⁰ Not all changes were broadly positive, however. The previously mentioned tightening of control of labourers' lives on the estates to prevent 'bolting' is reflective of their continued low societal status. However, the tangible improvements to labourers' lives are indicative of the professionalisation of Ceylonese society both in direct relation with the labourer and on the whole. The areas of improvement here will be investigated further in the final two chapters. It is important to note here that these improvements in society were the result of a more inclusive political arena developed in early twentieth century Ceylonese society.

An increasingly settled nature for Indian Tamils on the island had deep political ramifications. Firstly, and perhaps most importantly, was the introduction of universal franchise for all persons who had resided on the island for five or more years due to the Donoughmore Constitution in 1931.⁸¹ Prior to this, franchise depended on income, property and literacy qualifications that had encompassed only around four percent. This resulted in the registration of around one hundred thousand Indian Tamils whilst the first general election in 1931 saw two Indian Tamils elected from plantation areas.⁸² Extending the franchise universally in this way was, however, controversial. On a platform of fear mongering regarding Indian intervention in Ceylonese matters, many politicians and aristocrats voiced concern over allowing labourers with Indian heritage the right to vote. Nadesan notes, somewhat sarcastically, that "they [aristocrats and local capitalists] loved the country so wholeheartedly that they clamoured for the extension of franchise to European planters, capitalists and Indian merchants and money-lenders while they stood totally against votes for the estate workers born and bred here in the island."⁸³ This broad antipathy to the extension of the franchise stemmed from old perceptions of Indian Tamils being a transitory people, all the while being framed through the lens of colonial hierarchical power structures.

This development allowed the Indian voice in society to become more vocal about injustices and more able to enact change. For example, a proposed amendment to the Village Committee Ordinance in 1937, which determined amongst other things who was allowed to vote or be liable to pay taxes, wished to include Europeans and Burghers who were previously excluded. This

⁸⁰ Samaraweera, "Indian Tamil Immigrant Labour", p. 97

⁸¹ Kurian, *State, Capital and Labour*, p. 252

⁸² Kurian, *State, Capital and Labour*, p. 252

⁸³ Nadesan, *History of the Up-Country Tamil People*, p. 72

would leave the Indian estate population as the only group without these rights in the villages.⁸⁴ The two Indian Tamils elected voiced their concerns, amongst others, but were unsuccessful as the matter was resolved by exempting all estate persons from the Village Committee Franchise. This resulted in outcry from the wider Indian population on the island as a form of racial discrimination.⁸⁵ Indian Tamils once again found themselves at the bottom of the social hierarchy, ignored in favour of European and Burgher people.

A similar reaction was voiced when another act of discrimination occurred, but in this case the local Sinhalese were favoured. The aforementioned Jackson Commission on Immigration clearly stated that there were no economic disadvantages suffered by Ceylon's permanent population on account of Indian immigration. In fact, they were needed to work on the plantations for decades to come.⁸⁶ The Ceylon government did not accept this, however. Due to growing economic pains, such as growing unemployment and a general falling standard of living, it was decided to terminate the employment of daily paid unskilled Indian employees in government departments with less than five years of experience and replace them with local Sinhalese people.⁸⁷

Right up to independence in 1948 the 'Indian question' was not concretely resolved. However, at the time of the 1947 election which would determine the composition of independent Sri Lanka's first parliament, the Tamils of Indian origin were allowed to vote.⁸⁸ Their presence in society, in the view of the British, was seen as positive. In 1936 Sir Edward Jackson noted that the Indian-origin Tamils were doing work that the Sinhalese people were, for whatever reason, unable to complete. Far from harming the economy, the Indian Tamils represented a vast economic benefit to Ceylon.⁸⁹ Conversely, Sinhalese leaders saw their presence and ability to contribute to the democratic process as a danger. Specifically, their presence in the Kandyan area was said to lead to the 'complete political and economic extermination of the Ceylonese, primarily the Sinhalese'.⁹⁰ This prejudice against the Indian Tamils by the Sinhalese meant that the professionalisation of their resistance, being able to vote, was at risk when Sri Lanka became independent. Indeed, their ability to vote was removed by the Sinhalese-dominated parliament the year after the 1947 election. This would leave the Indian Tamils stateless and powerless in Sinhalese society for multiple decades.⁹¹ This shift underscores the Indian Tamil position in society. Being at the bottom of the hierarchies of power established by the British, and retaining

⁸⁴ Kurian, *State, Capital and Labour*, pp. 253-254

⁸⁵ Kurian, *State, Capital and Labour*, p. 254

⁸⁶ Kurian, *State, Capital and Labour*, p. 254

⁸⁷ Kurian, *State, Capital and Labour*, pp. 254-255

⁸⁸ Fries, Y. and Bibin, T., *The Undesirables: The Expatriation of the Tamil People of Recent Indian Origin from Plantations in Sri Lanka to India*, Calcutta, Bagchi, 1984, p. 18

⁸⁹ Fries and Bibin, *The Undesirables*, p. 18

⁹⁰ Fries and Bibin, *The Undesirables*, p. 18

⁹¹ Fries and Bibin, *The Undesirables*, p. 19

such a position under the Sinhalese, meant that their formal ability to protest through democratic procedures was always determined by those in power at the time.

This development also underscores the intersectional interests that existed in Ceylonese society after over one hundred years of British rule. The favouring of Sinhalese people highlights not only how ingrained the 'transitory' image of the Indian Tamil was, but also the remnants of the Uva and Matale rebellions in the last century. The integration of the 'loyal' Sinhalese people into British Ceylonese society reflects the continuing influence of Sinhalese power in the era of 'professionalisation' undertaken in the early twentieth century. On the other hand, *The Planters' Association of Ceylon* were worried this would affect their source of labour as the Indian government branded the policy as an overt act of discrimination. In a public statement they declared that they are against any measure that would "affect the well-being of estate labourers" and that they are anxious about "the recent action being taken by the Government".⁹² This division between the Ceylonese government and *The Planters' Association* over anti-Indian Tamil discrimination reflects not only the simmering tensions between the British and the planters, but also the role of professional associations in society. *The Planters' Association* became a corporation in 1916, reflecting the integration of Ceylonese financial interests into the global markets. Pertinently, however, it serves as a channel to voice displeasure, to rebel against the Ceylonese government.

Finally, the almost total shift from laissez-faire capitalism in Ceylon to a professional, bureaucratic function in the twentieth century is underscored in the establishment of plantation trade unions in the wake of the Donoughmore Constitution. Three were established: the Ceylon Labour Federation, the Ceylon Indian Congress, and the All-Ceylon Estate Workers Union.⁹³ Militancy increased with their establishment, as strikes were more common, as were demands for wage increases and action against discriminatory employers. This created tensions with other political interests on the island, as a left-wing coalition with plantation workers materialised, increasing class conflict on the island.⁹⁴ Pertinently, the establishment of collective organisations for plantation workers' interests highlights the totality of the professionalisation of society. Acts of rebellion had fundamentally shifted from the era of individual 'compartmentalisation' to a time of collective agency in which grievances could be voiced in the political arena.

The different types of rebellion seen in this chapter reflect the complex intersection of colonial caste hierarchies that make up British Ceylon society. Further, different temporalities were applied to these sections of society. *The Planters' Association*, for instance, was a functioning vehicle for vocalizing grievances in a way that was not made available for much of society until several decades later with the dawn of the trade unions. The lumbering shift to the professionalisation of government apparatus from laissez-faire eventually encompassed most of

⁹² Kurian, *State, Capital and Labour*, p. 257

⁹³ Kurian, *State, Capital and Labour*, p. 262

⁹⁴ Kurian, *State, Capital and Labour*, p. 268

Ceylonese society. The establishment of estate worker trade unions to rebel against, at that point, decades-old malpractices by the Kangany system and estate managements represent a turn away from the 'compartmentalisation' of old into a networked nation of trade unions and elected officials.

This rather idealistic view of this shift masks a truth that carries on into the present day. Even though Indian Tamil people were represented politically, the elected officials came from privilege. As mentioned before, one of the two elected officials in the first elections of 1931 was the son of a head kangany. Coming from a family that took part in oppressing the Indian indentured labourer through cycle of debt implies an increased standing in society. Moreover, excluding the estate workers in the Village Committee Ordinance during the 1930s shows that in spite of a 'professionalisation' of society, in which dissent could be pushed through official channels by a plethora of groups, the stigma attached to the estate workers and their perceived 'transitory' character lingered through this societal shift.

Moreover, the strict caste hierarchies were adopted and taken advantage of by the British colonial government. After the two rebellions of Uva-Wellassa and Matale marked the transition from exploratory to management colonialism, the British kept the loyal Sinhalese within positions of power. Even during the laissez-faire coffee plantation-era, this reward for loyalty can be seen in both the system for Kanganies and allowing the Sinhalese to farm their own land with respect to their standing in the caste. Several decades later in the time of 'long shadows', the Sinhalese were preferred over Indian Tamils in, for example, governmental roles in times of crisis. The British colonial government favoured this, whereas different strata of society did not, such as the planters as their industry is built on Indian migrant labour. This intersection between colonial government, planters, and labourer is a common thread to this chapter, and this thesis, that in this case is driven above all by the global economy. Indeed, in this example it was the economic slump caused by the Wall Street Crash of 1929 that meant a more 'trusted' part of society would fill administrative societal roles over the Indian Tamil. Further back, the drop in coffee prices fuelled a crisis that affected the numbers of Indian migrants, causing panic in an era of laissez-faire economics and attitudes amongst the planters.

Conflict between different strata of society, then, resulted in rebellious acts that by and large were determined by initial power in society and how 'professionalised' society was. This, however, was not the case for the Indian indentured labourers. Even in the era of mass enfranchisement and trade unions, their voice was quashed under societal stigma. Within the plantation, an oppressive level of control was exerted to hinder rebellious activities. Control and coercion sprung up in insidious ways, preventing any meaningful change for the voices of the subaltern for decades.⁹⁵ The reasons for change were dependent on a multitude of factors that coalesce around one factor: agency.

⁹⁵ Jayawardena and Kurian, *Class, Patriarchy and Ethnicity*, p. 17

Chapter Four: Educating the Excluded through Language, Caste, and Structural Violence

“Labourers and their families were members of at least two communities and two systems of cultural reproduction.”¹

The well-being of a child is considered to be the responsibility of the family and the state. The former provides micro level support in the shape of love, care, protection, nutrition, and socialisation. On the other hand, the state is responsible for macro level functions such as the provision of schools and health services. If either one fails in carrying out their responsibilities, the welfare of the child suffers. For example, even though a family may be able to financially provide a good education, health treatment and nutritious food for the child, it is unable to build the schools and hospitals necessary to access these services without state support.²

Indian Tamil migrants in Ceylon, meanwhile, had three institutions to access resources. In order of influence these were: the family, the estate management, and the state. However, each of these in some capacities were inadequate in providing sufficient welfare. Firstly, the families on the estates were economically weak and thus lacked the strength to provide their own resources. The estate management, their employer, provided limited support for the welfare of workers. The support given was generally in proportion to profits made. The existence of this institution beside family and state is a unique feature of the plantation economy. Finally, to access state resources one must be part of a group that is integrated into the national community, as the state is only obliged to look after the welfare of its citizens. The state invariably contributes the most, suggesting that the well-being of the child of a community of migrant workers is a function of integration into any given society.³

This chapter will expand on this rather broad summary of how access to public services was minimised at every layer of society for the Indian Tamil estate worker. To do this, the focus will be put on one type of public service: education. Analysis of this framework will illustrate how religion and language coalesced to sustain the hierarchies of power that kept the indentured labourer in a position of societal insecurity. Further, in considering the development of education through a paracolonial lens, the change from British Ceylon to independent Sri Lanka did little to integrate the estate worker. This chapter argues that the Sinhalese rulers at the top of post-independence Sri Lanka actively replicated the colonial power structures to sustain the Indian Tamil position at the bottom of society.

¹ Little, A., *Labouring to Learn: Towards a Political Economy of Plantations, People and Education in Sri Lanka*, Colombo, SSA, 1999, p. 104

² Nallasamy, A., *Rights of Tamil Children in a Plantation Community*, Colombo, Initiative in Research and Education for Development in Asia (INASIA), 2000, p. 2

³ Nallasamy, *Rights of Tamil Children*, pp. 2-3

Analysis of education on the plantations will illuminate the “divide and rule” system that characterised British rule of Ceylon. Indeed, the “twin pillars” of racial division and patriarchy laid the groundwork of class-based capital exploitation that the Indian Tamil labourers experienced in Ceylon. This intersection between class, race, and gender has been dubbed by sociologist Berch Berberoglu as the “triangle of oppression”.⁴ The physical split of plantation to society reflects this ‘triangle’, as does the hierarchy of power embedded not only in the plantation structure between employer and labourer, but also in the caste system utilised by the British to sustain their control. A complement to this theory that deepens the framework to analyse education through is Johan Galtung's own theory of the same name. Here, Galtung notes how a cycle of violence can permeate through and strengthen divisions within a given society. In his influential paper ‘Violence, Peace, and Peace Research’, the concept of ‘structural violence’ is put forward.⁵ This is a less direct form of violence that happens ‘at the hands of an *actor* who *intends* this to be the consequence’.⁶ Instead, violence is ‘the difference between the potential and the actual’ when the aforementioned difference is avoidable.⁷ From this the idea that structures, or institutions, can be violent is developed as they can play a role in limiting either an individual or a group’s potential. On the surface the idea that structures are harmful is not new. In 1845 Friedrich Engels introduced the term ‘social murder’ to describe the dark social and economic recesses of capitalism that brought misery and death upon the working class.⁸ Galtung's idea of structural violence, however, showed that violence could be inadvertent and also the result of actions taken by no one in particular. This renders the violence invisible, something that on the individual level may even seem ‘natural’.

Both Berberoglu's ‘triangle of oppression’ and Galtung's ‘structural violence’ analytical lenses illuminate the inner workings of educational policy to highlight the invisible hand of structural violence placed on the indentured labourers. To achieve this, it is pertinent first to historicise how educational attainment within Sri Lanka has shifted through different colonial powers into the modern-day Sinhalese era. Shifting dynamics in relation to language and religion shaped how educational attainment shaped society. Further, as was explored in detail in chapter three, the shift from laissez-faire style control to a more bureaucratic-centred professional approach to society will be shown to have shaped the way in which those in lower strata of society were heard. However, the voices of the Indian Tamil plantation workers were silenced due to a sequence of unsuccessful negotiations between Sri Lanka and India from the time of

⁴ Berberoglu, B., “Class, Race and Gender: The Triangle of Oppression”, *Race, Sex & Class*, vol. 2, n. 1, 1994, pp. 69-77

⁵ Galtung, J., “Violence, Peace, and Peace Research”, *Journal of Peace Research*, vol. 6, n. 3, 1969, pp. 167-191

⁶ Galtung, “Violence”, p. 168

⁷ Taylor, S., “Structural Violence, Oppression, and the Place-Based Marginality of Homelessness”, *Canadian Social Work Review*, vol. 30, n. 2, 2013, p. 257

⁸ Taylor, “Structural Violence”, p. 257

independence.⁹ Indeed, the perception of them on the 'sidelines' of society after physically being separated for over a century became reality with the adoption of the Citizenship Act of 1948.¹⁰ This act rendered this group effectively stateless and without any political rights that would help their standing in society. At this point, the state refused to provide key services related to one's well-being to an entire group of people, leading to a replication and deepening of oppression that silenced the subaltern in independent Sri Lanka.

Finally, it is worth noting that this analysis of indentured labourers is one part of a wider issue pertaining to Sri Lankan history education at this moment. Whilst Tamil histories are systematically sidelined in schools, digging deeper reveals that Indian Tamils, Muslim, and even Christian histories are ignored. This deeper look at historical tensions reveals that tensions within society are not simply along ethnic divides as the recent Sri Lankan Civil War would suggest. Historical tensions are also along religious, class, and caste divides.¹¹ This alternative 'triangle of oppression' allows for a thorough interrogation of the different intersectional identities that not only made up this society but were the subject of structural violence across time through social programs such as education.

4.1 Educating for a Colonial Future

4.1.1 Shaping a Colonial Society

Colonial education in Sri Lanka through the Portuguese, Dutch, and the British reflected the shifting waves of priorities exhibited by the changing regimes. Indeed, on a broad scale, Karl Marx states that educational systems are intrinsically static and stabilizing of class relations in broader society. The skills and values promoted by education systems 'correspond' with the demands of the social relations of capitalist economic production.¹² This view of education as a force for societal stabilisation lends itself well to the paracolonial method of analysis found in this thesis. Analysis of how education shaped society as a whole through different regime changes proves how intersectional issues such as class, race, gender, and caste were subject to and were influenced by the European capitalist production that was placed upon the island of Sri Lanka from the time of the Portuguese.

Language and religion were at the forefront of issues pertaining to education from the outset of Portuguese influence in 1505 with the capture of the maritime coastal areas. Regarding religion, strong Roman Catholic links were established in the form of parish schools. These served as hubs

⁹ Sahadevan, P., "The Case of Indian Tamils of Sri Lanka", *World Affairs: The Journal of International Issues*, vol. 2, n. 2, 1992, p. 59

¹⁰ Karunaratne, N., "The Battleground of Sri Lankan History Education: Barriers to Teaching Inclusive Histories", *International Centre for Ethnic Studies*, 2021, p. 35

¹¹ Karunaratne, "Battleground of Sri Lankan History Education", p. 35

¹² Little, *Labouring to Learn*, pp. 22-23

for religious conversion.¹³ Sinhala and Tamil remained the primary languages of instruction, but Portuguese and Latin were taught as subjects in colleges. This developed the seeds of an elite educated class that were well-versed in European languages and religions. On the other hand, Indigenous Buddhist, Hindu, and Muslim schools were officially discouraged to promote this European identity along the colonised maritime areas of Sri Lanka.¹⁴

In 1658 the Dutch displaced the Portuguese and were the colonial rulers of Sri Lanka until 1796. The Protestant Dutch Reformed Church led this period and hid certain rights behind faith. For example, only those baptised in the Dutch Reformed Church and whose parents were married in one may inherit land.¹⁵ Regarding education, Sinhala and Tamil remained as the primary language of instruction. There seemed to be little interest in teaching Dutch to the native populations. The three key maritime ports at the time of Colombo, Galle, and Jaffna all saw an extension of the parish school system established by the Portuguese.¹⁶ Whilst there is little documentary evidence of the social composition of those who participated in education at the time, there is evidence that they relied on an existing hierarchy of 'native officials' for their colonial administration. Moreover, this approach perpetuated a system of social status based on a moulded version of the pre-existing caste system.¹⁷

4.1.2 Early British Era

Following the takeover of Sri Lanka from the Dutch into British hands, there was a renewed need for political stability. The lack of an economic surplus and a general philosophy of laissez-faire did not predispose the nascent colonial government to support social welfare. Indeed, this lack of interest in social welfare mirrored that of policy in the metropole. State-run education systems were not fully established there at this time, with factory owners given the onus of educating their child labour.¹⁸ The only remnant of a policy that was pushed by the colonial government was directed towards conversion to Christianity through toleration and encouragement of the work of the missions. Indeed, missionaries represented the 'one consistent agent of change' at this time.¹⁹ Promotion of a laissez-faire attitude as well as the support of missionaries is a method of rule that encapsulated all British policy in the early years. From education to systems of recruitment for Indian Tamil labourers, faith in the free hand of free-market capitalism ruled Ceylon under the British during the nineteenth century.

¹³ Little, *Labouring to Learn*, p. 72

¹⁴ Little, *Labouring to Learn*, p. 72

¹⁵ Little, *Labouring to Learn*, p. 73

¹⁶ Little, *Labouring to Learn*, pp. 73-74

¹⁷ De Silva, K. M., *A History of Sri Lanka*, London, Hurst, 1981, pp. 345-356

¹⁸ Musgrave, P. W., *Society and Education in England since 1800*, London, Methuen, 1968, p. 6

¹⁹ De Silva, K. M., *Social Policy and Missionary Organisations in Ceylon, 1840-1855*, London, Longmans for the Royal Commonwealth Society, 1965, p. 5

A change from the Dutch in education policy, however, was a focus on utilising education for determining social status. Before the annexation of Kandy, two layers of school developed. Firstly, a 'superior layer' was developed along the maritime areas of Sri Lanka, comprising education centres including that of preparatory feeder schools for high-caste Sinhalese, Tamils, and Dutch Burghers. Students were also taught exclusively in English.²⁰ An 'inferior layer' comprised the parish schools established under the Dutch. The primary method of instruction was either in Sinhala or Tamil, not English.²¹ This split in education established a status and caste-based system of government education where elites had more access to the upper strata of society.

By the time of the annexation of Kandy, the realm of education had been overtaken by the religious sphere over the course of centuries of colonial influence. The growth was remarkable. Baptists were established in 1812, Wesleyans in 1814 and the American Ceylon Mission in 1813 were all established to spread Christianity amongst the native populations. Further, the Colombo Academy recruited young men for subsequent employment in the colonial administration and from 1814 it admitted a small number of village youth for preparation as teachers for the church.²² Support for missionary-led education came from the governor of Ceylon, Governor Brownrigg. He and his wife were keen on religious conversion with a missionary-supported system running in parallel with government-financed schools. Indeed, this support began a colonial tradition on the island in which the wife of the governor would become the ex-officio patron of charitable activity in Ceylon.²³

4.1.3 The Importance of Governors in the Early Years of British Rule

The aforementioned need of the British colonial government for an economic surplus meant that state control on education was minimal. However, almost paradoxically, this did result in the whims and wants of the governors of Ceylon being critical to the development of the social sphere not least until the remnants of professionalisation in 1833 with the Colebrook-Cameron Commission. Through analysis of the governorships of Robert Brownrigg and his successor Edward Barnes on education, the broader interplay of language and religion on colonial rule will illuminate how the hierarchies of power established by the British were felt in education across all strata of society.

Robert Brownrigg's governorship of British Ceylon was principally characterised by the annexation of Kandy in 1815 as well as the resulting fallout leading to the 1818 Uva-Wellassa Rebellion. Due to Kandy's eminent position in Sinhalese society, an apparent concession was

²⁰ Little, *Labouring to Learn*, p. 74

²¹ Little, *Labouring to Learn*, p. 74

²² Little, *Labouring to Learn*, p. 75

²³ Little, *Labouring to Learn*, p. 75

made with implications for education on the island. The Sinhalese-led Buddhist practices were declared 'inviolable' whilst its 'ministers and places of worship' were 'to be maintained and protected'.²⁴ However, following the rebellion the Sinhalese Kandyan were removed from power and parity was given to all religions in the country, including Islam, Hinduism, and Christianity. This paved the way for missionary work and education among the up-country Sinhalese.²⁵ Brownrigg was initially hesitant to open up the Kandyan heartland to a plurality of religions. Eventually, however, he made a political judgement and proclaimed that 'the people were willing to listen to them.'²⁶ This shift not only broke the political power within the Kandyan heartland but allowed for different missionary groups to influence this space through the development of religious schools.

The governorship of Edward Barnes between 1820 and 1832 was primarily predicated on invigorating the colonial export economy rather than the promotion of Christianity and the English language.²⁷ While tolerating the work of the English missionaries he was antagonistic toward the 'foreigners', by which he meant the Americans, working in Jaffna. He even went as far as refusing to allow a member of an American missionary to take up residency in the country.²⁸ In correspondence regarding this matter, he stated that 'the means we possess in our own country for the conversion of our heathen subjects to Christianity are in the Lieutenant Governor's opinion fully adequate to all purposes.'²⁹ This statement reveals several facets of the state of the laissez-faire system at the time. Firstly, Barnes' comment reflected his own personal support of Christian missionary education, contrasting with Brownrigg's pluralistic attitude to missionary education. Consequently, this shift in attitude emphasises how under a general philosophy of laissez-faire social welfare initiatives such as that of education can be affected to a large degree by the individual governors.

The policy of non-intervention into education by Britain both in the metropole and in Ceylon began to change with the release of the Colebrook-Cameron Commission. Motivated by the prohibitively high cost of employing English staff throughout the colonial administration, it was determined that the best course of action was to develop through English language education a local loyal elite that were rendered morally and intellectually competent to fill offices of trust.³⁰ Immediately this meant that the low-country Sinhalese and Tamils who attended colonial education in the maritime provinces were at an advantage. Moreover, education was being used as an instrument of control over the hereditary Kandyan elites who had lost power over a decade before but still represented a threat to British hegemony due to their symbolic status.

²⁴ Ruberu, R., *Education in Colonial Ceylon*, Kandy, The Kandy Printers Limited, 1962, p. 121

²⁵ Little, *Labouring to Learn*, p. 76

²⁶ Ruberu, *Education in Colonial Ceylon*, p. 127

²⁷ Little, *Labouring to Learn*, p. 76

²⁸ Little, *Labouring to Learn*, p. 76

²⁹ Ruberu, *Education in Colonial Ceylon*, p. 130

³⁰ Little, *Labouring to Learn*, p. 79

In the end, this commission represented the first steps away from a laissez-faire philosophy of control to a more professional, bureaucratic approach. Education was used in such a manner for three reasons. Firstly, the creation of an English-speaking local elite would mean the business of government could be carried out at a lower cost than before. Secondly, they would theoretically be bound by feelings of loyalty and gratitude to the British for the favour and recognition that was bestowed upon them. Finally, the creation of such a group would bring about the slow erosion of the influential symbolic power of the old hereditary elites.³¹ These factors coalesced into a tangible difference with Governor Barnes and created some tension. The stress on using English at all levels of administration, including in schools, was repeated multiple times in the report. Schools were recommended to change any vernacular methods of instruction to English. In particular the American missionaries were commended by the commission as a positive influence due to their focus on using English in their teachings, especially when compared to the English missionaries. Its overall recommendation to leave teaching through vernacular language to the missionaries was criticised by outgoing Governor Barnes. His argument, in line with his overall aim of increasing the economic surplus of Ceylon, was that this would leave too much power in the hands of the clergy and their mission of conversion rather than advancing 'civilisation'.³²

Ultimately, these misgivings not being considered reflect the changing power of the governorship of Ceylon. Over the following decades vernacular education in government schools plummeted whilst missionaries and other educational entities embraced vernacular education. Civil administrative roles were filled predominantly with Dutch Burghers, Jaffna Tamils, and low-country Sinhalese people. Whilst the continuing prevalence of European migrants are represented here, what is key for British control is the low-country Sinhalese. Their new high-status jobs through English language education were at the explicit expense of the Kandyan Sinhalese deposed during the Uva-Wellassa Rebellion. Ceylonese society through education had morphed dramatically in favour of the British hierarchy of power due to an expansion of the English language to favoured groups. In only benefiting those deemed suitable by the British colonial government, this dawn of education professionalisation in Ceylon further exacerbated inequalities for those deemed unworthy of such status in colonial society.

4.2 Estates, Education, and Exclusion

As previously mentioned, Governor Barnes' time in office was defined by the need to overturn the lack of an economic surplus in Ceylon. Pertinently this led us to the migration of Indian Tamil peoples to work on the coffee plantations. They entered a system that had a clear caste system moulded by the British colonial government. Moreover, their lives on the plantation estates were

³¹ Little, *Labouring to Learn*, p. 79

³² Little, *Labouring to Learn*, p. 80

the result of unfettered capitalism brought about by a laissez-faire ideal. For the planter, the aim was to extract the maximum profit for himself in the shortest possible period of time. To do this they were huddled together in insanitary huts as small as twelve feet for ten people. Wages were low and not paid regularly while the sick were driven off to die on the side of the road. Any protest to these conditions were regularly 'silenced by blows and personal restraint.'³³ Within this environment a semblance of education found itself on the plantations. What follows is an analysis of how the plantation education system during the coffee plantation-era reproduced the colonial hierarchies of power and laid the foundations for the social inequalities felt by the Indian-origin Tamils in Sri Lanka today.

There were three main types of school that were established during this early period of coffee plantation. These were run by Kanganies, missionaries, or planters. Each school was run by a different subsection of society, and they were consequently defined primarily by their individual aspirations with the school. Whilst these aspirations differed, they each used to varying degrees language and religion to reproduce the divisions within society kept the Indian Tamil from climbing the proverbial social ladder.

4.2.1 Kanganies

The Kangany, as discussed in previous chapters, played a vital role in the organisation of new recruits. As well as labour recruiter, manager, and money lender, they also played the role of educator.³⁴ Two different types of school were established during this time which reflected and reproduced the social division of labour within the estate.³⁵ The first type of school was exclusively for the children of Kangany as well as 'staff' on the estate, which excluded the Indian Tamil plantation workers. Reading, writing, and arithmetic were taught here alongside some English. The second type of school was known as a 'line school'. Here the sons of labourers or the labourers themselves could take part. Education here reflected the traditional Tamil *thinnai pallikudam*, or verandah school, which was prevalent in southern India and Jaffna at the time.³⁶ The Kangany teacher also had the role of relaying written information to the students as they were illiterate. This included reading letters sent from their homes in South India as well as reciting *puranas*, ancient histories which are a core part of their religious identity.³⁷

The vast majority of these schools were line schools, as Kanganies and estate 'staff' usually chose to send their children to schools run by missionaries. Some historians came to describe line schools as a communal effort of self-help in which those in the community came together to

³³ Gnanamuttu, G. A., *Education and the Indian Plantation Worker in Sri Lanka*, Colombo, G. A. Gnanamuttu, 1977, p. 4

³⁴ Little, *Labouring to Learn*, p. 103

³⁵ Gnanamuttu, *Education*, p. 15

³⁶ Little, *Labouring to Learn*, p. 103

³⁷ Little, *Labouring to Learn*, p. 103

provide a service. In doing so they 'kept the community together, preserved its institutions, its values and its unwritten codes of conduct, and were a bulwark against disintegration'.³⁸ This is certainly true to an extent. The communities were kept together in school while the teaching of the *puranas* kept their religious traditions alive. However, the idea that they were 'self-help' is not strictly true. The Kanganies were of a higher caste and therefore held a more secure standing in society. This was exacerbated in the long-term due to their children being taught English as well as skills that allowed for employment outside of the plantation.

Moreover, as Angela Little points out, the middle of the nineteenth century was the height of the seasonal labourer. Plantation workers were returning home with frequency due to coffee being a seasonal plant. Labour was migrating between India and Ceylon regularly in numbers regularly reaching above fifty thousand annually in this period.³⁹ The fact that these labourers and their families were members of two communities and two systems of cultural reproduction may also explain the way line schools operated. Retaining the same cultural identity in the Indian village as well as in the plantation could explain the response to the educational efforts of Kanganies by the indentured labourers.⁴⁰

4.2.2 Missionaries

Following the Colebrook-Cameron Commission and its associated approval of missionary-led education, Christian missionaries began working in the plantations in the early 1840s. The earliest was that of the Baptists under one Reverend Dawson. He obtained permission from other planters for his Baptist workers to enter his plantation on a weekly or fortnightly basis.⁴¹ This was unusual, however, as most planters denied entrance to the Baptists. This could have been due to the fact that many of the early planters in Ceylon had come from Jamaica. As a result, they had a labour rights model that was consistent with slavery rather than indentured labour. Also, and perhaps most key, was that another source of resistance arose from religious conflict. Many of the planters were Anglicans who possessed 'no disposition to encourage the labours of the Baptist Mission'.⁴²

One which was to assume greater importance in the provision of education in the estates from 1854 was the Anglican Mission, or the Tamil Cooly Mission (hereafter TCM). This mission was more successful than the former not only because it aligned with the religion of the majority of planters. They were funded from a wide variety of Christian sources, including merchants, Indians, those with interests in labourers in London, plantation labourers, staff and Kanganies,

³⁸ Gnanamuttu, *Education*, p. 16

³⁹ Little, *Labouring to Learn*, p. 104

⁴⁰ Little, *Labouring to Learn*, p. 104

⁴¹ Little, *Labouring to Learn*, p. 105

⁴² De Silva, *Social Policy*, p. 270

and Ceylonese Christians in the towns surrounding the emerging plantations.⁴³ This wide array of funding sources is indicative of the general interest in British colonial society at the time for missionary work in the name of Christianity.

The schools established by the TCM, much like the ones established by the Kanganies, replicated and reproduced societal divisions along social and economic class lines. The key difference here, though, is the children of plantation staff and Kanganies could attend schools that were not within the geographical boundary of the plantations. The hill-country towns of Kandy and Badulla were popular destinations, as was Colombo on the west coast.⁴⁴ The schools for the children of labourers were established within the plantations, thus establishing a spatial-social differentiation that still exists to this day. Reversing the trend from the Kangany schools, the TCM schools were more popular with those more privileged in society due to their position outside of the plantation. Unlike the children of the indentured labourers, they were economically freer and therefore could afford the time to attend schools outside of the plantation area. Further, it was reported in the first report of the Tamil Cooly Mission in 1857 that the poorer children had 'little inclination to learn' after working ten hours a day.⁴⁵ This gap in ability to learn severely influenced the future of these children purely depending on the class of their parents.

Moreover, the general consensus on plantations at the time that 'children who were old enough to learn were old enough to work' was an issue taken up by this same report.⁴⁶ This was identified as an issue for educational attainment but also highlights the motivations of the planters at the time. They were mere 'speculators' who hired superintendents with 'no or very poor education' to take care of the plantation. They had very little interest in social welfare areas such as education as they were adventurers, 'a motley crew in search for a quick buck'.⁴⁷ The primary motivation of these planters was primarily profit, and providing education to the labourers was seen as a waste of resources. As a result, education was mostly placed in the hands of the TCM whose religious morals they aligned with.

4.2.3 Planters

⁴³ Little, *Labouring to Learn*, pp. 105-106

⁴⁴ Gnanamuttu, *Education*, pp. 18-26. The author here provides details on the vast spread of missionary schools at this point in time. For example, the TCM was responsible for the opening of the Kandy Bazaar school in 1858, as well as the Badulla Boys' Day and Boarding School in 1872, which later became Uwa College. Boarding schools in Colombo were also established through them for 'Christian children from up-country districts', which included the separate Borella Boarding Schools for girls and boys in 1867 and 1875 respectively. The latter would provide education to fill roles such as conductors, tea makers and clerks for the estates, as well as produce teachers, priests and trade union leaders more generally.

⁴⁵ Little, *Labouring to Learn*, p. 106

⁴⁶ Little, *Labouring to Learn*, p. 106

⁴⁷ Forrest, D. M., *A Hundred Years of Ceylon Tea, 1867-1967*, London, Chatto and Windus, 1967, pp. 36-37

Planters were generally sceptical of education in its worth for them and their profits. Indeed, some saw education as antagonistic to the supply of cheap labour for their estates. However, some planters saw a well-rounded workforce as a benefit to their estate, therefore pursuing positive education policies.⁴⁸ One such example is that of A. M. Ferguson, a Scottish planter who had been described as a planting pioneer of the 'most dauntless kind' as he was responsible for the clearing of large areas of forest in Uwa.⁴⁹ In the 1840s he established Abbotsford Estate in Lindula, in which he set up a school for the education of his labourers. Elsewhere, as described earlier, some planters were happy to donate to the TCM as this not only promoted an Anglican society but put the onus of education off the planters themselves.

A modest government subsidy, named 'grant-in-aid', was offered to planters to encourage estate education. This followed J. S. Laurie's investigation into education on the island as the newly appointed Director of Public Instruction in 1869. Including a section on estate schools he recommended that the obligation of education should mirror that of factory owners in Britain, namely that it should be mandatory for them to provide primary education to their child labourers.⁵⁰ This recommendation was not followed, but the aforementioned grant was offered to planters. This represented the first and only government intervention into education on the plantations for decades to come. Some did indeed take this offer up. One particularly enthusiastic recipient was one A. T. Rettie, manager of Spring Valley Estate in Badulla. Establishing Spring Valley Mixed School in 1886, he stated how the advantage of this works both ways. For himself it results in better workers, whilst for the labourers themselves it presents opportunities for better employment opportunities in the plantation as well as the ability to write letters home to India.⁵¹ Interestingly, A. T. Rettie's reasoning for educating his workforce wasn't strictly philanthropic as his primary motivator was to invest in his labour force to create a better equipped workforce. Evidence suggests that he recognised that the harsh conditions found on most plantations at this time reduced profits in the long run.

It is important to note here that the planters willing to become involved in education were few and far between. They tolerated the work of the missionaries but saw education largely as an expense that went against their primary reason for being: profit. Furthermore, this lack of agency regarding education is indicative of the way in which the Indian indentured labourers were continually placed at the bottom of society for decades. The laissez-faire attitude displayed by the planters allowed the policies of the British colonial government to deepen the divisions in society over time. The split in language and religion demonstrated by the two types of school that were established in the plantations highlight this. Those in a higher societal position could go to school and learn English in a Christian environment. These factors accompanied with the

⁴⁸ Gnanamuttu, *Education*, p. 73

⁴⁹ Forrest, *A Hundred Years*, p. 194

⁵⁰ Little, *Labouring to Learn*, pp. 109-110

⁵¹ Little, *Labouring to Learn*, p. 111

chance to learn reading, writing, and arithmetic allowed them to learn skills to apply for jobs not in hard labour. On the other hand, those children of the indentured labourers were forced to work in the day and had no access to opportunities that would give them the chance to leave a life of hard labour. This broad reality for indentured labourers would not change for decades, though the policies that would lead to the change began earlier.

4.2.4 Plantation Education Repercussions

Education within the plantations is defined clearly by both metaphorical societal boundaries as well as the physical which reinforced existing divisions within society. Those separated from wider society, namely the Indian Tamil labourers on the plantations, had their destinies laid out for them from birth through the education they received. A lack of access to English language education meant they could not pursue higher class jobs in the colonial government. Moreover, the education they received from the Kanganies in 'line schools' was of a traditional Tamil nature. Despite being useful for retaining their cultural and aiding community cohesion between the labourers, it further reinforced their marginalised position within society at that time. The physical division they had from wider Ceylonese society also ended up creating rifts between the Tamil people within Ceylon. Tamil teachers based in Jaffna generally regarded the estate Tamil language as 'coarse and corrupt' whilst also claiming that they had a more refined teaching of Hinduism over those in the plantations.⁵² This rift illustrates how physical division between people can also accentuate an 'othering' between people of the same ethnolinguistic group. Official government statistics do well in illustrating how the hierarchies of power were reproduced and replicated through education. Only forty-three schools were recorded as being officially open in estates in 1904. Of those only five had been started by planters, despite the best efforts of a minority of planters such as Ferguson mentioned earlier. Two were set up by the government and thirty-six by missionaries.⁵³ The heavy reliance on missionary schools indicates that the planters mirrored the government's philosophy of laissez-faire economics. Profit was the main incentive; therefore, any social program was left to the invisible hand of the free market. Moreover, the silence in these statistics speaks volumes. There were 299 'line schools' operating at this time that were not recognised in these official statistics.⁵⁴ The omission of these indicate that these were not seen as institutionally legitimate educational facilities. This not only underscores the importance bestowed upon a Christian English language education by the British colonial government but also highlights the marginalisation of groups deemed of a lower social class. In turn any official governmental education policy would not incorporate the plantation labourers and therefore distance them from the rest of the Ceylonese society. This disregard of

⁵² Little, *Labouring to Learn*, pp. 55-56

⁵³ Little, *Labouring to Learn*, p. 112

⁵⁴ Little, *Labouring to Learn*, p. 112

an entire societal group for decades provided the backdrop for their sidelining in post-independence society along two key societal indicators: language and religion.

4.3 Long Shadows

The roots of inequalities established during this time set the tone for how the 'professionalisation' of education would manifest itself. These policies set the tone for a variety of intersectional conflicts. English-language versus vernacular instruction, Christian versus Indigenous religious schools, inside versus outside the plantation and, in post-independence Ceylon, a Sinhala versus Tamil conflict that was partly defined by linguistic and religious differences. The following analysis of the 'long shadows' deriving from the coffee-era educational policies will explore the effects of both governmental policy and religious education on the Indian Tamil population. In doing so it will demonstrate specifically how two commissions in the colonial period nurtured existing divisions before highlighting how an exclusionary linguistic policy in the post-independence period was used to further the Sinhalese Buddhist standing in post-British Sri Lankan society.

4.3.1 The Professionalisation of Education: The Wace Commission

The first indicator of the professionalisation of education deepening divisions within colonial society is that of the Wace Commission in 1905. Outside of the plantation this commission signalled an expansion of free Sinhala and Tamil schools, compulsory education for boys, and increased freedom regarding religious education. This latter point included religious teachings being dependent on consent of parents, as well as restricted hours of religious education. The cost of this expansion of education was to be borne by the government, with the exception that Village Committees were to still bear the cost of new school buildings, as well as extensions to existing ones.⁵⁵

One of the key aspects of this commission was the expansion of vernacular education facilities for the population as a whole. This led specifically to an expansion of vernacular-medium schools as well as the introduction of compulsory education in densely populated areas.⁵⁶ This was due to local pressure groups wishing for an increased focus on indigenous languages in an era in which school curricula being more relevant to the Ceylonese socio-economic context was more favoured.⁵⁷ British opinion was also aligning with this. Colonial administrator in India Lord Curzon's views were oft quoted in this regard. He stated that English should be taught to those who are qualified to learn it, but it should be secondary to the role of the Indigenous languages.

⁵⁵ Gnanamuttu, *Education*, p. 35

⁵⁶ Little, *Labouring to Learn*, p. 89

⁵⁷ Little, *Labouring to Learn*, p. 89

This is due to the fact that no one will ever use another tongue with as much freedom and ease than his own.⁵⁸ This alignment of values between the urban Ceylonese and the British indicates how decades of Ceylonese influence in the colonial administration can benefit the indigenous population, albeit those with more means.

The expansion of education at this time did not go unnoticed by the planters. Indeed, they were worried about the increased cost of such an enterprise and voiced their discussions regularly between themselves in *The Planters' Association* meetings. On 5th October 1928, a particular planter states that 'if government insist on compulsory education the estates should be relieved of a great part of the expense which they are at present called upon to bear in this connection'. Costs such as 'floor space ten square feet per child is too much', 'desk and bench accommodation is unnecessary' while 'trained teachers are difficult to get'.⁵⁹ As shown earlier this antagonism toward education and its associated costs on the estates was shared by the majority of planters. One of the unchanging factors during British occupation of Ceylon is that the general view of the planters towards the indentured labourer was not that of welfare, but of the relationship between and the maximisation of capital and labour.

Regarding education within the area of the plantation, the Wace Commission took a much more hands-off approach. The commission categorically recommended to not enforce 'any rigorous system of compulsory education during fixed hours'. This was enforced with the general view that the education of the children of Tamil 'coolies' should not 'form part of the local organisation'. The recommendation by the commission was to carry on with grant-in-aid schools whilst accepting that the vastly more popular 'line schools' were sufficient for educational purposes.⁶⁰ Indicating the sufficiency of the 'line schools' falls in line with the general recommendation of an increase in vernacular education in wider Ceylonese society. It also signals how the language of instruction in education can be used simultaneously as a tool of empowerment and as a prohibitive measure. In the case of those outside of the plantation who may have received a more comprehensive education over the decades, it can be both a source of pride and, as will be seen later, a driver for a nationalist movement. Inside the plantation, however, the restrictive and insufficient level of education attained here means that vernacular education reproduces a colonial hierarchy of power, made worse through commissions such as that of 1905.

A minor form of government intervention was recommended, however. Inspectors were to certify boys on the plantation to see if they had reached a certain standard in reading, writing, and arithmetic. If indeed they had, they would be deemed 'as being in need of no more learning'.⁶¹ Whilst this puts some pressure to achieve a certain academic level, the idea that

⁵⁸ Little, *Labouring to Learn*, p. 195

⁵⁹ Minutes of the Meetings of Subcommittees of the Planters Association of Ceylon from Mar 1926 to Mar 1929, Colombo, 5 October 1928, Sri Lanka National Archives (hereafter SLNA) 248/2

⁶⁰ Gnanamuttu, *Education*, p. 35

⁶¹ Gnanamuttu, *Education*, p. 35

learning would stop before a child would be an adult suggests that the priority was still with the planter and the ability to utilise an able-bodied workforce to maximise profits.

The educational opportunities for girls on plantations at this time was even bleaker. Girls were encouraged to not partake in education and focus on home chores or labour in the fields. This resulted in, of the entire population of schoolchildren on the plantations in registered estate schools, a mere ten percent being girls in 1903.⁶² Whilst some exceptions existed, such as A. T. Rettie's estate schools in Badulla having 25% of their enrolled schoolchildren being girls, the trend was clear.⁶³ Education on the estates was not only built to favour the profits of the plantation owners, but reproduced gender divides that placed greater importance on education for boys over girls.

4.3.2 The Professionalisation of Education: The Donoughmore Commission

As explored in previous chapters in this thesis, the Donoughmore Commission paved the way for the extension of the franchise in Ceylon. This in turn led to radical changes in all areas of society, not least in education. Access to, control of, and use of language in education were all shaped by this period of Ceylonese history due to the extension of the franchise. This new era also meant that, on the recommendation of the Donoughmore Commission, education would be under the control of an elected minister. This brought education for the first time completely under state control, marking an end to the slowly eroding philosophy of *laissez-faire* that had defined education policy in Sri Lanka during British rule. The person to lead this role at this most critical juncture was Dr. C. W. W. Kannangara, known as the 'father of free education'. He was a Christian Sinhalese by birth but, after spending time studying it, he made the unusual move at the time to convert to Buddhism in 1917.⁶⁴ When leaving his role as Minister of Education in 1947, he had led through the transition to an independent Sri Lanka from British rule.

One of his key moments in office involved appointing a committee in April 1940 composed of local educationists to investigate the faults in the education system. The Kannangara Committee, as it was popularly named, met regularly over a span of three years. Four major defects were highlighted that had developed through over a century of British rule, including noting the division in society between an English-speaking elite and the 'multitude' who spoke only Sinhala or Tamil. It also noted how equality of opportunity was lacking due to the existence of fee-levying schools creating a barrier to quality education that only the rich could afford.⁶⁵ Indeed, in the

⁶² Little, *Labouring to Learn*, p. 196

⁶³ Little, *Labouring to Learn*, p. 182

⁶⁴ Little, *Labouring to Learn*, p. 90

⁶⁵ Gnanamuttu, *Education*, p. 39. The four major defects can be summarised as follows: the existence of two types of education according to the medium of instruction, creating a division in the country between an English-speaking elite and the 'multitude' speaking only Sinhala or Tamil; the purely academic nature education that was unfit for the needs of the country, creating a class of educated unemployed; an absence of equality of opportunity as only the

mid-1940s Kannangara addressed this by underscoring the fact that whilst vernacular education was fee-free, English-medium instruction was not. As the highest paid jobs required a good knowledge of the English language, he argued that the most gifted child could get 'no higher than to the comparatively unremunerative posts of a vernacular teacher, an ayurvedic physician or a notary'.⁶⁶ The resulting Free Education Act of 1945 was passed, opening up education completely to every child between the ages of five and sixteen.

Whilst the recognition of the entrenched inequalities caused by over a century of British rule was valid, Kannangara failed to reference estate schools in his report or organisations that provide welfare to them.⁶⁷ Not only this, the government spending necessary to fund the opening up of education to 'all' was taken from the profits generated by the then-burgeoning plantation industry in Ceylon.⁶⁸ The deafening silence of the Indian Tamil voice at the dawn of an independent Sri Lanka has roots in British Ceylon. However, it is also indicative of the replication of power structures that would occur in an independent, Sinhalese Buddhist dominated Sri Lanka.

4.3.3 Sinhala One and Only

The silence of the Indian Tamils embedded into a society shaped by British colonial policies not only extends into independent Sri Lanka but is utilised to further certain groups' interests within society. To begin with, the Citizenship Acts of 1948 and 1949 required citizens to have ten years of uninterrupted residence in Ceylon, as well as an income above a certain level. This excluded most Indian Tamils from citizenship.⁶⁹ Without citizenship, their state of housing, health, and education plummeted as they were not represented in any official governmental capacity. Entrenched language inequalities were used to further continue a policy of linguistic hegemony within Sri Lanka, pushing the Indian Tamil community further to the sidelines. Since its founding in 1951, the Sri Lanka Freedom Party (hereafter SLFP) has been dominant in Sri Lankan politics, associating itself primarily with Sinhalese nationalist parties. In the first few decades of its life the party ran on a campaign promoting Sinhalese dominance in society whilst also using the threat of the 'other', namely the Indian Tamils and their perceived links with India, to rally support.⁷⁰ This push for a Sinhalese-dominated society was crystallised in the Sinhala Only Act. Passed in parliament in 1956, this piece of legislation made Sinhala the sole official language of the country.

well-to-do could afford to attend the better, fee-levying schools; an absence of any provision to compel school attendance, as the law itself was lax. School attendance was also deemed low due to a paucity of schools, poverty and parental apathy.

⁶⁶ Little, *Labouring to Learn*, p. 91

⁶⁷ Gnanamuttu, *Education*, p. 39

⁶⁸ Gnanamuttu, *Education*, p. 39

⁶⁹ Jayawardena, K. and Kurian, R., *Class, Patriarchy and Ethnicity on Sri Lankan Plantations*, New Delhi, Orient Blackswan, 2015, p. 210

⁷⁰ Jayawardena and Kurian, *Class, Patriarchy and Ethnicity*, pp. 210-211

In turn, it excluded Tamil from being an official language.⁷¹ This policy represents the Sinhalese nationalist movement not only seizing power for themselves in a post-colonial society, but utilising the blueprint of linguistic dominance laid down by the British through politics of exclusion. Much like in British Ceylon, the higher-class jobs would be restricted to those who knew a particular language. Severe rioting and communal violence occurred, as well as mass internal migrations of Tamil and Sinhalese people. As a result, an amendment was passed in 1958 providing for the use of Tamil for administrative purposes in Tamil-dominated regions, as well as a medium of instruction in secondary and higher education.⁷²

Attempting to create a barrier to education through linguistic hegemony inspired pushback from multiple non-Sinhalese groups. For example, A. M. A. Azeez was a Muslim Ceylon civil servant born in the northern regions whose goal was to increase literacy rates of Muslim people as he noticed their fall by the wayside. He was highly critical of the Sinhala Only Act, as this was passed in the context of many senators discussing the idea of one race, one language, and one religion. More specifically, he noted how Tamil-medium schools were planned to be discontinued and the teaching of Sinhalese made compulsory in them.⁷³ Further, he speaks of the disadvantage a Ceylonese Tamil-speaking boy would have going to school using Tamil but then, if he wishes to go to university, he would have to switch to Sinhalese.⁷⁴

Elsewhere different schools around Sri Lanka set up to preserve their own identities under the British found themselves fighting the same fight in an independent yet Sinhalese Buddhist state. Manipay Hindu College, established to help Hindus who were being forced to convert to Christianity and western values, is a prime example of this. In literature celebrating fifty years of existence in 1960, the Principal references the fact that there are political developments in the country to 'take over' schools such as his to impress a Sinhalese identity on the island. He noted that the Sinhalese found stoking anti-Tamil sentiments through educational attainment was a shortcut to power.⁷⁵

These examples display how educational attainment is found in the middle of the cross-section between language and religion in both the colonial and independent eras. These two factors were consistently utilised by both the British and the Sinhalese to consolidate power within the island. Pertinently, in the pushback to the latter's Sinhala Only Act, there was no mention of Tamil workers on the estates. The archival material in the archives focused on the plight of the

⁷¹ Ismail, Q., "Constituting Nation, Contesting Nationalism: The Southern Tamil (Woman) and Separatist Tamil Nationalism in Sri Lanka", in Chatterjee, P. and Jeganathan, P. (eds.), *Subaltern Studies XI: Community, Gender and Violence*, London: Hurst & Company, 2001, pp. 234-236

⁷² Britannica, "Sinhala Only Bill", <https://www.britannica.com/place/Sri-Lanka>, last date of consultation 31 December 2024

⁷³ Addresses and Articles of Mr. AMA Azeez, Articles 26-52 (9 May 1938 - 23 June 1957), Colombo, 8 May 1956, SLNA 25.17/3

⁷⁴ Addresses and Articles of Mr. AMA Azeez, Articles 26-52 (9 May 1938 - 23 June 1957), Colombo, 3 July 1956, SLNA 25.17/3

⁷⁵ Manipay Hindu College Golden Jubilee 1960, Colombo, 4 July 1960, SLNA 25.17/12

Ceylonese or, in the case of A. M. A. Azeez, the Muslim Tamil. The Citizenship Acts of 1948 and 1949 relegated Indian Tamils to the fringes of independent society and thus left them powerless to provide a voice to the fight against Sinhalese power consolidation.

4.3.4 The Question of Citizenship

The statelessness deriving from the Sinhalese-led Citizenship Acts in the late 1940s sharpened the isolation felt by the Indian Tamil plantation community. Looking at the voting populations in key Indian Tamil constituencies in elections before and after these acts, it is clear to see how their political power was reduced drastically. In Nuwara Eliya, the total eligible voting population was cut from 32,798 in 1947 to 12,551 in 1952. Talawakelle has an even steeper drop from 26,054 to 3,934.⁷⁶ These statistics highlight not only the removal of rights the population suffered at this time, but also the physical divisions put in place between Indian Tamils and the rest of the country.

The nature of their stay in Sri Lanka had also become more sedentary. No longer were they returning home to South India regularly to see their families. Now, it was common for their families to join them on the estates. Many knew nothing of India as they had resided in Ceylon for generations working on the plantations with their families. As early as 1929 N. J. Luddington, the Controller of Indian Immigrant Labour, stated that 'of the Indian estate population of 740,130 people, 242,161 were men, 232,996 were women, and 264,973 were children.' He goes on to state that this is 'satisfactory' as it means that family life is 'almost universal amongst adult Indian estate labourers in Ceylon.'⁷⁷ Indeed Sir Edward Jackson, a one-man Commissioner appointed in 1936 to report on labour immigration from Ceylon to India, noted that many have 'severed their connection with India and have become permanently settled in Ceylon.'

Rejecting citizenship to the majority of estate Indians left a million people stateless. Due to their Indian origins this was framed as an Indo-Sri Lankan issue and culminated in an Indo-Ceylon conference beginning in New Delhi on 24th October 1964 between Indian Prime Minister Lal Bahadur Shastri and Sri Lankan Prime Minister Sirimavo Bandaranaike. After six days of negotiating Shastri agreed to grant citizenship to 525,000 people, Bandaranaike 300,000 and the other 150,000 people would be decided at a later date. This pact was named the Sirima-Shastri Pact.⁷⁸ Progress in migrations was slow. Due to administration delays on the part of Sri Lanka, many people who applied for Indian citizenship had to wait years for their application to be processed. For example K. Sithuravelu, on the eve of his expatriation to India on 11th February 1979, stated that his departure was 'delayed for years due to the local authorities' incapacity or

⁷⁶ Ramesh, R., "Party Politics in the Plantation Community: Growth and Changes", in Shastri, A. and Uyangoda, J. (eds.), *Political Parties in Sri Lanka: Change and Continuity*, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2018, p. 290

⁷⁷ Nadesan, S., *A History of the Up-Country Tamil People in Sri Lanka*, Colombo, Ranco Printers and Publishers Ltd., 1993, p. 84

⁷⁸ Nadesan, *Up-Country Tamil People*, p. 191

unwillingness to clear the formalities.⁷⁹ The question of citizenship, and therefore the question of giving state-given rights to Indian Tamils, was formally resolved in 2003 when the Sri Lankan parliament passed the Grant of Citizenship to Persons of Indian Origin Act. This gave citizenship to all Indian Tamils and their descendants who had lived in Sri Lanka since the Sirima-Shastri Pact in 1964.⁸⁰

Many who moved from Sri Lanka to India did so because of the poor living conditions they found themselves in. K. Sithuravelu, even after stating that he knew nothing about India, noted that the primary reason for his family to move from Sri Lanka was not the lack of latrines or electricity, but the closure of the school for his three children. Now they had to descend five kilometres to the new school that was assigned to them. The impracticality of this meant no education was available for his children.⁸¹ Notably, poor living conditions were the same reasoning people had for leaving the Tamil Nadu region of India to come to Ceylon in the nineteenth century. Decades of underfunded public services meant that the families who resided on the estates were stuck in an increasingly hopeless situation exacerbated by the Sinhalese leadership of Sri Lanka. Being able to claim citizenship after 1964 was a positive step in being able to fight for change. However, the systemic issues they found themselves in led to situations similar to K. Sithuravelu and his family in which there was a chronic lack of access to basic resources such as toilets and food, while access to education was severely limited.

4.3.5 Tamil Fractures

Deepening divisions between Tamil peoples residing in Sri Lanka developed largely due to the expansion of the education system outside of the plantations. Running parallel with the Sinhala Only Act, this meant that there were many Indian Tamils who had been educated through the Sinhala medium and some who could not read Tamil. Moreover, there are thousands of people born of mixed parents, Indian Tamils and Sinhalese, whose native language is Sinhala.⁸² As explored previously, differences in the language of instruction in schools severely restricted the opportunities afforded to Tamil children on the estates. The Indian Tamils who lived outside of the estates, therefore, had more opportunities to pursue higher paying jobs.

This attainment gap due to language was known. All trade unions associated with plantation workers agreed that Sinhalese should be taught to the Tamil children on the estates. President of the Ceylon Plantation Workers' Union stated at a rally in 1962 that whilst all estate children

⁷⁹ Fries, Y. and Bibin, T., *The Undesirables: The Expatriation of the Tamil People of Recent Indian Origin from Plantations in Sri Lanka to India*, Calcutta, Bagchi, 1984, p. 1

⁸⁰ Lawnet, "Grant of Citizenship to Persons of Indian Origin (Amendment)", https://www.lawnet.gov.lk/wp-content/uploads/Law%20Site/4-stats_1956_2006/set6/2003Y0VOC35A.html, last date of consultation 2nd January 2025

⁸¹ Fries, *The Undesirables*, p. 1

⁸² Nadesan, *Up-Country Tamil People*, p. 197

should be taught in their mother tongue, they should learn Sinhalese as a second language 'thereby helping to end isolation which imperialism has sought to impose on the workers on estates.'⁸³ A resolution adopted from this time expanded upon this idea, urging the government to nationalise all estate schools and integrate them into the national system of education. A stipulation to this was that all children on the estates would be taught in their native tongue, be it Sinhalese or Tamil.⁸⁴

Ceylon Tamils, those who had resided in Sri Lanka for thousands of years, also benefited from the physical barrier between estate and wider society. Access to more opportunities through the privilege of living outside of the plantations and being able to go through an education system that afforded benefits in later life can be seen through one S. Sivanson. A Ceylon Tamil, he applied for a position at Ceylon University in the 1920s due to his father moving back to Ceylon after receiving his pension in Kuala Lumpur. He had many documents, all in English, from past school teachers in Ceylon praising him and his abilities.⁸⁵ His mastery of the English language hints at his family's wealth and therefore the quality of education he received as a child. His experience with education compared with an estate Tamil around the same period, who had to go to a 'line school' while also doing hard labour the same day, is stark.

Highlighting the differences in the Tamil experiences in Ceylon underscores the limitation of analysing education along simply ethnic lines. Multiple factors come into play, including ethnicity, religion, language, and caste amongst others. Living inside or outside of a plantation, however, is a good indication of the opportunities you received, be that under British Ceylon or Sinhalese-dominated Sri Lanka.

The Indian Tamil's experience with education under both the British colonial government and post-independence Sri Lanka was one of scarcity. A lack of time, money and power were defining features that were the result of decades of oppression. Revisiting Galtung's theory of 'structural violence', in which he states that violence can be done by institutions to limit one's freedom, similarities and continuities can be seen between British and Sinhalese rule. The laissez-faire philosophy that permeated British Ceylon allowed for the unfettered hand of capital to wreak havoc on social policy in the plantations. The Kangany-led 'line schools', for example, were structured through circumstance. The traditional Tamil style of school was familiar to all involved, students and teachers, while the students' illiteracy meant the Kanganies served to relay messages from home. The lack of government intervention into estate schools would not change for decades. Indeed, Angela Little argues that the 'provision, or lack of, education was due to lack of government intervention rather than the nature of the plantations'.⁸⁶ This is only partially true. Whilst lack of government intervention was an issue, the nature of estate management also led

⁸³ Nadesan, *Up-Country Tamil People*, p. 196

⁸⁴ Nadesan, *Up-Country Tamil People*, p. 197

⁸⁵ 1868, Letters from Director General of Ceylon Govt Railway to Col Sec, Papers Relating to Reduction in Transport of Coffee from Kandy, Peraderiya and Kadugan, Colombo, SLNA 11/114

⁸⁶ Little, *Labouring to Learn*, p. 104

to poor educational facilities. With only a few exceptions, most plantation owners cared primarily about profits and saw an educated labour force as undermining the 'guarantee of a ready supply of cheap labour.'⁸⁷ Particularly in the early days, many of the planters had come from plantations of enslaved peoples in Jamaica, so their thoughts on the welfare of the indentured labourers ran thin.

Structural violence can also be seen at the dawn of newly independent Sri Lanka with the Citizenship Acts of 1948 and 1949. Creating a stateless mass of people, composed mainly of Indian Tamils on plantations, meant that their ability to improve their living conditions was cut drastically. Through the removal of citizenship rights the labourers were unable to seek better opportunities outside of the plantation through education. Moreover, the wide attainment gap that had developed since the first migrations of Indian Tamils into Ceylon meant that the removal of their rights distanced them even from other Tamils in society.

The idea of the 'triangle of oppression' put forward by Berch Berberoglu, composed of class, race, and gender, can be modified here to apply to the Indian Tamil experience with education specifically. Whilst these three are applicable through actors such as plantation owners or Sinhalese people, it is crucial to add one more factor: physicality. In the estate, the Tamil relationship with the physical boundaries of the plantation was one of restraint and ostracization. Life inside the plantation meant very little education policy would directly affect you. If you were Tamil and lived outside the estate, you had a much greater chance to be taught in a language or through a religious lens that suited what you wanted.

Finally, the alternative 'triangle of oppression' of religion, class, and caste is more fitting to fit analysis of the education of plantation workers. Religion and class, which embodies language due to its link with wealth and opportunity, are found to be vital factors throughout. Whether under British or Sinhalese rule, the dominant religions of Christianity or Buddhism would always be favoured in society. A similar story can be found with language, be it English or Sinhalese. Caste is something more ingrained. Throughout Sri Lankan history caste has played an important role. In fact, the colonial period of Sri Lanka is sandwiched between two periods of Sinhalese dominance. What is important to note here, however, is that the caste system was morphed and used by the British to implement their own hierarchies of power. Buddhism was replaced by Christianity, Sinhalese by Buddhism, even Kandyan Sinhalese by other low country Sinhalese after the Uva-Wellassa rebellion of 1818. The reproduction and replication of these power structures, and therefore the oppression of the Indian Tamil indentured labourers, was forged in education and cemented into society.

⁸⁷ Little, *Labouring to Learn*, pp. 142-143

Conclusion

5.0.1 Indian Tamils and Civil War

The Sri Lankan civil war between 1983 and 2009 was fought ostensibly between the Sinhalese and Tamil ethnic groups on the island. It spoke to a generalising truth that masked the intersectional complexities at play within this Indian Ocean island. Sinhalese dominance in post-independence Sri Lankan society is well-known. Adopting Sinhalese as the official language in the country in 1956 and the elevation of Buddhism to constitutional status in 1976 resulted in the linguistic and religious pillars of the country to broadly exclude the diverse Tamil population.¹ However, on the other side of the conflict led by the Liberation Tigers of Tamil Eelam (hereafter LTTE) were policies that were similarly exclusionary to the Indian Tamils in Sri Lanka. Investigating this exclusionary activity by the LTTE will highlight how the introduction of these people from South India was not only a disruptive influence on colonial-era Ceylon, but also served to sharpen pre-colonial divisions resulting in recent modern conflict.

On May 14 1976 the *Vaddukoddai Resolution* (hereafter VR) was adopted by the LTTE and declared for the first time in history a demand for a separate Tamil state, named 'Eelam'.² This form of legitimisation in the post-colonial era has been dubbed "the most universally legitimate value in... political life".³ This demand stemmed from the idea that Tamils have always seen themselves as having a nation within Sri Lanka, specifically where they have historically been the majority in the northern and eastern areas.⁴ The strict borders imagined by this Tamil nationalism excluded the Tamil-speaking people living outside of these borders, including the majority of the disenfranchised Indian Tamils on the estates. They are offered citizenship in this new state, but the reservations of Tamil groups about estate Tamils are noted in the VR. These reservations made by Ceylon Workers' Congress derive not only from a strict perception of nationality requiring habitation in the northern and eastern Tamil regions, but questions over their 'Tamilness'.⁵ Whilst giving the concept of 'Tamilness' the anthropological care it deserves is outside the scope of this thesis, it is pertinent to consider a trend here between habitation and identity. The idea of 'Tamilness' here partly refers to the perceived difference between the Tamil people who have lived in Sri Lanka for thousands of years as opposed to those who migrated to work on the plantations in the 1830s. Questioning the level of 'Tamilness' based on geographical

¹ Hennayake, S.K., "The Peace Accord and the Tamils in Sri Lanka", *Asian Survey*, vol. 29, n. 4, 1989, p. 404

² Ismail, Q., "Constituting Nation, Contesting Nationalism: The Southern Tamil (Woman) and Separatist Tamil Nationalism in Sri Lanka", in Chatterjee, P. and Jeganathan, P. (eds.), *Subaltern Studies XI: Community, Gender and Violence*, London, Hurst & Company, 2001, p. 227

³ Anderson, B., *Imagined Communities: Reflections on the Origin and Spread of Nationalism*, London, Verso, 1991, p. 3

⁴ Ismail, "Constituting Nation", p. 234

⁵ Ismail, "Constituting Nation", pp. 241-242

and temporal habitation meant that the VR was inherently prejudiced against the estate Tamil workers and therefore replicating historic grievances against them.

Initially non-antagonistic, the LTTE reversed this policy with regards to VR after an anti-Tamil pogrom in 1983 instigated by the Sinhalese. This escalated to violence erupting on both sides. As a result, the establishment of Eelam was predicated on the belief that the only alternative to separation was genocide.⁶ An aggravation of motivation such as this had a severe knock-on effect on the already partially shunned Indian Tamil population. The violence against Tamil people around Sri Lanka was now utilised by the separatists to justify their own violence in the civil war. This resulted in the policy of the LTTE requiring, acknowledging, and accepting the pogrom against Tamil people outside of the boundaries of Eelam. This resulted in the Indian Tamil now being outside of the project. A necessary outside, one that was needed for the separatist project “to both justify and impel itself”.⁷

Eelam being a Tamil nation was, on the face of it, inclusive. However, the exclusion of the Indian Tamil from the ‘Tamil’ cause was anchored in colonial-era policies that physically separated them from the rest of society in the plantations. The physical distance was compounded by their harsh treatment and lack of government intervention into their social services that meant they were for the best part of a century and a half socially trapped. Further, their disenfranchisement at the hands of Sinhalese nationalism and bloody sacrifice at the altar of Tamil nationalism indicates how considering the civil war as one fought simply along ‘ethnic’ grounds is limiting.

5.0.2 ‘Flattening’ the Estate Worker

Considering the limitations of looking at the Indian Tamil experience along only ethnic lines, it is worth revisiting why intersectionality is important considering the research presented in this thesis. Akin to labelling one as simply ‘gay’ or ‘black’, collapsing the ‘Tamil’ identity into one results in one's true nature being lost.⁸ In an administrative sense this did happen under the British. From the beginning of census operations in Sri Lanka in 1871 until 1911 Sri Lankan Tamils were lumped together with Indian Tamils.⁹ This is indicative of a certain ‘flattening’ of identity under the British colonial government during the entirety of the coffee-era plantations and into the twentieth century.

Whilst this can partially be attributed to ignorance on the part of the British, this thesis proposes a more accurate explanation for this ‘flattening’ is linked with the archive. Archives are teeming

⁶ Ismail, “Constituting Nation”, p. 267

⁷ Ismail, “Constituting Nation”, p. 268

⁸ Johnson, V., “Solutions to the Silence”, in Thomas, D., Fowler, S., and Johnson, V. (eds.), *The Silence of the Archive*, London, Facet Publishing, 2017, p. 146

⁹ Suryanarayan, V., “In Search of a New Identity”, <https://web.archive.org/web/20080529221016/http://www.flonnet.com/fl1816/18160950.htm>, last date of consultation 7 January 2025

with records of the rich and powerful. *The Planters' Association*, a network of primarily rich, white, European men, is prevalent in the archive. Minutes of meetings and their correspondence is available to represent their side of the story. A similar story can be said of the British colonial government, as well as those in powerful positions in public institutions such as schools. This strict adherence to representing the views of the rich and the powerful in society offers an ordered view of both society and the people who ran it for the scholar. This naturally excludes "the messy, the ephemeral and the voices of the people who are not 'like us'".¹⁰ The somewhat 'messy', or to use a preferred term 'intersectional', nature of the Tamil identity in British Ceylon was 'flattened' then to contemporarily order society under the moulded hierarchies of power and temporally illuminate a clean and ordered view of British colonial society.

However, the 'flattening' of the Tamil identity under an intersectional lens helps to illuminate the Tamil experience. Consider the case of the Sri Lankan Tamil applying for university in Ceylon in chapter four.¹¹ He has reams of documents pertaining to his educational history and application to Ceylon university from Kuala Lumpur in Malaysia, all of which were in English. This, along with his status as a Sri Lankan Tamil, indicates a life of wealth and opportunity in British colonial society that simply was not afforded to the Indian Tamil plantation worker. This example underscores how intersectionality can illuminate the existence of the subaltern. By considering factors of identity such as religion, language, gender, and caste amongst others the colonial 'flattening' of identity can be reversed. In this way, the voices of the 'messy' subaltern voices can be excavated.

5.1 Identity through Time

Pertaining to the concept of this 'flattening', this thesis' main goal has been to demonstrate the multifaceted nature of the Indian Tamil indentured labourer's inclusion in the historical flow of Sri Lanka. Initially motivated primarily to fulfil an economic need of the British, these migrants found themselves within and adapting to the multitude of intersectional identities existing in British Ceylon and independent Sri Lanka. What follows are some concluding thoughts regarding the Indian Tamil experience as well as where this has led them to in the modern day.

5.1.1 Identity in Colonialism

The experience of the indentured labourer within the colonial period was marked by a slow shift from a laissez-faire style of control to a more professional, bureaucratic form of control. This shift worked in tandem with the hierarchy of power established by the British to promote and subjugate those the colonial power deemed helpful or a threat, respectively. For example, due

¹⁰ Johnson, "Solutions to the Silence", pp. 17-18

¹¹ 22/05/1945 - 02/05/1946, Correspondence Between Ceylon Government Rep in Malaya and Individuals Registered Ceylon Uni Admissions, Colombo, SLNA 71/340

to the Uva-Wellassa Rebellion following the annexation of Kandy in 1815, the low-country Sinhalese were promoted over the rebellious and religiously symbolic Kandyan Sinhalese. The British achieved this for two main reasons, each of which also laid the groundwork for the Sinhalese to dominate independent Sri Lanka.

Firstly, it is important to note that the 'professionalisation of institutions' is simply another way to say the 'Europeanisation of institutions'. This idea stems from the idea that India as a concept that the independence of the nation state of India as a concept would not have been possible by the colonisation of 'Indian' institutions.¹² A European notion of national identity was used in both instances as a unifying ideal. For Sri Lanka this meant that English was preferred over Sinhalese or Tamil to conduct the most well-respected business in. This included not only government business but also the best schools, meaning social advancement was tied to a European language. Access to this education became increasingly more widespread under the British. The successive commissions from Wace and Donoughmore expanded on the seeds of professionalisation laid by the Colebrook-Cameron Commission several decades prior. Increased government intervention was made possible by the establishment of governmental as well as educational institutions that mirrored that of the metropole.

However, the benefits of government intervention in this era of professionalisation never reached the estate workers in a great or meaningful way. Education within the estate was largely kept within the 'line schools' established by kanganies. Travelling to school was often a laborious task, while the education received resembled that of a traditional Tamil school. Education existed, but it served to widen the attainment gap already existing in a fractured Sri Lanka due to the lack of opportunities presented by the 'line schools' on the plantations. The hierarchy of power and its associated divisions was sharpened by the widening gap between those embedded in the 'professionalised' institutions developed by the British, and those lacking the help of governmental intervention. This reproduced and replicated existing divisions in society.

Secondly, the exacerbation of divisions between Indian Tamils and the rest of society was aggravated by the physical divisions put in place by the plantations themselves. Due to the nature of what they were producing on the plantations, particularly tea from 1880, the labourers were forced to occupy the up-country regions surrounding Kandy including Nuwara-Eliya and Badulla. The historically richer areas of Sri Lanka associated with maritime activity such as Colombo or Galle contained more Sinhalese and Sri Lankan Tamil people. This physical split not only allowed for the deepening of societal divisions due to the spread of governmental intervention but was compounded by the harsh treatment afforded to the workers by the planters. The punishments

¹² Anderson, P., "Gandhi Centre Stage", *London Review of Books*, vol. 34, n. 13, 2012, pp. 3-11; Krishna, G., "The Development of the Indian National Congress as a Mass Organisation, 1918-1923", *The Journal of Asian Studies*, vol. 25, n. 3, 1966, p. 413. These two texts discuss how India was united through culturally unifying aspects such as Hindu culture and acts of rebellion in everyday actions through abstinence from consuming colonial economic products respectively. This unified people across territories determined by colonial powers and their national consciousness developed reflecting a European model

administered were harsh, particularly for those who were pushed to leave and decided to 'bolt'. The physical geographical location of the Indian Tamil, then, intensified the social divisions placed on them by the colonial hierarchies of power.

Cultural fractures were also highlighted because of these physical and metaphorical rifts separating Indian Tamils from much of Ceylonese society. Having only recently migrated from South India to Ceylon, there were some differences in language and religion that had developed over time. A Tamil teacher from Jaffna in the north of Ceylon was noted to have regarded estate Tamil language as "coarse and corrupt".¹³ Moreover, Sri Lankan Tamils considered themselves to have a more refined teaching of Hinduism over that practised by Indian Tamils. Physically dividing these groups whilst keeping one side trapped in a cycle of debt, trapping them to a life on the estates, meant that divisions were allowed to not only exist but widen. The 'flattening' of the Tamil experience under the British in the nineteenth century masked a complex picture of inclusion and exclusion that fed into the simmering nationalism harboured by the Indigenous populations of Sri Lanka that exploded in the latter half of the twentieth century.

5.1.2 Identity in Independence

Whilst the focus of this thesis has been principally an analysis of the experience of the Indian Tamils under the British in the nineteenth century, it is important to historicise their experiences into the present day. This paracolonial lens has been implemented into the historical analysis of each chapter considering the long shadows put forth by the coffee-era in the plantations. This thesis' concluding thoughts here will highlight how the colonial identity of the Indian Tamil was influenced by and was shaped by an independent Sri Lanka, both before and after its colonial period. In doing so a marked continuation will emerge, highlighting how the indentured labourer's experience was defined not simply by colonialism. Instead, the pre-colonial hierarchies that existed were sharpened by colonialism, were made less pluralistic, and found form in a nationalism that excluded the Indian Tamils.

As detailed in chapter one, pre-colonial Sri Lankan society was marked by a Sinhalese Buddhist-dominated society that tolerated religious pluralism as long as they were acknowledged as the rightful rulers of the island. Moreover, slavery was not only a key part of society but was seen as honourable. Intrinsicly linked with religion and power, servitude represented a way to serve both the ruler and the religion at once through serving in temples or royal spaces. Manumission was common, highlighting that you had done service to the entwined entity of religious power. The flashpoint of Portuguese colonialism marked a shift that cast a long shadow over the island's history. Along the maritime coastal areas the Portuguese used language and religion to encroach on the system of power the Sinhalese elites had cultivated for centuries prior. Parish schools were

¹³ Little, A., *Labouring to Learn: Towards a Political Economy of Plantations, People and Education in Sri Lanka*, Colombo, SSA, 1999, pp. 49-51

established, serving as hubs for religious conversion. Additionally, whilst Sinhala and Tamil remained the primary languages of instruction, Portuguese and Latin were taught as subjects in the newly formed colleges.¹⁴ Together, these represented the nascent beginnings of the professionalisation of institutions found under the British. Moreover, this encroachment served to sharpen Sinhalese Buddhism. As evidenced by Alagiyavanna's texts in chapter one, the Sinhalese became less inclusive and welcoming of other religions as they were seen as a threat to their power. Kandy came to represent the sharpened nature of Sinhalese Buddhism and was revered by Buddhists around the island until the annexation of Kandy three centuries later by the British.

The post-colonial era saw the reemergence of a Sinhalese-dominated Sri Lanka. From this point in the late 1940s Sri Lanka was a nation state with fully functioning governmental and educational institutions run primarily by leaders whose educational background was western. For example, S.W.R.D. Bandaranaike, the Prime Minister of Ceylon who introduced the Sinhala Only Act in 1956, read Classics at Oxford. Meanwhile Dudley Senanayake, Prime Minister of Ceylon from 1960, was educated at Cambridge.¹⁵ The elites in post-independent Sri Lanka were not only educated in fundamentally colonial institutions in Western forms of knowledge but were representing Sinhalese interests. The resulting policies, such as the Sinhala Only Act, reflected a return to a Sinhalese dominant society that had become less inclusive in its outlook due to the adoption of Western governmental institutions and nationalisms.

This adoption of a less pluralistic and antagonistic form of rule displayed by the Sinhalese compared with the pre-colonial era had a knock-on effect on the Tamil population. As discussed before, 'Tamilness' is a complex concept, and one that has only briefly been touched upon here. However, here Sri Lankan Tamils and Indian Tamils, those who migrated from the 1830s to work on the plantations, will be treated as two separate groups due to multiple decades of diverging fortunes in colonial and post-colonial society.

Sri Lankan Tamils mirrored the Sinhalese in adopting a western-style nationalistic fervour based on exclusion. In their adoption of VR, and subsequent call for civil war following the anti-Tamil pogroms of 1983, there was a marked departure from the system of subordinated harmony they found themselves in in pre-colonial times. Strict physical boundaries were marked with the proposed state of 'Eelam', whilst religious and linguistic boundaries were set due to Eelam being a Tamil state. This was a post-colonial imaginary that was born out of a rejection of centuries of domination by the Sinhalese and the British. Plurality was lost as the hardened shell of nationalism took shape in this imagined community.

Where did the Indian Tamils fit into this rigid caricature of identity? Their 'Tamilness' in the shape of a shared religion and language was crucified on the altar of the needs of an alienating colonial

¹⁴ Little, *Labouring to Learn*, pp. 72-74

¹⁵ Fernando, T., "Elite Politics in the New States: The Case of Post-Independence Sri Lanka", *Pacific Affairs*, vol. 46, n. 3, 1973, p. 371

economy. Decades of separation, mistreatment, and neglect in the midst of a 'professionalising' Sri Lanka led to a Tamil identity marked by difference, caused by exclusion. Their introduction to the island was a divisive one whose split from society was exacerbated post-independence by their position at the bottom of the Sinhalese and Tamil nationalistic powers of hierarchy.

5.2 Long Shadows: Agency in Identity

The nationalisms that emerged out of the colonial period inherently supports the silencing of voices such as those of the Indian Tamil. The LTTE, for example, actively used the pogroms against the Tamil people outside of the boundaries of Eelam to support their cause. Nationalism thrives on differences of identity. The Indian Tamil struggles in this arena of nationalism marked by differences in language and religion show actions of agency that not only reflect the fractured society they find themselves in but the non-binary nature of such differences.

Indian Tamil people, excluded and marginalised in a society their families moved to generations ago, experienced a complex tale of conflicts stemming from paracolonial tensions whilst seeing evidence of a disregard for historical baggage. Take the experience of Saroja Solomon, for example. She is a Southern Tamil whose house was destroyed and property vandalised during the pogrom. Solomon later stated that a Sinhalese neighbour kept her and her family safe, a Muslim neighbour drove them to a refugee camp, and an old Sinhala school friend who lived nearby provided refuge from life in the camp.¹⁶ This highlights a reality much more complex on the local level than the grandiose and overly simplistic binary of Sinhala versus Tamil.

Further, Tamil identity is distorted in the face of subjugation. Solomon stated that she did not want to be identified as Tamil through language or appearance. She only spoke Sinhalese to her family at home and encouraged them to marry Sinhalese people. Further, she refused to wear the traditionally Tamil Indian *sari* and *pottu* in public.¹⁷ Her rejection of both Tamil identity and engaging with Sinhalese customs outside of the language demonstrates a rejection of the binary choice of Sinhalese and Tamil nationalism. This method of rebellion echoes the limited forms of rebellion exhibited by the indentured labourers in the plantations. In an environment of subjugation, refusal to participate was common. Absenteeism for the indentured labourers or rejection of cultural norms for Southern Tamils such as Solomon were ways to sustain oneself in the face of hardship.

Another example would be that of Kamala. Like Solomon, she faced violence in the pogroms in southern Sri Lanka and did not find a home in Sinhala or Tamil nationalism. Neither form of nationalism allowed her to express herself freely, and her identity as Southern Tamil was used by these two oppressive powers to further a post-colonial agenda of exclusion. Her choice of

¹⁶ Ismail, "Constituting Nation", p. 272

¹⁷ Ismail, "Constituting Nation", p. 274

resistance was emigration.¹⁸ A link to 'bolting' here, whilst somewhat disingenuous, can be fruitful as it reflects in a similar way a form of resistance that ran through time in the geographical region of the plantations. Whilst the bolting of the labourer was usually to another plantation for debt reasons, the bolting to New Zealand, in the case of Kamala, reflected a way to start afresh, to express oneself freely outside of oppressive nationalisms.

What these experiences of Southern Tamils highlight, as Valli Kanapathipillai notes, is that "local level events... are grafted onto national events by reasons of continuity".¹⁹ Or in other words, every incidence of violence has a 'local' dimension distinct from the national.²⁰ The rather 'flattening' tale of Sinhala and Tamil nationalism masks a story of agency and rebellion performed by local level actors every day. The stage for the Indian Tamils in Sri Lanka was built from centuries of historical nationalisms that were shaped for the modern day by colonial intervention. The 'messy' nature of the local, however, calls for a reconstruction of identity away from the temptations of binary definitions and into intersectionality. Achieving this will go some way in the championing of subaltern peoples whose experiences are buried under the weight of the powerful.

¹⁸ Ismail, "Constituting Nation", pp. 276-277

¹⁹ Kanapathipillai, V., "July 1983: The Survivor's Experience", Das, V. (ed.), *Communities, Riots and Survivors in South Asia*, Delhi, Oxford University Press, 1992, p. 327

²⁰ Ismail, "Constituting Nation", p. 268

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